

D8.6: Public Engagement and Communication Activities Report

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Deliverable Development and Review Process

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Executive summary

This document (D8.6) reports on Project Ô's public engagement and communication activities, providing context and details on the structure, content, and execution of the activities and events, as well as key findings. Here, we describe how the communication strategies and actions for the project have developed to cover external communications (including website, videos, events, social media, etc.), event management and internal communications since The Institute for Methods Innovation (IMI) joined the project as a partner during Reporting Period 2. These strategies were then implemented by IMI, under the work package leadership of Professor Alexander Gerber (Rhine-Waal University of Applied Sciences).

A broad range of communication activities, both internal and external, were designed and implemented by IMI. Examples of these activities include refreshing the project website, developing media assets (such as bi-fold and tri-fold brochures, slide deck templates, infographics and visual explanations of project demosites and technologies, signage for demosites, and numerous high-quality project videos, overhauling the project brand assets including the logo, etc.), creating content and managing social media accounts (including planning and scheduling for Twitter, Facebook, YouTube and LinkedIn), as well as project newsletters (internal and external, including content creation, design and dissemination).

The goal of the public engagement co-creation events was to engage non-expert communities in the project, with a focus on co-creation. These co-creation workshops with the public were conducted in Italy, Israel, Spain and Croatia with local community members around project demosite areas. Furthermore, two online international public engagement events were organised and facilitated to build awareness of good practices developed through the project relating to international public engagement, research impact and science communication. The Institute for Methods Innovation team had to take responsibility for planning and delivering these activities and events to ensure their success. In addition, demosite representatives attended the public engagement events. The international events IMI organised were aimed at extended professional networks interested in water sustainability-related topics. These events were in extremely high demand, gaining almost 600 participants.

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Abbreviations

WWTP	Wastewater Treatment Plant
WTT	Water Treatment Technology
DoA	Description of Action
RP	Reporting
WP	Work Package
EC	European Commission
EU	European Union
IMI	Institute for Methods Innovation
SWOT	Strengths, Weaknesses, Opportunities and Threats
SDGs	Sustainable Development Goals

Introduction

This report provides an overview of Project Ô public engagement and communication activities undertaken within Work Package (WP8): Communication and Stakeholder Management. This strategy development, communication and event management work has been conducted by the Institute for Methods Innovation, under the Work Package leadership of Professor Alexander Gerber (Rhine-Waal University of Applied Sciences).

We begin this Deliverable by presenting communication strategies (T8.3), which guide the implementation of the external and internal project communications (T8.5 and T8.6) and event management (T8.7).

T8.3 Communication Strategies

T8.5 External Project Communications

T8.6 Internal Project Communications

T8.7 Event Management

In the first main section of this deliverable, we describe the strategic framework IMI developed for key tasks. This framework saw production of a greatly improved website, vastly expanded range of visual media (including videos, photos and illustrations), and a highly coordinated social media engagement campaign, as well as design, data collection and analysis of public engagement co-creation events across all project demsites.

This report shows how the project's aims of developing effective communication and upstream stakeholder engagement were realised in practice. A number of high-level aspirations for the internal and external communication of the project were foreseen in previous deliverables (D8.2; D8.3). These previous deliverables kicked off the process of developing objectives for the communication plans for the project. IMI prepared detailed objectives and strategies for aligning project activities to the needs of stakeholders in and around each demonstration site, as well as wider beneficiaries of the project's work.

In this deliverable, we present the public engagement and communication work that has been completed since these previous deliverables to develop impactful communication strategies, create engaging external project communications, develop and deliver public events to enable

co-creation and local stakeholder participation and internal project communication to help to update the consortium and ensure its different work streams are well aligned.

(T8.3) Communication Strategies

The communication strategies for Project Ô have been developed to cover a range of channels (including website, videos, events, social media, etc.) for sharing information and resources with external audiences, internal stakeholders and public engagement. This groundwork was first described in the Stakeholder Analysis (D8.2) and Communication Strategy (D8.3) deliverables, submitted early in the project, which clarified objectives and broad aspirations for targeting messages to project-relevant audiences. In this section, we present key aspects of our work in Task 8.3 Communication Strategies, which helped to shape the delivery of subsequent tasks.

These communication strategies have since been developed by the Institute for Methods Innovation (IMI) after the organisation joined Project Ô as a partner part-way through the second reporting period (RP2). The Work Package (WP) leadership provided by Prof. Alexander Gerber (HSRW) has supported this work to develop communication guidelines and ensure the effectiveness of communication activities, especially during the third reporting period (RP3) for the project. The communication strategies were developed by IMI, based on clarified objectives and employing established best practice in science communication, stakeholder management and public engagement (e.g., see Jensen & Gerber, 2020).

The action plan helped at a practical level to maximise communication and engagement with internal and external audiences, which has included management and delivery of a range of public engagement events (see T8.7) for each demonstration site. Communications were aligned with the expressed hopes in D8.2 and D8.3 deliverables to emphasise the economic, environmental, and societal implications for the implemented technologies and transition to circular water management. Furthermore, stakeholders from European Commission agencies and institutions, sister projects¹ related to Project Ô and the broader circular water sector, were engaged in a wide range of demosite-specific communications. In the rest of this section, we present key communication strategies that have guided our work.

¹ ICT4WATER cluster projects

Strategies for external communications

Website strategy for external communications

The website is a critical hub for an EU-funded initiative such as Project Ô. It is expected to cater to the needs of non-technical public audiences while accurately representing the project's work and *raison d'être*. A basic prototype placeholder version of the website was launched by HSRW during the project's Reporting Period (RP) 1 as a starting point early in the project to facilitate initial discussions about content and layout strategy. The main website strategy development and implementation commenced when IMI joined the project in RP2 to make sure it would meet the communication needs of the project. This included addressing issues such as improving the communication of important ideas that needed to be easier to understand for non-technical audiences. In RP3, the placeholder website was replaced with a new look and feel, navigation and page structures. The theme was completely re-designed, including custom CSS and plug-ins development. Additionally, text and visual content were created and added to the website to elaborate on and illustrate the ongoing research, technologies, and demosites and setting up project databases. This required multiple meetings and iterative development of proposed communications with the scientific and technical partners to find phrasing that was satisfactory for them, while providing clear communication to non-technical audiences.

As part of IMI's website strategy development work, a SWOT (strengths, weaknesses, opportunities and threats) analysis was conducted on the placeholder project website to compare with other water-related websites, and identify strengths and weaknesses, opportunities and threats to an effective website for this project. Screenshot examples of good practice in particular were identified for inclusion in the strategy to inspire the website designers. Here, we present the SWOT analysis results and rationale for the creative process required to produce a greatly improved project website. We then provide a detailed account of how the website needed to be developed to meet project needs.

Figure 1. Placeholder version of Project Ô website

This website strategy was presented to Work Package leader Professor Alexander Gerber for his feedback prior to implementation by IMI. Although the Description of Action states that the 'project website will be constructed and managed by the coordinator', because IMI had the relevant technical and communication expertise, it took on full responsibility for delivering this aspect of the project.

Please note that the material below is future-oriented because it was drafted prior to the main development of the website.

IMI's Website Strategy

Website Purposes

The website should be designed to be the public hub of Project Ô and provide access to the greatest depth of information (compared to other communication sources). For example, this allows the latest headlines to be shared on social media and linked to the full story on the website. This will ultimately drive traffic to the website and encourage web visitors to dwell on the site.

The website should be referenced by all partners in relevant communications, again fulfilling the role of being a deeper source of information than their original communiqué. The website should share results and scientific innovations, where appropriate, as well as raise awareness of achievements

and project milestones, while shining a light ahead towards future developments in the project and beyond.

Following an assessment of communication objectives in the project documentation, the IMI team has identified a number of ways to ensure the website can more effectively address the needs of project stakeholders in both internal and external communications. For example, the website in particular can act as a place for resources or materials relevant to public engagement events, co-creation workshops with stakeholders, policy briefs and science advocacy.

Finally, the website is a contributor to the project's overall success. Freely providing key information to the general public and interested groups can help them understand, engage and hopefully accept the solutions provided by the project. For example, it is important for communication strategy to dispel the stigma around "re-used" water, which has been identified as a potential barrier. As a digital instrument, the website can have unique interactive capacities that can help play a key role in stakeholder engagement and dissemination of project outputs.

Website Development Plan

A website must be visually appealing to encourage a user to explore based on curiosity. The content itself then must be accessible, informative and fit for purpose. It is suggested that the website is improved in the following areas:

1. *Visual appeal*

- 1.1. Navigation
- 1.2. Layout & Colour
- 1.3. Illustrative Media & Videos

2. *Content*

- 2.1. Breadth and type of content
- 2.2. Accessibility of language

1. Visual appeal

Navigation

The current (pre-IMI placeholder website's) navigation method in the placeholder website relies on a menu bar found at the top of each page. While this is a common approach to navigation, there are some opportunities to improve page behaviour. For example, users can only scroll down on each page to read content and then back up to navigate to other areas. This is not an optimal structure or behaviour for navigation.

It is suggested that this top navigation and menu bar, including the project logo, remains the main navigation method while including additional features to improve page structure and behaviour. For example, the project logo can replace the hyperlink to the "Home" page, which is standard practice and visually streamlines the menu bar. The size of the logo in the placeholder website is currently lacking 'visual confidence' and should be larger and bolder to facilitate this adjusted hyperlink. The top menu bar should also follow the user down the page to remain accessible at the top of the screen on all pages. Once the user has scrolled down the page, the height of the top menu can be decreased and made less visually dominant, as per an example on the digital-water.city² website.

Once users click into a section, user experience with a sub-navigation can be an improvement through a column on the left-hand side. This lists the relevant subsections links to help users navigate the page and creates a more accessible column or grid layout with a defined body area for the content. Examples of this navigation method can be found on the Incover³ project website and digital-water.city mobile site, as shown below.

² <https://www.digital-water.city/digital-solutions/>

³ <https://incover-project.eu/>

Figure 2. Incover Project website

Figure 3. Digital Water.City mobile site

Layout and Colour

Alongside navigation, the layout of a website affects accessibility and ease of interaction and therefore correlates to how long users will engage. The current placeholder website has a full page of text that expands to the width of the screen. Moving from larger screens to mobile devices, this creates a full page of text and results in an uncomfortable reading experience. To resolve this issue, the area available for text should be restricted to stay within comfortable boundaries. This can be aesthetically achieved using columns, “cards” or text boxes. Examples of this can be seen on the [Smart Water Supply Systems news page](#)⁴, [Scorewater team profiles](#)⁵ and this article on the [Guardian newspaper](#)⁶ website.

To increase prominence of project branding and improve aesthetics, a defined border can be used to frame a website. This has the advantage of introducing colour to make the website more appealing and encourage dwell. Using this method over a full colour or photograph background, still allows for some areas of white space. This white space is needed to provide contrast between text colours in the foreground with background colours. This colour contrast is an important issue for legibility. A basic example is shown on the [Run4Life](#)⁷ pages and a more subtle version is on the [afrialliance](#)⁸ pages (see below).

⁴ <http://life-swss.eu/en/news-events/>

⁵ <https://www.scorewater.eu/#ourteam>

⁶ <https://www.theguardian.com/artanddesign/2020/sep/21/radical-transparency-will-rotterdam-open-museum-change-art-the-depot-boijmans-museum>

⁷ <https://run4life-project.eu/demosites/ghent-be/>

⁸ <https://afrialliance.org/action-groups>

Figure 4. Run4Life website

Figure 5. AfriAlliance website

1. Illustrative media and videos

On the current placeholder website, scarce illustrative media (which consists of videos, photos, gifs, etc.) are not well-integrated with the existing text, nor fully utilised to support comprehension from the reader. When this existing content is re-written, it should allow for illustrative media to replace or support text-based content, and vice versa. The creation of illustrative media will need to facilitate user interactions across social media platforms and build familiarity with the project when users reach the website.

Part of this effort will need to include the creation of a suite of videos. The messages in videos should be limited to one topic. This has two important benefits: First, this reduces the length of videos and helps viewers stay focused; second, viewers are provided with more choice of which video topics are relevant to them. Additionally, 'emotive language' and familiar comparisons can help viewers understand unfamiliar topics through relevance to their lives. For example, an understanding of how the 'current technology module in Croatia can fit in a wardrobe or scale to fill a football field', is a comparison that can help make content more relatable and easier to understand. Finally, videos should be tailored to specific audience or stakeholder groups, such as the general public (non-expert), technical (expert) and/or policy. For example, a policy audience may benefit from context about how water reuse connects to upcoming changes to EU legislation or regulations and how the focus of this project can help them.

The interactive and responsive natures of a website need to be utilised. For example, the current placeholder website's "Modules and Technologies" page can be improved by separating the content across a series of pages and using hyperlinks to connect them. Such improvements have high value when giving users more control over how they navigate and view content. It is also important to optimise page structure to ensure that only a small number of clicks are needed for users to reach their desired destinations.

2. Content

Breadth and type of content

As previously established, the pre-IMI placeholder website's content will require complete rewriting. Each page will address specific and important topics (or content), including revised headings, overviews and demo site/ technology-specific pages (below):

- **Homepage**
- **About**
 - a. **Background:** Origin of the project, how it is funded, why it exists, and importance of a circular water system, e.g. “re-using” water.
 - b. **Purpose:** Explains that this project is one of many [ICT4Water](#) projects working towards ‘improving access to water for all’ and the context of achieving Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) with links to the [SDG](#) website.
- **Action**
 - a. **Overview:** Explains that four demonstration sites were chosen to trial the technology and that it can be replicated in other sites (“think global, act local”).
 - b. **Site-specific pages:** The pages for each demonstration site will have the same structure that includes useful data and rationale, including location, why it was chosen and what work is happening there (may include key statistics). Illustrative media can include images and videos from each site. Also, a stream can be provided with updates from the news page. There is a need for person/people-led stories from both the project stakeholders’ and communities’ perspective).
 - i. Israel
 - ii. Spain
 - iii. Italy
 - iv. Croatia
- **Solutions**
 - a. **Overview:** Explains the technology in plain language and what it is intended to achieve. There can be reference to the ICT4Water wider programme.

- b. **Technology-specific pages:** The pages for each technology will include useful data and rationale, such as an overview of what it does, how it achieves its goal, and partner/s responsible. Further illustrative media will be provided for each solution, including simple animations showing how it works and links to news or relevant scientific papers, etc.
 - i. ADV.ERT Module
 - ii. SALTECH Module
 - iii. MOBILE3TECH Module
 - iv. PHOTO.CAT Unit
 - v. Decision Analytic Platform
 - vi. Circular Economy Platform
- **Collaboration**
 - a. **Structure:** Explains the project as an Innovation Action that must achieve economic impact with tangible products and business models. It also indicates how this project is applicable to more locations than the current demonstration sites and offers an overview of Work Packages in a clear format and with links to news pages or other project updates.
 - b. **Partners:** Explains how/why the project is a collaboration and includes the logos of each consortium partner or stakeholder. Each logo will link to their own external website.
- **Creating Change**
 - a. **Water Governance:** Explains how co-creation processes are key tools to engage current and new stakeholders to further improve institutional arrangements and water reuse management strategies. It provides an overview of the co-creation workshops in each of the demosites.
 - b. **Sustainability Analysis:** Explains how the project is evaluating if its water treatment systems are environmentally friendly, socially just, and economically viable. It provides an overview of the sustainability evaluations, including Environmental Life Cycle, Social Life Cycle, and Life Cycle Costing assessments.
 - c. **Public Engagement:** Provides an overview of the public engagement events planned with a focus on co-creation, political communication and science advocacy.

- **Resources**

- a. **Library:** Provides easy access to materials, public deliverables, newsletters and publications developed throughout the project. Each publication from the project, such as reports, newsletters, scientific papers, etc., can be accessed on a separate page and with options for viewing PDFs in-page or downloading.

- **Latest**

- a. **Overview:** Provides easy access to news, events and publications headlines [and link to archive].
 - b. **News or Article-specific pages:** Each news article can be accessed on a separate page. Additionally, articles can be 'tagged' or labelled to allow easy cross-referencing, such as with Work Packages, partners, demonstration sites, or other references that cross-link to the "About" section.
 - c. **Event-specific pages:** Each event can be accessed on a separate page. Event pages can be 'tagged' for cross-referencing.

To provide further detail on each page:

Homepage

The following three homepages are examples of good introductions and the best, applicable elements to Project Ô will be emulated: [Incover](#), [INNOQUA](#) and [MONOCLE](#). A video overview of the project should be located here. Two good examples are from [AquaNES](#) and [Smart Plant](#), which give clear explanations of what they are trying to achieve and how humour can make a video more memorable and engaging. The footer of each page should include, at a minimum, the required EU flag and project funding acknowledgement.

About

Part of the project's success relies on support from local communities. It is therefore important that the context and how water is re-used is explained and given prominence on the website. The latest behaviour change research advocates for positive framing and this should be particularly followed here. An example of context explanation can be found on the [nextGen](#) website.

The importance of reusing water can include a “reminder” of the water cycle. It can explain how water is a finite resource and that domestic, industrial and agricultural systems are all reliant on water for everyday processes. To help make it relatable, end products can be given as examples with the [Water footprint](#) website as a good example of how this can be engaging.

Referencing the SDGs and the wider ICT4Water programme helps show that this is one of many projects. The intention is to help with community acceptance and broaden the available evidence base for the success of such projects. It also benefits those working on the technical side by enabling them to connect with others working in similar fields and build a peer network.

Action

Example layout from [Smart Water Supply Systems](#) for suggested navigation and [NextGen](#) for suggested replication of identical content layout for each site and breakdown of information.

Graphics to be created can include a linked “pinned” map of Europe showing where the four demo sites are located. Users can then access location specific information on the page. This improved map will label countries (Israel, Spain, Italy and Croatia) and have pins that indicate the cities (Eilat, Almendralejo, Puglia region and Omiš). These graphics would then connect to site-specific pages with images and narratives.

To help generate site-specific narratives, ideally there would be a few people who could act as spokespeople for each demonstration location. Illustrative media using their photographs and putting text in “their” voices helps give a human perspective to the projects and make them more relatable. It also offers potential for layouts to be styled as “diaries” to show how the projects are progressing over time.

Solutions

Providing an overview of what the technology is trying to achieve helps explain the innovation action happening in the project. It’s also an opportunity to describe how this project has a “think global, act local”

perspective, as the technology trialled at the demo sites can be replicated in other locations.

Each type of technology should be given an identical but content-tailored page. This makes assimilation of information easier for the user. Simple animations can be created to show how the technology works or even video footage from the demo sites, if suitable. Pairing this content with links to partners and relevant publications will increase time spent on the project website.

It should be explored if each of the technologies can be given a mini logo. This could be used on the partner “ID cards” to simply visually link each partner with the relevant module/technology. They could also be duplicated across social media, again to increase familiarity.

Collaboration

A brief description explaining the advantages of the partnership and how they relate to each other via the work packages can be used to further increase confidence in the project and its planning process.

Currently the information about each partner is found by clicking away from the placeholder project website onto the partner’s external page. This can be improved by giving an overview of who each partner is and what their role is in the project.

Dwell time on the website can be increased by including links back to the demo site and technology pages to which they are connected. There can also be a third link to a relevant external website for each partner.

A good example of brief partner introductions can be seen on the [Scorewater meet our team](#) section.

Latest

An example layout for this page can be similar to the [Smart Water Supply Systems](#) website. Another layout example for news/article pieces can be found on the [Scorewater](#) news page.

When there is a news article to be published the full piece should be written for the website with the appropriate style abridged versions for each of the social media platforms.

Depending on the diversity of news and whether analytic data is available from other similar websites, it could be considered whether tags are helpful for searching the news section. At the most basic level they can be linked to the site, module/technology and partner. Potentially this could be hashtags to link with the social media platforms.

To futureproof the website, it's also worth considering whether an archive page should be set up and when articles are defined as old enough to be transferred over.

Accessibility of language

The reading age of the placeholder website content is too high for the public. It is possible that the pre-IMI placeholder website's content was written with an assumption about visitor knowledge that is higher than what should normally be expected for a publicly-funded project with public stakeholders. When the content is re-written, the language should be simplified to a lower reading age. Sentences should be shorter and contain only one clear topic, idea or message in order to improve the chances that users will understand the information and find it useful or shareable.

To better support assumptions that the website terminology should be accessible for the general public, this proposal ensures a clear connection between basic overviews and explanatory background knowledge, with links to more detailed information. This is designed to allow users to 'opt in' to additional detail as they require it. These terminology and content accessibility issues will be considered when re-writing the website content.

As this project is Europe-wide (and beyond), accessibility can be improved by providing alternative language versions for key aspects of the communication.

Supporting documentation

To ensure the website is kept active and the information on it is fresh and up-to-date, it can be paired with a timeline engagement plan to collect and disseminate information from project partners. This should clearly state roles and responsibilities, particularly regarding how illustrative media will be

generated. This would ensure opportunities for project photography or videos are not missed during active project work. Clearly setting out deadlines, responsibilities, standards and expectations in advance will ensure all involved understand the communication requirements they are expected to contribute to. This is particularly important for partners with person-months allocated to WP8, because failure to contribute will increase the burden on other partners (especially on IMI, which would need to ensure the work is completed to maintain project success).

Use of specialist terms or jargon

It has been highlighted through past project documentation that the language and presentation of “re-used” water is important to ensure community buy-in and acceptance. It is therefore suggested that a shared phrase book or glossary of preferred terms is created as a project resource to help partners positively discuss the project and to ensure consistency between the website, social media and partner-linked outputs.

Additionally, the language and terminology used in communications for the general public audience should be different from that used by the experts and specialists who are actively working and contributing to the project. A differentiated communication approach is critical to avoiding misunderstanding or putting off public audiences from engaging with the project. Therefore, a simplified glossary and conversion document may be useful to explain what terms should be swapped when creating external communication materials or publication documents. These purposes can be assessed when writing new content for the digital and offline materials.

Secure domain

The placeholder website is not currently showing as “Secure” when visiting. Most web browsers will alert users that something is wrong with the privacy or identity of a site’s connection. Many browsers also allow users to check for security information about a site. Lack of security can discourage users from remaining on a website.

 Secure

 Info or Not secure

 Not secure or Dangerous

Insufficient security can substantially decrease website traffic and site engagement over time. To fix this issue, a security certificate (SSL/TLS) will be installed to update the domain from HTTP to HTTPS. These security certificates are a standard encryption protocol that provides end-to-end security of data sent between applications over the Internet. It is mostly familiar to users through its use in secure web browsing, and in particular the padlock icon that appears in web browsers when a secure session is established. Ensuring that the website gains this security certificate and that it is kept updated will be a basic essential requirement to enable broader use of the website.

Social media strategy for external communications

Based on the communication goals and analysis of the identified target audiences for Project Ô, a strategic communication plan for social media was developed to guide project communication and dissemination after IMI joined as a project partner in RP2. The narrative of this document starts with an assessment of the pre-IMI status of the project's social media accounts, followed by an analysis of similar accounts. It proposes a detailed work plan for standing up the social media accounts and building an audience based on key messages, target audiences and communication channels. This document, prepared by IMI, was also designed to allow us to evaluate our efforts during the implementation of the social media strategy to see if we are generating the desired impact. This strategy was presented to Work Package leader Professor Alexander Gerber for his feedback prior to implementation by IMI.

Please note that the material below is future-oriented because it was drafted prior to the project's main effort with social media (which began after IMI joined as a partner in RP2).

IMI's Social Media Strategy

Social media status prior to IMI joining the project

A social media audit creates a clear picture of current (pre-IMI) social efforts, with the aim of revealing gaps and opportunities that highlight the best ways to improve results. In this particular case, the social media accounts have been inactive since February 2020 due to staffing challenges at HSRW, and the only relevant starting information available for the audit is the number of followers. This will help us evaluate progress once this strategy is implemented.

Table 1. *Social media status*⁹

Platform	Handle	Followers
Twitter	@EUProjectO	365
Facebook	/euprojectoeu	44
YouTube	@euprojecto	0
LinkedIn	/eu-project-ô/	0

⁹ As of January 11th, 2022, when IMI's work on social media commenced in earnest.

Benchmarking

While developing a social media strategy, it is useful to analyse what other similar or comparable projects are already doing right or wrong (and with what effect on their communication outcomes). The goal of this benchmark is to understand from external examples what is working and what needs to be improved in our social media activities.

The table below contains examples of projects from the IC4TWater cluster of EU-funded projects, where Project Ô is also located. Even with a benchmark comparison of the ICT4Water cluster of EU-funded projects, there are clearly vast differences in the level of social media output and the degree of uptake from audiences. This highlights the importance of project-specific strategies to boost visibility and impact. The table indicates the main indicators of social media reach and the nature of their social media messaging:

Table 2. IC4TWater social media benchmarking

Project	Social media	Types of posts	Examples
Aqua3s	<p>Twitter: @aqua3seu 188 followers 151 tweets since 2019</p> <p>LinkedIn: 166 followers</p>	<p>Retweets, short texts with emojis, links and images.</p> <p>Content focuses on events and explanations of how their technology works.</p> <p>Posts focusing on events (short description and an image).</p>	

<p>AquaSPICE</p>	<p>Twitter:</p> <p>@AquaSPICE1</p> <p>120 followers</p> <p>44 tweets since November 2020</p>	<p>Short texts with emojis, links and images.</p> <p>Mainly original posts with EU news related to the topic, events, public workshops and explanation of technical processes.</p>	<p>AquaSPICE @AquaSPICE1</p> <p>Did you know that the Port of #Antwerp is the leading #European oil & chemical hotspot in the 🇪🇺 ?</p> <p>A month ago, @AquaSPICE1 partners joined the CS#3-Antwerp case Workshop to discuss the 2 subcases in this location 📍 buff.ly/2QWshSD Stay tuned 4 more #WorkshopWeekly</p> <p>Traducir Tweet</p> <p>CS#3 - ANTWERP CASE Workshop</p> <p>BASF y 3 más</p>
<p>Blue-RoSES</p>	<p>Twitter:</p> <p>@BlueRoSESproj</p> <p>50 followers</p> <p>24 tweets since December 2019</p> <p>LinkedIn:</p> <p>22 followers</p> <p>Instagram:</p> <p>@blue_roses_project</p> <p>8 followers</p> <p>17 posts</p> <p>Facebook:</p> <p>/BlueRosesProject</p> <p>186 likes</p>	<p>Medium-length texts without emojis.</p> <p>Each text is accompanied by links and images (pictures of virtual meetings, infographics, etc.).</p> <p>Mainly original posts focused on the progress and activities of the project.</p> <p>One post per week. Focus is on the progress, activities and events of the project.</p> <p>Same images used in Twitter, Facebook and LinkedIn with longer text descriptions.</p> <p>Same images as Instagram and longer text.</p>	<p>Blue-RoSES @BlueRoSESproj</p> <p>Fascinated with marine robots, but wonder what UMW, AUV, ASV or ROV stand for? We've assembled an infographic to clarify these acronyms and provide an overview of marine robot categories.</p> <p>#infographic #roboticsforall #sustainability #environmental @cinea_eu @EUgreenddeal</p> <p>Traducir Tweet</p> <p>Marine robots Unmanned marine vehicles</p> <p>ASV Autonomous Surface Vehicle Surface Wave-powered or propeller driven Partial or fully autonomous control</p> <p>ROV Remotely Operated Vehicle Underwater Tether for power supply & communications Short range long time operations Interactions with the environment also with robotic arms</p> <p>AUV Autonomous Underwater Vehicle Underwater Acoustic communication Torpedo-shaped Energy efficient Long range operations Poor interaction with the environment</p> <p>3:40 a. m. · 17 may. 2021 · Twitter Web App</p>

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<p>BWaterSmart Project</p>	<p>Twitter: @B_WaterSmart 243 followers 40 tweets since September 2020</p>	<p>Short text without emojis, sometimes without images as well. Retweets from other similar accounts. Context focuses on the activities of the project such as meetings, published papers and events.</p>	
<p>Digital Water City</p>	<p>Twitter: @digitalwater_eu 514 followers 367 tweets since July 2018</p> <p>LinkedIn: 820 followers</p>	<p>Short texts, minimum use of emojis, proper use of hashtags and links. Content focuses on the activities and events, its members and the impact of the project. When they're not using photographs, they follow design templates such as the example on the right. The content is very similar to Twitter. At least 1 post per week.</p>	

<p>Monocle</p>	<p>Twitter: @MONOCLE_H2020 536 followers 200 tweets since November 2017</p>	<p>Short text descriptions accompanied by images. No use of emojis. Mainly original posts. Content focuses on the project's technologies.</p>	
<p>NIAIDES</p>	<p>Twitter: @naiadesproject 257 followers 152 tweets since August 2019</p> <p>Facebook: /naiadesproject 161 likes</p> <p>LinkedIn: 66 members</p>	<p>Medium-length texts, minimum use of emojis. Proper use of hashtags and links. Every tweet is usually accompanied by an image. Content focuses on their technology and events. Long texts, minimum use of emojis and hashtags. Context focuses on events, world news related to the project and explanations of their technologies. Profile is set up as a closed group.</p>	

<p>Zero Brine</p>	<p>Twitter: @zero_brine_ 922 followers 981 tweets since November 2017</p> <p>LinkedIn: 442 followers</p> <p>YouTube: 16 videos 396 total views</p>	<p>Medium-length texts, minimum use of emojis.</p> <p>Proper use of hashtags and links.</p> <p>Retweets from similar accounts.</p> <p>Content focuses mainly on events, activities and the technology of the project.</p> <p>One post every two weeks focusing on the technology and events of the project.</p> <p>Zero Brine’s videos are located in a playlist within REVOLVE’s YouTube channel, alongside with videos of other EU projects related to topics such as water, energy, forests, mobility, cities and circular economy.</p>	

Target audiences

Two main target audiences have been identified from our preliminary stakeholder mapping: technical communities with an interest in water sustainability and general, non-technical public audiences that may be affected by water sustainability initiatives and projects such as Project Ô. Each one of these broad audience categories comprises specific stakeholder groups with different levels of awareness, understanding, engagement and knowledge of the topics concerning Project Ô. A differentiated view of the target audiences is important to ensure that communication approaches are tailored in a way that will be effective. However, the two broad categories of technical vs. non-technical audiences help to clarify the key distinction between communications aimed at professionals in the water sector or the general public.

Table 3. Target audiences

Target audience	Specific stakeholders' characteristics
Technical communities	<p>Policymakers</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • May understand the basics of some of the technical aspects but not a high level of detail. • May be former engineers, now in a policy-making role and therefore seeking technological knowledge. • May be public-facing/accountable for decisions, so need to back up decisions with credible sources of knowledge. <p>Industry or Private-Sector</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • May implement and use the technologies. • May work for private-sector companies looking to exploit the technology as a means for increasing shareholder value or improving public perception, e.g. utilities or factories with sewage. <p>Academic researchers</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Academics and scholars involved in water-related research. • May work for universities, scientific institutions, consultancies, NGOs, and/or research funding organisations.
General, non-technical public audiences	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • May have no background knowledge to understand what the project is and the implications it could have for them. • May already be aware that water reuse could affect their everyday lives or local communities. • May reside near the demosites and/or in towns that have not yet adopted these kinds of technologies. • May use green spaces, such as community parks that are impacted by poor quality or undrinkable water. • May recognise the benefits for themselves or their community of more reliable, mobile and scalable water sources.

Audience profiles

An audience profile is the visualisation of a "person" representing an aggregated idea of our audiences and their motivations for engaging on social media. Audience profiles help clarify demographics (i.e., age, education, etc), behaviours, goals, challenges, interests, and more. A profile guides further development of messaging for social media content by targeting specific audience characteristics. A key question for content and visual development is whether it will resonate with a particular person in these target audience profiles.

The following profiles are a starting point and may change over time depending on the results of social media and stakeholder analytics.

Table 4. Overview of audience profiles

Technical Community	General Public
<p data-bbox="475 842 584 875">Profile 1</p> <p data-bbox="959 1084 1259 1117">Small Business Manager</p>	
<p data-bbox="475 1144 584 1178">Profile 2</p> <p data-bbox="927 1420 1291 1453">Recent High School Graduate</p>	

Technical Community Profiles

Profile 1: Water Systems Engineer

The first profile is represented by someone in her mid-40s who is a highly educated engineer, working in the private-sector for water treatment. She manages a team that maintains and improves water treatment systems, works on a range of high-profile projects, and dedicates a significant amount of time to keep up-to-date with the latest research and innovation available in the water treatment sector. She tends to gain information by attending professional conferences and workshops, talking to peers in the field of engineering and reading published academic journals.

Twitter and LinkedIn are her preferred social networks to connect and share information with other professionals working in the water treatment sector. She shares highlights of her work irregularly, but she is part of several LinkedIn groups with professionals and peers that share local updates on technologies and innovative practices.

Figure 6. Technical community profile: Water Systems Engineer

</p>	<p>Professional responsibilities: Manage a team of engineers, improve efficiency of water treatment systems</p> <p>Professional objectives:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Make water treatment systems more efficient. ● Find materials and source innovative practices to reduce costs and limit waste byproducts. ● Stay informed of the technologies available in the water sector. <p>Preferred sources of information: Published scientific journals, professional conferences and workshops, informal conversations with practitioners, social media for professional networking, technology fairs.</p> <p>Preferred methods of communication Face-to-face, phone, email, social media</p>
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Profile 2: Policymaker in EU Parliament

The second profile is represented by a policymaker in his mid-50s from a rural community in Spain. He now serves in the European parliament after a career at Amnesty International, where he was an advocate for human rights legislation in neighbouring EU countries.

His work involves regular meetings with representatives from private industry, community groups and non-governmental organisations to gain insights for his legislative agenda, which still prioritises sustainable development goals around food and water security. For this reason, he frequently interfaces with other policymakers and sits on sustainability committees that deal with water supply and sanitation.

He stays interested in the innovations coming from university research and private sector (i.e., local utilities and water suppliers), and wants to stay current on water treatment systems that will address water supply challenges. He prefers to review policy briefs first and then follow up directly with scientists or engineers to better understand any technical information.

Twitter and LinkedIn are his preferred social networks to promote legislation and learn about interesting research and innovative technologies. He will engage with projects that support his legislative agenda and focus on circular water economy.

Figure 7. Technical community profile: Policymaker in EU Parliament

<div data-bbox="352 1379 547 1570"> </p>	<p data-bbox="683 1361 1002 1391">Professional responsibilities: Draft and promote legislation, meet with industry, represent constituents, review policy briefs, stay aware of innovative technologies</p> <p data-bbox="683 1529 946 1559">Professional objectives:</p> <ul data-bbox="715 1570 1286 1738" style="list-style-type: none"> ● Improve the life quality of his constituents. ● Be properly informed for legislative procedures. ● Take scientific advice into account when making important decisions. <p data-bbox="683 1778 1054 1807">Preferred sources of information: Policy briefs, printed media, conferences, peer-to-peer conversations, social media.</p> <p data-bbox="683 1906 1121 1973">Preferred methods of communication: Face-to-face, phone, email, social media</p>
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General Public, Non-technical Profiles

Profile 3: Small Business Manager

The third profile is represented by a small business manager in his mid-40s living in Croatia's capital. After living in the city for so many years, he has generally positive views about his local water supply and usually drinks water straight from the tap. While he is unfamiliar with water treatment technology specifically, he is interested to learn about innovations that reduce pollution and improve clean drinking water.

He does not see his relationship with nature as any integral part of who he is, but he would agree that he has a responsibility to help protect the environment. He has worked for the same small business for 16 years and did not complete a university degree. If asked, he would say that prioritising people's jobs is more important than the environment. With his country being outside of the EU, he expresses doubt in the European Commission's ability to help his country or do what is right for his community.

He uses Google when searching for information and will use Facebook to stay connected with family and friends.

Figure 8. General public profile: Small Business Manager

<div data-bbox="379 1256 592 1464" data-label="Image"> </div> <p data-bbox="432 1480 528 1505">Job Title</p> <p data-bbox="352 1514 612 1538">Local Business Manager</p> <p data-bbox="379 1576 584 1601">Level of Education</p> <p data-bbox="311 1610 652 1666">Educational qualification below university degree</p> <p data-bbox="392 1704 571 1729">Social Networks</p> <div data-bbox="424 1733 541 1785" data-label="Image"> </div>	<p data-bbox="695 1270 1011 1294">Professional responsibilities:</p> <p data-bbox="695 1319 1299 1395">Maintain his business on a day-to-day basis, look after his employees</p> <p data-bbox="695 1433 956 1458">Professional objectives:</p> <ul data-bbox="746 1480 1278 1545" style="list-style-type: none"> ● Keep jobs for himself and his employees ● Keep good relationships with his community <p data-bbox="695 1572 1066 1597">Preferred sources of information:</p> <p data-bbox="695 1621 1283 1646">Talking to community, meetings with local authorities</p> <p data-bbox="695 1673 1121 1697">Preferred methods of communication:</p> <p data-bbox="695 1722 1238 1747">Face-to-face, social media, text messaging, phone</p>
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Profile 4: Recent High School Graduate

The last profile is represented by a young adult, recently graduated from high school in Israel. She has a generally negative view about her local water supply, seeing it as dirty and risky. For this reason, she almost always drinks from bottled water but will drink filtered water when it is available.

She is completely unfamiliar with water treatment technology and may feel confused or bored by technical information; however, she is also hopeful that innovations from modern science might someday solve environmental problems, such as reducing pollution, keeping lakes and rivers clean and improving drinking water. The environment is important, but she does not feel there is anything she can do personally to help protect the environment. Additionally, with her country being outside of the EU, she doubts the European Commission would do what is right for her community.

She prefers Instagram and TikTok to share stories and highlights from her life. She uses Google when searching for information and will use Facebook messenger to stay connected with family and friends.

Figure 9. General public profile: Recent High School Graduate

<div data-bbox="405 1160 609 1393" data-label="Image"> </div> <p data-bbox="432 1442 572 1503">Age Young Adult</p> <p data-bbox="327 1541 679 1632">Level of Education No Formal Qualification: Recent High School Student</p> <p data-bbox="376 1671 624 1756">Social Networks </p>	<p data-bbox="715 1178 1243 1283">Professional responsibilities: Prepare for college, help cook and look after her younger siblings</p> <p data-bbox="715 1308 1114 1480">Professional objectives:</p> <ul data-bbox="762 1357 1129 1480" style="list-style-type: none"> ● Get into a good university ● Travel outside of her country ● Become more independent <p data-bbox="715 1518 1142 1592">Preferred methods of communication: Social media</p> <p data-bbox="715 1630 1150 1704">Preferred sources of information: Google, Browsing Instagram and TikTok</p>
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Audience-specific Goals and Objectives

A key part of a social media strategy is setting targeted goals to develop content with a clear direction. Identifying clear, specific goals will help us get the most out of social media. The following goals are based on WP8. However, it is worth noting that WP9 is primarily responsible for communication with technical communities.

Technical Communities

The main objective is to raise awareness of Project Ô technologies and to build trust in them. This will be achieved through content posted on Facebook, Twitter, YouTube and LinkedIn.

Table 5. *Communications Goals for Technical communities*

Platforms	Objective	Specific goals based on WP8	KPIs
Facebook, Twitter, YouTube and LinkedIn	Raise awareness of the project technologies and build trust in them.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Audiences can see that research used by Project O will solve a societal and environmental challenge in their communities and around the world. ● Audiences can see the scientific excellence and European added value in the water sector. ● Audiences can see that research conducted by Project Ô's consortium members promotes European competitiveness and circular water economy. ● Audiences can see the transnational aspects of H2020 projects. ● Audiences can see the challenges and opportunities of regulatory change in the circular water economy at the European level. ● Audiences can see and understand how Project Ô relates to other similar projects. ● Audiences can encourage others in the technical community to know about and follow best practices. ● Audiences can trust Project Ô's modules and technologies as game changers in the water sector. ● Audiences can articulate a joint vision of a new infrastructure wave in the water sector based on "small loops" and the circular economy. 	<p>LinkedIn: >100 followers</p> <p>YouTube: >100 views</p> <p>Twitter: >100 likes</p>

General, Non-technical Public Audiences

The main objective is to raise awareness of the value of water and the urgent need to adopt circular water systems, as well as to show the benefits of Project O technologies at the demo sites. This will be achieved through content posted on Facebook, Twitter and YouTube.

Table 6. Communications Goals for General, Non-technical Public Audiences

Platforms	Objective	Specific goals based on WP8	KPIs
Facebook, Twitter and YouTube	Raise awareness of the value of water and the importance of adopting circular water systems.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Audiences can recognize and value water as a precious resource. • Audiences can see the impact of the linear circular water systems. • Audiences can recognize and value circular water systems. • Audiences can see the importance and relevance of Project Ô technologies for society. • Audiences can re-signify water reuse, combating its social stigma and developing social acceptance. • Audiences can understand the basic functioning of Project Ô technologies. • Audiences can encourage others to know about and follow best practises. • Audiences can use their knowledge to communicate and debate with their local policy makers. • Where feasible (e.g., in the wake of the events), public audiences will be able to actively share their perspectives with the project and community. 	<p>YouTube: >500 views</p> <p>Twitter: >500 likes</p> <p>Facebook: >500 likes</p>

Project's voice and visuals on social media

Project's voice

We will speak to audiences as people, not as a project advertisement. This means that every post needs to be produced as a conversation. Our voice will be relatable to encourage engagement with a non-technical general public, and clear and open to discussion to engage with technical communities.

Grammar, terminology, and levels of depth of information

The main language for publications will be US English to maximise international uptake and engagement. Following the target audiences' descriptions, there are three levels of depth of information that should be kept in mind when producing content for the social media platforms:

Table 7. Levels of depth of information

Level of depth	Content
General interest (low depth)	What a circular water economy model is and generally the effect it has. In this case, we need to avoid using jargon or specialised terms and strive towards a more clear language.
Policy and Business (medium depth)	Information about the technology on a social and practical level and practical information as to the benefits for using the technology, e.g. savings, PR value, etc. Specialised terms are deemed ok but their use should be limited.
Technical (high depth)	Details of how the technologies work and more technical reporting of facts and figures relating to practical application. Specialised terms are ok.

Post formatting

The length of the text in posts will be variable depending on the social media platform and the content itself. The following guidelines will allow content to be brief enough to be quick to read and to grab our audiences' attention, but long enough to offer some details. All posts should ideally be accompanied by an image or a video.

- **Facebook** posts should be between 40 and 50 characters.
- **Tweets** should be between 71 and 100 characters.
- **LinkedIn** posts should be less than 140 characters (this will avoid the appearance of the "See more" button).
- **YouTube** videos should be between 2 and 3 minutes long.

Hashtag usage

The official hashtag of the project is #EUProjectO or #EUProjectÔ. The use of either one is indifferent since all special characters (such as the Ô) are converted to regular ones to work as one metadata tag. We can also use related hashtags like #ICT4WATER, #WaterReuse, #CircularWater, #WaterManagement, #H2020, #CircularEconomy, #EUfunded, #SDGs, #SDG6, #SDG12, #SDG13 and #RRI, depending on the content of the post. It is recommended to always capitalise the first letter of each word of hashtags to improve readability.

Hashtags can be used within the text if possible. Example:

Figure 10. Hashtags example #1

The #SDGs are 17 goals with a total of 169 targets among them, most of which are meant to be achieved by 2030. #EUProjectÔ will contribute most directly to 3 SDGs: #SDG6 (Clean Water & Sanitation), #SDG12 (#ResponsibleConsumption & Production) & #SDG13 (#ClimateAction) #H2020

Pertinent hashtags that cannot be inserted within the text should be placed at the end of the post. Example:

Figure 11. Hashtags example #2

Last week, the review meeting of #EUProjectÔ was held in Brussels. The fruitful meeting was used as an opportunity to inform and discuss the progress towards the project goals, achievements, deliverables to date, and future project work plan #H2020 #WaterManagement

Visual guidelines

All photographs and/or graphics shared in original posts need to be high resolution images and must be licence-free or produced in-house, otherwise written consent by the author will be needed. The design team will work on design templates intended for different purposes in order to unify all social media platforms' visual identity.

Figure 12. Project Ô logo and colour palette

Content strategy

Key messages

Key messages are the main points of information we want our audience to hear, understand, and remember. They are bite-sized summations that articulate what we do, why we do it, how we are different, and what value we bring to stakeholders. Key messages describe overarching themes, so the potential to create specific messages and combine them is endless. These messages must be formulated in a way that will gain attention and leave a lasting impression. To achieve this, there must be alignment of the message content and associated visuals with the existing needs and interests of the target audience. That is, a differentiated communication approach is required to maximise reach and impact.

Table 8. Differentiated key messages for specific target audiences

Technical communities	General, non-technical public audiences
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Project Ô is a transnational cooperation in a diverse consortium and drives scientific excellence in the water sector. ● Project Ô contributes to European competitiveness and is part of the new infrastructure wave necessary for the circular water economy model. ● Project Ô modules and technologies are game-changers and change makers. ● Project Ô is part of a series of efforts to rethink current water distribution systems. ● Project Ô solves societal and environmental challenges through (not only) innovative technologies (e.g., impact on everyday lives, contribution to SDGs, climate change, etc.). ● Project Ô implements real-life techniques, methodologies, technologies, procedures or participatory processes which are successful and have an impact in specific contexts of application. 	<p>Although this cluster includes different target audiences within each demonstration site that will require specific key messages, these are the general ones:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Water is a precious and finite resource, and we should value it. ● Water scarcity is a human-made problem and can be fought with circular water systems. ● One feature of a circular water economy is to turn what is thought of as “waste” into a resource. ● Circular water systems have economic, environmental and societal impacts. ● Project Ô has developed technologies to optimise how water is used (e.g., processing water depending on the quality required for its next use or developing WWT portable modules). ● Project Ô has developed both water treatment modules and digital platforms in collaboration with local stakeholders. ● The treatment modules are currently installed at four different industrial and household water management situations, and each of the technologies tackle different problems.

Posting content types

Social media posts should be a mix of different types of content. There is a monthly calendar to identify key dates and authentic opportunities to share content from each category that will be updated on a monthly basis based on the results of analytics. This calendar will directly feed to our social media content manager account.

- **Promotional:** Focus on the project itself: technology, actions, demo sites, events, etc. Most of this content will come from the website and be produced by IMI.
- **Curated:** Focus on sharing helpful information (e.g., blog posts, quotes, infographics, best practises, etc.). Most of this content will focus on the concept of circular economy, water sustainability, water reuse and sustainability communication, and will be produced by IMI. Where content ideas / material produced by partners, IMI plays an editorial role in refining prior to posting.
- **Reposted:** Share content from other accounts we follow. Accounts to re-post from must be pre-approved by the task leader.
- **Engagement:** Ask questions of audiences and seek to gain responses (e.g., polls, questions, etc).

Posting frequency

In 2021, the data science team of Sprout Social, a social media management software company, reviewed findings and trends in social media usage of their 20,000+ customers to understand when their content was most and least frequently engaged with, broken out by platform and industry¹⁰. According to their results for non-profit accounts, the most suitable category for this project, these were the best days and times in terms of levels of engagement to post on each platform. Since the majority of Project Ô partners are located in Europe, the time zone we will use is Central European Time (CET).

- **Facebook:** Tuesday, Wednesday and Friday 9 a.m. – 1 p.m.
- **Twitter:** Wednesday 9 a.m. – 3 p.m., Tuesday through Thursday 9 - 11 a.m.
- **LinkedIn:** Tuesday through Thursday 9 a.m. – noon.

¹⁰ To read the full report follow this link: <https://sproutsocial.com/insights/best-times-to-post-on-social-media/#np-times>

Although determining the posting frequency depends on Project Ô followers' age range, interests and social media habits, there are general frames of reference that can be used as a starting point. The following numbers may change over time depending on the results of social media analytics (Section 7).

According to Myers (2022)¹¹, these are the suggested minimum and optimal numbers of posts per platform to maintain a steady level of engagement. This implies that the posting frequency must be balanced or concerns may start becoming relevant: If we post too infrequently, Project Ô audiences will forget about the project; however, if we post too often, we will become a nuisance and audiences will stop following us.

Table 9. Strategy for social media posting frequency

Platform	Minimum	Optimal	Project Ô's goal
	Weekly		
Facebook	1	3	3
Twitter	5	15	7
Linkedin	2	5	2

*YouTube videos publishing frequency relied on the video production plan

Monthly planning calendar to ensure consistency

A monthly planning calendar¹² will be available to offer an overview of what needs to be published in each platform each day following the content strategy (Section 6.2). It is recommended that the community manager plans all platforms' weekly posts at least one week in advance. Short-term planning will allow us to include emergent information and relevant news.

In the calendar, there will be a tab for each platform (Twitter, Facebook and LinkedIn) for a weekly plan linking to the Social Media Posts Database. Each platform will have pre-established times for posts (Section 6.3). Although the community manager will be free to choose the best time to publish from the options offered, the days are fixed and will be determined by the Monthly Content tab.

¹¹ Myers, L. (2022, January 11). How Often To Post On Social Media: 2021 Success Guide. *Louise Myers Visual Social Media*. <https://louisem.com/144557/often-post-social-media>

¹² <https://drive.google.com/file/d/1daQAe-uTvgf-iEB93VTPpqcbYCGvjUt/view?usp=sharing>

Figure 13. August 2021 Monthly Content tab

MONTHLY CALENDAR							KEY:
							Promotional
							Curated
							Engagement
							TBD
							TBD
							TBD
SUNDAY	MONDAY	TUESDAY	WEDNESDAY	THURSDAY	FRIDAY	SATURDAY	
	Facebook - Promotional Twitter - Curated Twitter - Promotional	Twitter - Curated LinkedIn - Promotional	Facebook - Curated Twitter - Curated	Twitter - Curated LinkedIn - Curated	Facebook - Engagement Twitter - Curated Twitter - Engagement		
SUNDAY	MONDAY	TUESDAY	WEDNESDAY	THURSDAY	FRIDAY	SATURDAY	
	Facebook - Promotional Twitter - Curated Twitter - Promotional	Twitter - Curated LinkedIn - Engagement	Facebook - Curated Twitter - Curated	Twitter - Curated LinkedIn - Promotional	Facebook - Engagement Twitter - Curated Twitter - Engagement		
SUNDAY	MONDAY	TUESDAY	WEDNESDAY	THURSDAY	FRIDAY	SATURDAY	
	Facebook - Promotional Twitter - Curated Twitter - Promotional	Twitter - Curated LinkedIn - Curated	Facebook - Curated Twitter - Curated	Twitter - Curated LinkedIn - Engagement	Facebook - Engagement Twitter - Curated Twitter - Engagement		
SUNDAY	MONDAY	TUESDAY	WEDNESDAY	THURSDAY	FRIDAY	SATURDAY	
	Facebook - Promotional Twitter - Curated Twitter - Promotional	Twitter - Curated LinkedIn - Promotional	Facebook - Curated Twitter - Curated	Twitter - Curated LinkedIn - Curated	Facebook - Engagement Twitter - Curated Twitter - Engagement		
SUNDAY	MONDAY	TUESDAY	WEDNESDAY	THURSDAY	FRIDAY	SATURDAY	
	Facebook - Promotional Twitter - Curated Twitter - Promotional	Twitter - Curated LinkedIn - Engagement	Facebook - Curated Twitter - Curated	Twitter - Curated LinkedIn - Promotional	Facebook - Engagement Twitter - Curated Twitter - Engagement		

Reporting plan to evaluate progress

A review of Project Ô social media analytics can be prepared at any point to provide enough information to adjust the social media communication strategy, whether in terms of audiences, types of posts or content. Each social media platform has its own built-in analytics and dashboards (at min. these analytics will feed into final technical reporting):

- Facebook Insights can be accessed by clicking the *Insights* tab in the menu bar across the top of the Facebook Page.
- Once logged in, Twitter Analytics can be accessed here: analytics.twitter.com
- To access LinkedIn Page analytics, we need to sign in to our Page admin centre, click the Analytics tab in the menu and select Updates, Followers, or Visitors from the dropdown.
- Once logged in, YouTube Analytics can be accessed here: youtube.com/analytics

Strategies for Event Management

Based on Project Ô targets, a strategic communication plan for event management was developed to guide the public engagement and communication programme of activities. This plan started with event program objectives, followed by activities for each event module, and ended with a proposed resource plan.

The event management strategy was developed after reading previous deliverables and project documentation. The overall goals noted for public engagement events outlined in D8.1 pointed to the need to increase participation in the project's innovation processes. This necessity is also set out in the EU Water Framework Directive of 2000 (60/EC)¹³, which aims “to ensure the participation of the general public including users of water in the establishment and updating of river basin management plans” (p.8). Furthermore, Article 14 of the 2000/60/EC Directive says that “the success of this Directive relies on close cooperation and coherent action at Community, Member State and local level as well as on information, consultation and involvement of the public, including users” (p.4). IMI has applied these European policy principles in its design of the public engagement co-creation events for the four demosite locations in the project. Each demosite offers different stakeholder configurations and challenges for implementing new circular water technologies, highlighting the importance of effective stakeholder analysis and engagement.

First, IMI's event management plan was developed based on key objectives in the Project Ô Description of the Action (DoA):

¹³ The EU Water Framework Directive came into force in 2000 pushed by a series of open consultation processes and workshops, which aimed at articulating the demand of several stakeholders involved with the water sector. As a conclusion of such consultations processes and workshops, it was proposed the necessity to avoid policy fragmentation in water management at the European level and to take into account river basins across regional, national and political boundaries. In addition, the European Commission justified the new directive of 2000 based on the results of the Eurobarometer on the environmental problems that Europeans consider most urgent. Among these problems, the concern for the water quality stands out.

Table 10. Module inferences derived from DoA objectives

Module Inference	Objective from DoA
Introduction	Promote (or introduce) the project and its results
Group discussion	Ensure a bi-directional knowledge transfer between the project and its stakeholders
	Incorporate stakeholder expectations and objections at an early stage of the value-creation process
Co-creation	Focus on co-creation , political communication and science advocacy

Second, the following inferred module types were developed into primary objectives that were drafted for each major component of the Public Engagement programme:

Table 11. Module types and primary objectives for the public engagement event program

Module type	Primary Objective (Long-Term)
Introduction	To inform individuals from the public about Project O innovations and key concepts (e.g., water reuse).
Tour demo sites	To improve public awareness of how key innovations developed at local Project O demo sites.
Group discussion	To clarify local public perspectives on Project O innovations.
Co-creation	To enrich local public engagement with Project O innovations by providing opportunities for participation.

Third, at least one activity was planned for each event module type within the co-creation public engagement event structure.

Table 12. Event module types and activities for the public engagement event programme

Event module type	Activities
Introduction	Project overview & need for water reuse
Tour demo sites	Digital/virtual walk-through of different areas of the demo sites
Group discussion	Understanding perspectives on water sustainability concerns and hopes
Co-creation	Co-creating & sharing news story about the future of water sustainability in local area

The basic event structure commenced with an introduction to the project and an overview of water reuse specific to a circular water economy. Event facilitators presented virtual tours and walk-throughs of different areas of the demo sites. This was followed by facilitated group discussions to reveal participants' attitudes and perspectives on water sustainability, including the hopes, expectations and concerns of participants. The final and most participatory element of the public engagement events was a co-creation activity that asked participants to create and share news stories about the future of water sustainability and related innovations at the demonstration sites.

Each event included organisational aspects such as determination of the workshop approach and outline of the agenda, preparation of workshop materials (including invitations, worksheets, slide decks), translation of workshop materials, recruiting and liaising with workshop participants, liaising with demosite partners and other stakeholders, gaining informed consent/GDPR consent form creation, dissemination and collection, facilitating workshops (including managing the agenda, recording, breakout group sessions, worksheet completion), recruiting additional multilingual facilitators as necessary, transcription of workshop recordings and participant feedback (including survey preparation, delivery and analysis).

The event management strategy included documentation of the steps required to successfully implement a programme of co-creation public engagement activities (see Table below). The details of the event management plan developed by the Institute for Methods Innovation are embedded in the reporting from the co-creation public engagement events later in this report.

Table 13. Programme planning by tasks

	Task Type	Primary Task	Sub-task	Description
1	Per programme	Event Programme Strategy		
1a			Event Plan/Template	
1b			Event Evaluation Plan/Template	
1c			Event Communication Plan/Templates	
2	Per programme	Event Programme Coordination		Coordinates across events
3	Per programme	Event Programme Implementation		
4	Per event	Event Management (x4)		Coordinates partners and sub-tasks within each event
4a			Administration	Scheduling, Registration, GDPR Consent
4b			Technical Administration	Zoom, Survey System, Recording, Database, Registration Webpage/Platform, Participant Communications, Cross-platform integrations
4c			Participant Recruitment (DoA requires circa 50 participants per demosite)	Targeted Advertising, Translation, Graphic Design, Social Media Communications, Press Release, Mobilising Local Stakeholders
4d			Technical Content / Delivery of Virtual Tour	Details of local technology implementation prepared in plain language for virtual demosite tours.
4e			Co-creation / Focus group Preparation & Facilitation (1 FG Facilitator per 6-7 participants)	Social research experts to ensure high-quality data and participant experience.
4f			Co-creation/Focus Group: Research Aspects	Data Collection, Data management, Analysis, Reporting [Feeds D8.6]
5	Per event	Event Evaluation (x4)		
5a			Evaluation Surveys	Translation, Data Collection, Data management, Analysis, Reporting [Feeds D8.6]

(T8.5) External Project Communications Report

The external project communication refers to methods for sharing information with various external stakeholders. Project Ô started to communicate at the beginning of the project (see Milestone 30 report) and has continually improved the overall strategies and implementation approaches for each major component of the project. In this regard, communication strategies were revised and elaborated during RP2 with the new addition of IMI as a project partner. The strategies focused on refreshing and improving all aspects of the external communications, which included revisions to the brand identity. Work continued using the revised external communication plan to redesign the logo, website, and create a new library of media assets. All written content was fully revised and in-line with these communication plans, and social media tools and media assets were shared broadly to maximise value for the project.

The external communication channels for the project included the website, social media (Twitter, Facebook, LinkedIn, Instagram and Youtube), video production, signage and other communication materials for both electronic and in-person distribution.

Project Website

As indicated previously, an early stakeholder survey undertaken by HSRW reported that most stakeholders (90%) had a strong preference for information to be shared through the project website (see D8.1 Stakeholder Analysis). The prototype placeholder version of Project Ô website¹⁴ was established by HSRW during RP1 (see D8.3). In RP2, after joining the project as a partner, IMI developed the communication strategies to improve all aspects of the internal and external communications. Work began in the latter part of RP2 to improve the visual communication and language used to articulate Project Ô's most important ideas in ways that were more clear to understand for both its technical and non-technical audiences.

During RP3, the original placeholder version of the website was completely revised and replaced with a new look and feel, newly created text and visual content, and improved navigation and page structures. The theme was completely re-designed, including custom CSS and plug-ins development. Overall, the implementation involved much needed revisions to the brand identity. This required multiple meetings with the technology partners and setting up project databases.

¹⁴ Website URL: eu-project-o.eu

Figure 14. Comparison between the old and the new website Homepage

Before: Pre-IMI placeholder

After: Post-IMI revised website

Figure 15. Comparison between the old and the new website Actions page

Before: Pre-IMI placeholder

After: Post-IMI revised website

Figure 16. Comparison between the old and the new website Solutions page

Before: Pre-IMI placeholder

Implementation and scaling up of circular innovative technological solutions for water management

Project Ô implements **new technologies** and **solutions** for water treatment. These innovative technologies are diverse in their scope, but they all provide **high energy efficiency** and **low operational costs**, compared to competing solutions for the same type of treatment. This will be possible through the adoption of a **modular approach**, which optimizes the treatment and management of a given quantity of water at the maximum **energy efficiency** level as possible.

What is it in a nutshell that this technology does for us?

ADVANCED TERTIARY TREATMENT MODULE (ADV.ERT):

The module, called ADV.ERT, is an **advanced tertiary treatment mobile plant** that integrates two functions: a **desalinator** and an **advanced oxidation process (AOP)** for addressing microbial contamination, and other remedial activities. The selected train of technologies to be trialled in Puglia will be composed by **Nanofiltration** and **HiNaPEF**. The **HiNaPEF** has proven highly effective in the disinfection of water and in the mineralization of toxic organic pollutants, making it the most fitting technology for the elimination of microbial contamination and degradation of pesticides and pharmaceuticals.

ADV.ERT pilot module for water treatment will be installed at demonstration site 1 and it will treat 20m³/day. The module is targeted to serve water wells for local use, with **contained costs**. Impact is reached through **replication of such small modules**, which can be easily moved around to supply **clean water where required** or **duplicated** to be easily installed at different locations.

After: Post-IMI revised website

Solution

MOBILE3TECH module is a mobile plant integrating three technologies to treat water used in industry

It helps protect water treatment plants by pre-treating used industrial water to remove damaging pollutants

MOBILE3TECH module benefits include:

- ✂ Breaking down toxic organic pollutants and finer treatment of used water
- ♻ Increasing water reuse across the EU
- 📍 Local reuse of treated water
- 📋 Aiding compliance with micropollutant and pharmaceutical regulations
- 💰 Saving energy and money by only applying needed treatments
- 🛡 Protecting water treatment plants from damage by removing toxic contaminants

Figure 17. Comparison between the old and the new website Structure page

Before: Pre-IMI placeholder

Work packages

Project Ô is part of the [ICT4 Water Cluster](#), and is divided into 10 work packages with the following objectives:

WP 1 – Management:

- Ensuring the effective management of the project within time and budget constraints at the highest level of quality with active communication with the EU.
- Coordinating project partners and Advisory group to achieve synergy in collaboration.
- Defining data management strategy.

WP 2 – Small water management loop technologies enabling water treatment and reuse:

- This WP has as main objectives the development and validation of the technologies to be installed at the demo sites.

WP 3 – Integrated water management, planning and circular economy:

- Provide evidence-based knowledge regarding the framework conditions that may hinder or facilitate the transition to water-circular economy.
- Assess the bottlenecks of integrating water circular economy approaches into current water resources planning and spatial planning institutional frameworks.
- Foster the transition to water circular economy through the proposal of new institutional arrangements and associated social innovations.
- Use the demo-sites as examples, to design a process of co-creation with stakeholders of innovative planning and governance approaches to facilitate the transition to water circular economy.

After: Post-IMI revised website

Organisation

Project Ô partners are organised into smaller working groups

These working groups connect and flow in sequence to meet the project end goal

This novel process integrates social science research into the development process through direct consultation with audiences impacted by Project Ô technologies. Social innovation is intended to be promoted by incorporating, and even anticipating, stakeholder expectations and objections.

Co-creation projects help build a sense of public ownership of the new approaches and technologies developed by Project Ô. Water management is as much a responsibility for the end users as the regulators, and Project Ô wants to help increase public involvement.

The entire innovation process has an integrated and participative approach, which directly involves the community and the territory.

Figure 18. Comparison between the old and the new website Latest page

Before: Pre-IMI placeholder

Project Ô at the Smart City Expo World Congress

Yolanda Ballesteros (Socamex) introduced Project Ô to a variety of panelists at the Smart City Expo World Congress that took place in Barcelona, Spain, in November 2018. Yolanda demonstrated that Project Ô has solutions to some of the challenges of the circular economy.

After: Post-IMI revised website

Media assets

In line with the DoA’s statement that in T8.5 External Communications, ‘Dissemination material for non-expert communities will be produced,’ new illustrative media, photos, visuals and other communication materials were created by IMI. This included creating custom-designed illustrations to communicate key project ideas and establishing a consortium-accessible media repository. This repository is part of the project legacy and can be used by other EC-funded projects promoting a circular water economy. All visuals planned for the website were developed such that they boost communication on the website, but also act as individual shareable items across social media and other communication channels.

Figure 19. Examples of new visual media to support communication across channels

Spain Linear Water Economy diagram

Italy Circular Water Economy diagram

Table 14. List of illustrations

Name	Illustration
World resources	<p>EARTH'S SURFACE</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Seawater 69% Land 29% Freshwater but locked in, e.g., ice 1% Accessible freshwater 1%
Linear Economy	<p>Raw Materials → Manufacture → Use Once → Dispose</p>

<p>Linear Water Economy</p>	<p>Extract From Source Treat Use Once Treat Discharge Elsewhere</p>
<p>Circular Economy</p>	<p>Circular Economy</p> <p>PRODUCTION (RE)USE REPAIR & RECYCLE RAW MATERIALS</p>
<p>Circular Water Economy</p>	<p>Circular Water Economy</p> <p>Water Use Water Treatment & Transport Water Abstraction Replenish Water Store Wastewater Treatment</p> <p>Reuse Becomes by-products & energy for reuse</p>

<p>Circular Water Economy + Project Ô Demosites</p>	
<p>Demosites Map</p>	
<p>Cross Section of Aquifer</p>	
<p>Italy Linear Water Economy</p>	

<p>PHOTO.CAT Unit Detailed Representation</p>	
<p>ADV.ERT Module Simple Representation</p>	

<p>ADV.ERT Module Detailed Representation</p>	
<p>MOBILE3TECH Module Simple Representation</p>	

<p>Decision Analytic Platform (DAP) Features Overview</p>	<div style="display: flex; flex-direction: column; align-items: center;"> <div style="display: flex; align-items: center; margin-bottom: 10px;"> <div style="margin-left: 10px;"> <p>Shows the impacts of decisions on current and future water supply</p> </div> </div> </div>
<p>Circular Economy Platform (CEP) Overview</p>	<div style="text-align: center;"> <p>The diagram illustrates the flow of information and impact through the Circular Economy Platform (CEP). At the top, three entities—Water system authorities, Water regulator, and Water users—are connected by plus signs. Arrows from each point down to a central area where 'Evaluate overall effects' is written. Below this, a 'Water system' and a 'Business model' are shown with curved arrows indicating a cycle between them. A central box labeled 'Circular Economy Platform (CEP)' is connected to both the Water system and Business model with arrows labeled 'through'. An arrow from the CEP box points down to a grid of seven categories: Technologies, Economics, Resources, Environmental sustainability, Spatial planning, Social aspects, and Regulatory mechanisms.</p> </div>

<p>Circular Economy Platform (CEP) Features Overview</p>	<div style="display: flex; flex-direction: column; align-items: center;"> <div style="display: flex; align-items: center; margin-bottom: 10px;"> </div> <div style="text-align: center; margin-top: 20px;"> <p>CEP allows key players involved in water treatment activities to interact by sharing requests, offers, treatment technologies and logistics</p> </div> </div>
<p>Circular Economy Platform (CEP) Marketplace Overview</p>	<div style="border: 1px solid black; background-color: #0056b3; color: white; padding: 5px; margin-top: 10px;"> <p>New water loop</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Players meeting point - New opportunities creation - Speed up communications - Best economic proposals matching - New technologies promoter - Demands collector - Business facilitator </div>

Apart from infographics, IMI designed a bifold and trifold layout for brochures, and added relevant content for dissemination. The content of the brochure was drafted by IMI and reviewed by Professor Alexander Gerber of HSRW.

Figure 20. Project Ô brochure - Bifold layout

Figure 21. Project Ô brochure - Trifold layout

For general internal and external project communication, a new slide deck template was created, and provided to project partners, that better fits the project branding and is visually more pleasing.

Figure 22. Slide deck template

Videos

A suite of videos was created to enhance engagement with the website and social media channels. A total of 34 videos were produced and published on the Project Ô YouTube channel (23 public and 11 private). Videos that provided context for the project were embedded into the website.

Project Ô Overview video

The promotional video produced by IRIS¹⁵ was a focus for further development to push it towards completion. The original messaging required revising to tailor it towards the targeted audiences and there were inaccuracies in the visuals, such as typographical errors, that required correcting before it could be launched externally. Work by IMI was carried out to write a new voice-over script. The new script minimised visual changes to ensure maximum value for the work already produced but focused on communicating a clear message based on evidence. Visual inaccuracies were corrected and a new audio track (with voice-over, sound effects and background music) was produced by IMI. The video was published on the Project Ô YouTube channel.

In January 2022, it was decided that a brand new video would be produced to include an updated overview of the project. A new script was written to explain how Project Ô supports a circular water economy. The key message was that, while there are 4 demosites and 6 solutions, Project Ô technologies can be replicated and applied much more widely.

Figure 23. Project Ô Overview video

¹⁵ <https://youtu.be/3Eow7Nng4u8>

The IMI team had several meetings with partners from each demosite to fully understand how each of the technologies worked. The script was revised multiple times to ensure that the information was correct, clear and concise. The final version of the script was approved in April 2022 by project coordinator Giulia Molinari (IRIS) and partners from the demosites like SOCAMEX and Fondazione Politecnico.

The production of this video included pre-production (script-writing, storyboards), production (designing and animating infographics, motion graphics, recording voice-over), and post-production (compiling, video and audio editing, visual effects, rendering).

Table 15. Overview video details

Scene	Description	Screenshots
1	Introduction and contextualising the main topic: water	

<p>2</p>	<p>Overview of the problem situation</p>	
<p>3</p>	<p>Explanation of the linear water economy model</p>	<p style="text-align: center;">Linear Water Economy Model</p> </p>

<p>4</p>	<p>Introduction of Project Ô and the circular water economy model</p>	
<p>5</p>	<p>Details of Italy demosite</p>	

<p>6</p>	<p>Details of Israel demosite</p>	

<p>7</p>	<p>Details of Spain demosite</p>	

<p>8</p>	<p>Details of Croatia demosite</p>	

<p>9</p>	<p>Overview of the platforms (DAP and CEP)</p>	

		<p>The diagram illustrates a central system with two main platforms: a green 'Decision Analytic Platform' and an orange 'Circular Economy Platform'. Above these platforms are 'Water Portfolios' represented by water droplets. Below them are 'Water Regulators' (a building icon), 'Businesses' (a multi-story building icon), and 'Stakeholders' (a landscape with buildings, trees, a factory, and crops). Bidirectional arrows connect the platforms to each other and to the surrounding entities, indicating a dynamic, two-way relationship.</p>
<p>10</p>	<p>Project Ô website and social media details</p>	<p>The screenshot shows the Project Ô website interface. At the top is the Project Ô logo and navigation menu. A prominent blue banner asks users to 'SUBSCRIBE TO OUR NEWSLETTER'. Below this, there is a 'CONTACT' section with the Project Coordinator's name and email, a European Union flag with funding information, and a 'SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT GOALS' section. At the bottom, the Project Ô logo and website URL 'www.eu-project-o.eu' are displayed, along with social media icons for Facebook, Twitter, and LinkedIn.</p>

By November 2022, this video¹⁶ had 129 views and a total of 3.7 hours of watch time.

Figure 24. *Project Ô Overview video total views*

¹⁶ <https://youtu.be/4-rmJQgQglA>

Sustainability Analysis videos

A set of explanatory videos was produced about sustainability analysis within the project, including Environmental Life Cycle Assessment, Social Life Cycle Assessment, and Life Cycle Costing. These informational videos were primarily produced for the International School on Water Reuse held at the Chemistry Department of the Torino University in Italy in late September 2022, but they were also placed on the project website and circulated on social media.

Figure 25. Sustainability Analysis videos screenshots

For each pair of words below, please select the point between them that you think best describes your community's water supply.

My community's water supply is...

	3	2	1	0	1	2	3	
Safe	<input type="radio"/>	Risky						
Healthy	<input type="radio"/>	Unhealthy						
Worthless	<input type="radio"/>	Valuable						
Dirty	<input type="radio"/>	Clean						
	3	2	1	0	1	2	3	
Essential	<input type="radio"/>	Unnecessary						
Trustworthy	<input type="radio"/>	Untrustworthy						
Unnatural	<input type="radio"/>	Natural						
Pure	<input type="radio"/>	Impure						

The production of these videos included pre-production (script-writing), production (recording voice-over), and post-production (compiling, video and audio editing). By November 2022, these videos had 88 views and a total of 1.5 hours of watch time.

Table 16. Sustainability Analysis videos views and watch time

Video title	Views	Duration	Total watch time
Environmental Life Cycle Assessment ¹⁷	15	2:52 minutes	12 minutes
Life Cycle Costing ¹⁸	14	2:44 minutes	6 minutes
Social Life Cycle Assessment ¹⁹	59	2:38 minutes	72 minutes

¹⁷ <https://youtu.be/VqYs0R-AM4Q>

¹⁸ <https://youtu.be/NlbzyxglrY>

¹⁹ https://youtu.be/Vtq8t_5ZqCA

Technology videos

As part of the communication strategy, a set of videos focusing on Project Ô water treatment modules (ADV.ERT, SALTECH, MOBILE3TECH and PHOTO.CAT) were produced to increase general awareness of water sustainability innovation solutions that are being implemented in the EU. The aim of the videos was to improve EU taxpayers' attitudes towards investment in research and innovation by demonstrating how funds are invested to solve real-world problems. In addition to being included on the website and shared on social media channels, a version of these videos was used in the Social Acceptance Survey.

ADV.ERT Module videos

Short version video

Using Project Ô deliverables as a reference as well as a series of meetings held with the partners who developed each of the technologies, a first draft of the ADV.ERT module script was written in May 2022 and sent to project coordinator Giulia Molinari (IRIS) and Valter Maurino (University of Turin) for review. After a series of revisions, the script was approved in May 2022. This version of the video was published in July 2022.

Figure 26. ADV.ERT module video

The production of this video included pre-production (script-writing, storyboards), production (designing and animating infographics, creating motion graphics, translating the script to Italian and recording voice-overs), and post-production (compiling, video and audio editing, subtitling, visual effects and rendering).

Table 17. ADV.ERT Module video (short version) details

Scene	Key message	Screenshots	
1	Introduction and contextualising the general problem that the Project Ô demosite situation instantiates		
2	What is being done about the problem?		

<p>3</p>	<p>Details of the Project Ô solution</p>	
<p>4</p>	<p>Benefits of the solution - locally</p>	
<p>5</p>	<p>Project Ô technologies help close the loop on water use - global perspective</p>	

<p>6</p>	<p>Project Ô website and social media details</p>	linkedin/eu-project-o</p>
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Detailed version video

In August 2022, a detailed version of the script was developed. It included more technical details on each of the technologies and the partners involved in their development and implementation. After multiple revisions to refine the technical information and infographics, the script was approved by Simone Barletta (IRIS) in early November 2022. This version of the video was published in November 2022.

Table 18. *Modifications and new elements in ADV.ERT Module detailed version script*

Short version voice-over	Detailed version voice-over
<p>In Puglia, a mobile treatment module, combining two advanced technologies, is cleaning contaminated groundwater in a historic well, restoring this valuable resource.</p>	<p>In Puglia, a mobile Advanced Tertiary Treatment module called “ADV.ERT” has been developed by technology company, IRIS, and Aalborg University. This module cleans contaminated groundwater in a range of water areas, such as historic wells.</p>
<p>This module is designed to be moved around and can be installed easily in remote areas that are far from existing water treatment plants. The module’s two technologies remove harmful bacteria and excess salt from the water. They also reduce potentially harmful levels of pesticides and pharmaceuticals that could be present in the water, making it clean and safe for essential human needs such as drinking and farming.</p>	<p>ADV.ERT is designed to be moved around and can be installed easily in remote areas or isolated communities that are far from existing water treatment plants. The ADV.ERT technology uses two water treatment processes:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Nanofiltration where membranes with nanometer-sized pores remove excess salt from the water, and ● an Advanced Oxidation Process called “High-voltage Nanosecond Pulsed Electric Field”. This process uses low frequency and high voltage nano-pulses to generate a wide spectrum of very active oxidative species. These species reduce potentially harmful microorganisms, such as bacteria, and non-biodegradable pollutants, such as pesticides or pharmaceuticals. <p>These treatment processes have low electric energy consumption, making them cost effective for water reuse. The treated water is clean and safe for essential human needs, such as drinking and farming.</p>

The production of this video included pre-production (script-writing, storyboards), production (designing and animating infographics, creating motion graphics, recording voice-over), and post-production (compiling, video and audio editing, subtitling, visual effects and rendering).

Table 19. Modifications and new elements in ADV.ERT Module detailed version visuals

Short version animations	Detailed version animations

By November 2022, these were the total views and watch time for each video:

Table 20. *ADV.ERT module videos views and watch time*

Video title	Views	Duration	Total watch time
ADV.ERT Module - Social Acceptance Survey ²⁰	13	2:41 minutes	12 minutes
ADV.ERT Module - Social Acceptance Survey (Italian version) ²¹	177	3:04 minutes	438 minutes
ADV.ERT Module ²²	41	2:41 minutes	42 minutes
ADV.ERT Module (Italian version) ²³	50	3:04 minutes	54 minutes
ADV.ERT Module (Detailed version) ²⁴	18	3:23 minutes	18 minutes

²⁰ <https://youtu.be/OfjLbyYaY6A>

²¹ <https://youtu.be/i2F8Gg-GWhk>

²² <https://youtu.be/yphKx0btOU4>

²³ <https://youtu.be/QKHckPtqIQo>

²⁴ <https://youtu.be/0ddXcVCer2k>

MOBILE3TECH Module videos

Short version video

Using Project Ô deliverables as a reference as well as a series of meetings held with the partners who developed each of the technologies, a first draft of the MOBILE3TECH module script was written in May 2022 and sent to project coordinator Giulia Molinari (IRIS), Valter Maurino (University of Turin) and Cristina Herreros (SOCAMEX) for review. After a series of revisions, the script was approved in June 2022. This version of the video was published in July 2022.

Figure 27. MOBILE3TECH module video

Table 21. Examples of storyboards vs final motion graphics used in the MOBILE3TECH module videos

Storyboard	Motion graphic

The production of these videos included pre-production (script-writing, creating storyboards), production (designing and animating infographics, motion graphics, translating the script to Spanish and recording voice-overs), and post-production (compiling, video and audio editing, subtitling, visual effects and rendering).

Table 22. MOBILE3TECH Module video (short version) details

Scene	Key message	Screenshots
1	Introduction and contextualising the general problem that the Project Ô demosite situation instantiates	
2	What is being done about the problem?	
3	Details of the Project Ô solution	

		<p data-bbox="1061 224 1300 280">
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<p>4</p>	<p>Benefits of the solution - locally</p>	
<p>5</p>	<p>Project Ô technologies help close the loop on water use - global perspective</p>	
<p>6</p>	<p>Project Ô website and social media details</p>	<p>SUBSCRIBE TO OUR NEWSLETTER</p> <p>www.eu-project-o.eu</p>

		linkedin/eu-project-o</p>
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Detailed version video

In August 2022, a detailed version of the script was developed. It included more technical details on each of the technologies and the partners involved in their development and implementation. After multiple revisions to refine the technical information and infographics, the script was reviewed by Yolanda Ballesteros (SOCAMEX) and approved by Simone Barletta (IRIS) in early November 2022. This version of the video was published in November 2022.

Table 23. *Modifications and new elements in MOBILE3TECH Module detailed version script*

Short version voice-over	Detailed version voice-over
<p>The set of Project Ô technologies installed in Almendralejo, Spain, addresses many of the challenges associated with organic pollutants, and improves the cleaning and reuse of wastewater.</p>	<p>A water treatment module called “MOBILE3TECH” was developed in a collaboration between three research institutes: the Polytechnic University of Valencia, France’s National Scientific Research Centre and the Israel Institute of Technology.</p> <p>This module is installed by SOCAMEX, a service provider for water treatment located in Almendralejo, Spain, to improve the process of cleaning and reusing water.</p>
<p>Project Ô technology allows early detection of excessive water pollution from local food-based industries. Once detected, this wastewater is diverted for extra treatment before reaching the plant’s main system. This new treatment step is critical to protect the plant.</p> <p>This combination of early detection and as-needed extra treatment also saves energy and money by applying water cleaning technology in a targeted way.</p> <p>The Project Ô solution also includes technology that adds an additional layer of treatment after the water leaves the plant’s main system.</p>	<p>The water treatment plant in Almendralejo redirects samples of used water to MOBILE3TECH, which has an advanced control unit that assesses the toxicity levels as an early detection step. The control unit determines if the used water is within acceptable thresholds to go directly to the treatment plant or if pre-treatment is required.</p> <p>If used water requires pre-treatment, it will go through additional steps that reduce water toxicity levels. The first step is advanced adsorption which uses activated carbon, a low cost material, to filter contaminants from</p>

<p>This additional treatment enables the water to be immediately reused for vital human needs such as farming.</p>	<p>the water. The second step is an Advanced Oxidation Process called “solar photo-Fenton” which targets any remaining contaminants in the used water.</p> <p>These extra pre-treatment steps are effectively targeted to conserve energy and lower water toxicity level to thresholds that protect the treatment plant’s main system.</p> <p>Finally, MOBILE3TECH uses a tertiary treatment for advanced absorption that can remove emerging pollutants after the water leaves the plant’s main system.</p>
<p>Project Ô’s technologies increase the sustainable reuse of wastewater by helping to ensure it is thoroughly and efficiently cleaned, so it can once again help to meet human needs. This reduces the demands on finite water resources.</p>	<p>Project Ô’s technologies improve the sustainable water reuse by effectively targeting and removing contaminants in wastewater before and after treatment at plants, so used water can once again help to meet human needs. These treatment steps reduce the demands on finite water resources and protect the environment and human health.</p>

The production of this video included pre-production (script-writing, creating storyboards), production (designing and animating infographics, motion graphics, translating the script to Spanish and recording voice-overs), and post-production (compiling, video and audio editing, subtitling, visual effects and rendering).

Table 24. Modifications and new elements in MOBILE3TECH Module detailed version visuals

Short version animations	Detailed version animations

By November 2022, these were the total views and watch time for each video:

Table 25. MOBILE3TECH module videos views and watch time

Video title	Views	Duration	Total watch time
MOBILE3TECH Module - Social Acceptance Survey ²⁵	14	2:49 minutes	12 minutes
MOBILE3TECH Module - Social Acceptance Survey (Spanish version) ²⁶	184	3:10 minutes	438 minutes
MOBILE3TECH Module ²⁷	32	2:49 minutes	30 minutes
Módulo MOBILE3TECH (Spanish version) ²⁸	22	3:10 minutes	18 minutes
MOBILE3TECH Module (Detailed version) ²⁹	21	3:38 minutes	18 minutes

²⁵ <https://youtu.be/9DkInFV2IE8>

²⁶ <https://youtu.be/BWJ9gpOYTdg>

²⁷ <https://youtu.be/ULxYD6X2iOk>

²⁸ https://youtu.be/CDMCib_xp7Y

²⁹ <https://youtu.be/3Tk78YpPfO4>

PHOTO.CAT Unit videos

Short version video

Using Project Ô deliverables as a reference as well as a series of meetings held with the partners who developed each of the technologies, a first draft of the PHOTO.CAT Unit script was written in May 2022 and sent to project coordinator Giulia Molinari (IRIS) and Valter Maurino (University of Turin) for review. After a series of revisions, the script was approved in July 2022. This version of the video was published in July 2022.

Figure 28. PHOTO.CAT Unit video

Table 26. Examples of storyboards vs final motion graphics used in the PHOTO.CAT Unit videos

Storyboard	Motion graphic

The production of this video included pre-production (script-writing, creating storyboards), production (designing and animating infographics, motion graphics, translating the script to Croatian, recording voice-over), and post-production (compiling, video and audio editing, subtitling, visual effects and rendering).

Table 27. PHOTO.CAT Unit video (short version) details

Scene	Key message	Screenshots
1	Introduction and contextualising the general problem that the Project Ô demosite situation instantiates	
2	What is being done about the problem?	

<p>3</p>	<p>Details of the Project Ô solution</p>	
<p>4</p>	<p>Benefits of the solution - locally</p>	

<p>5</p>	<p>Project Ô technologies help close the loop on water use - global perspective</p>	
<p>6</p>	<p>Project Ô website and social media details</p>	<p>SUBSCRIBE TO OUR NEWSLETTER</p> <p>www.eu-project-o.eu</p> linkedin/eu-project-ô </p>

Detailed version video

In August 2022, a detailed version of the script was developed. It included more technical details on each of the technologies and the partners involved in their development and implementation. After multiple revisions to refine the technical information and infographics, the script was reviewed and approved by Simone Barletta (IRIS) in early November 2022. This version of the video was published in November 2022.

Table 28. *Modifications and new elements in PHOTO.CAT Unit detailed version script*

Short version voice-over	Detailed version voice-over
<p>Project Ô technologies in the treatment plant remove harmful chemicals and organic pollutants and recover salts from the water.</p> <p>The treatment process is designed to automatically mix different streams of treated water to ensure the right salt levels and temperatures for making clothing materials.</p> <p>These targeted treatments enable the factory's immediate reuse of the water, and also boost energy efficiency because the treated water is already optimised for clothing production.</p>	<p>PHOTO.CAT is a modular unit developed by the University of Turin and Aalborg University that removes harmful chemicals from water used in textile production.</p> <p>This water treatment module is composed of a solar photoreactor that produces superoxide and hydrogen peroxide, which are capable of removing bacteria and organic pollutants from water.</p> <p>In addition, the module is equipped with a nanofiltration unit where nanoporous membranes reduce and recover salts from the water.</p> <p>The combination of these two technical components allows the treatment plant to automatically combine streams of used water and ensure the salt levels and temperatures are calibrated for colouring clothing materials.</p> <p>These targeted treatments enable water reuse and boost energy efficiency because the treated water is ready for clothing production.</p>

The production of this video included pre-production (script-writing, creating storyboards), production (designing and animating infographics, motion graphics and recording voice-over), and post-production (compiling, video and audio editing, subtitling, visual effects and rendering).

Table 29. Modifications and new elements in PHOTO.CAT Unit detailed version visuals

Short version animations	Detailed version animations

By November 2022, these were the total views and watch time for each video:

Table 30. PHOTO.CAT Unit videos views and watch time

Video title	Views	Duration	Total watch time
PHOTO.CAT Unit - Social Acceptance Survey ³⁰	190	2:51 minutes	396 minutes
PHOTO.CAT Unit ³¹	32	2:51 minutes	42 minutes
PHOTO.CAT Unit (Detailed version) ³²	11	3:17 minutes	18 minutes

³⁰ <https://youtu.be/UNuWRRcJsYs>

³¹ https://youtu.be/q3_CPnOg4nc

³² <https://youtu.be/006CRb2FhAU>

SALTECH Module videos

Short version video

Using Project Ô deliverables as a reference as well as a series of meetings held with the partners who developed each of the technologies, a first draft of the SALTECH module script was written in May 2022 and sent to project coordinator Giulia Molinari (IRIS) and Valter Maurino (University of Turin) for review. After a series of revisions, the script was approved in July 2022. This version of the video was published in August 2022.

Figure 29. SALTECH module video

Table 31. Examples of storyboards vs final motion graphics used in the SALTECH module videos

Storyboard	Motion graphic

The production of this video included pre-production (script-writing, creating storyboards), production (designing and animating infographics,

motion graphics, translating the script to Hebrew and Arabic, recording voice-over), and post-production (compiling, video and audio editing, subtitling, visual effects and rendering).

Table 32. SALTECH Module video (short version) details

Scene	Key message	Screenshots	
1	Introduction and contextualising the general problem that the Project Ô demosite situation instantiates		

2	What is being done about the problem?	

<p>3</p>	<p>Details of the Project Ô solution</p>	<p>The diagram illustrates the Project Ô solution through five stages:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> Project Ô (Logo): Three water drop icons containing a molecular structure, a yellow symbol, and two cubes. Project Ô (Logo): Three water drop icons with red 'X' marks over the molecular structure, yellow symbol, and cubes. Project Ô (Logo): A water drop icon with a circular arrow, an arrow pointing to a hexagonal tank containing fish, and a plant icon. Project Ô (Logo): A water tap icon with a magnifying glass over a circular area containing green particles. Project Ô (Logo): A water tap icon with a magnifying glass over a circular area containing green particles, a smartphone, a car, a plant, and a money bag.
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<p>4</p>	<p>Benefits of the solution - locally</p>	
<p>5</p>	<p>Project Ô technologies help close the loop on water use - global perspective</p>	

<p>6</p>	<p>Project Ô website and social media details</p>	<p>The image displays a promotional graphic for Project Ô. At the top right is a screenshot of the Project Ô website with the headline "Developing practical tools for a circular water economy" and a "Learn more" button. Below this is the text "SUBSCRIBE TO OUR NEWSLETTER" and the website URL "www.eu-project-o.eu". The central part of the graphic features the Project Ô logo, which consists of a blue circle with three white wavy lines, followed by the text "Project Ô" and "Innovative circular water systems". Below the logo is the website URL "www.eu-project-o.eu". At the bottom, there are three social media icons: Facebook with the handle "facebook/euprojecto", Twitter with "twitter/EUProjectO", and LinkedIn with "linkedin/eu-project-ô".</p>
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Detailed version video

In August 2022, a detailed version of the script was developed. It included more technical details on each of the technologies and the partners involved in their development and implementation. After multiple revisions to refine the technical information and infographics, the script was reviewed and approved by Simone Barletta (IRIS) in early November 2022. This version of the video was published in November 2022.

Table 33. *Modifications and new elements in SALTECH Module detailed version script*

Short version voice-over	Detailed version voice-over
<p>Project Ô's water treatment technologies are installed at the National Center for Mariculture in Israel for wastewater from land-based fish farms.</p>	<p>Project Ô's water treatment module, called SALTECH, is installed at the National Center for Mariculture in Israel to treat wastewater from land-based fish farms.</p>
<p>Project Ô technologies remove nitrates, other pollutants and excess salts from the water, which enables it to be sustainably reused in fish tanks or to water plants.</p> <p>These technologies also allow for valuable nutrients to be recovered from the wastewater, which can then be used as fish food or processed further to be used as biofuel or green fertilisers.</p>	<p>SALTECH, developed by technology company IRIS, Aalborg University, France's National Scientific Research Centre and Israel's Oceanographic and Limnological Research implements two processes:</p> <p>First, wastewater from a fish tank passes through a filter which separates solid particles and recovers valuable nutrients which can then be used as fish food or processed further to be used as biofuel or green fertiliser.</p> <p>Next, the wastewater continues to denitrification reactors, where the nitrate level is reduced. A percentage of the treated water is then discharged into the sea.</p> <p>The rest of the water, intended for reuse in the fish tanks, moves through an algae plant to further remove nitrates and then through advanced adsorption treatment using activated carbon to further clean the water.</p> <p>If the water is intended for reuse in the fish tanks, it is channelled back to the tanks. If it is intended to water crops, the water passes through two additional stages of treatment:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● an Advanced Oxidation Process called High-voltage Nanosecond Pulsed Electric Field, which generates very active oxidative species

	<p>using nanosecond-pulsed electric discharges that remove potentially harmful levels of bacteria, pesticides and pharmaceuticals that could be present in the water; and</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • membrane distillation where water is filtered through nanometer sized pores to remove excess salts.
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The production of this video included pre-production (script-writing, creating storyboards), production (designing and animating infographics, motion graphics and recording voice-over), and post-production (compiling, video and audio editing, subtitling, visual effects and rendering).

Table 34. Modifications and new elements in SALTECH Module detailed version visuals

Short version animations	Detailed version animations

By November 2022, these were the total views and watch time for each video:

Table 35. SALTECH module videos views and watch time

Video title	Views	Duration	Total watch time
SALTECH Module - Social Acceptance Survey ³³	186	3:24 minutes	378 minutes
SALTECH Module ³⁴	41	3:24 minutes	36 minutes
SALTECH Module (Detailed version) ³⁵	41	4:33 minutes	30 minutes

Water Governance video

In the case of the “Key propositions to develop and strengthen the governance of a circular water economy” video used in WP3 co-creation workshops, IMI produced the entire video based on a document provided by the University of Aveiro (UAVR). A first draft of the script was sent to Teresa Fidélis (UAVR) for review. After a series of revisions, the script was approved in March 2022 and the video was published in April 2022.

Table 36. “Key propositions to develop and strengthen the governance of a circular water economy” video details

Scene	Voice-over	Screenshots
1	A successful transition towards a circular water economy requires an integrated approach to water resource management. It is necessary to consider new water uses and users, and the water-land use nexus.	

³³ <https://youtu.be/zle5IXkQoQc>

³⁴ <https://youtu.be/zsLGwyDLmpQ>

³⁵ <https://youtu.be/CqqfM5MyaAM>

2	Dedicated policy instruments, adequate legal and regulatory frameworks, favourable water resources and spatial plans are key factors to consider for a successful transition.	
3	The University of Aveiro presents eight key institutional design propositions to develop and strengthen the governance of a circular water economy.	
4	1. Clearly defined boundaries and responsibilities. This relates to the existing borders between allowed users and free riders, and ensures a clear perception of the responsibilities of agencies and stakeholders regarding new types of water.	1. Clearly defined boundaries and responsibilities
5	2. Congruence between appropriation and provision rules as well as local conditions and uncertainties. This relates to understanding the difficulty in the implementation of new water loops concerning the existing regulations, and local context.	2. Congruence between appropriation and provision rules as well as local conditions and uncertainties
6	3. Monitoring and evaluation of the process. This relates to understanding monitoring processes and guarantees safety of the use of water, and the involvement of people affected indirectly	3. Monitoring and evaluation of the process

	<p>by new water.</p>	
<p>7</p>	<p>4. Conflict prevention and resolution mechanisms. This relates to understanding if stakeholders have rapid access to low cost, local arenas to resolve conflict among users, or between users and officials. This principle stresses the need to discuss the rules to understand what infraction is and how conflicts can be reduced.</p>	<p>4. Conflict prevention and resolution mechanisms</p>
<p>8</p>	<p>5. Equal and fair (re)distribution of risks, benefits, and costs. This relates to the understanding of mechanisms of distribution of costs and benefits generated by the new water loops. It seeks to balance the distribution of costs and benefits.</p>	<p>5. Equal and fair (re)distribution of risks, benefits, and costs</p>
<p>9</p>	<p>6. Collective choice arrangements. This relates to understanding to what extent stakeholders are involved in the process, and if individuals affected by rules can participate in the modification of the operational rules and decisions.</p>	<p>6. Collective choice arrangements</p>

<p>10</p>	<p>7. Graduated sanctions. This relates to understanding rules and sanctions for non-compliance behaviours associated with the use or abuse of new water. This principle warns participants that if they break the rules (repeatedly) they will pay more. If this behaviour continues, they will be forced to leave the system.</p>	<p>7. Graduated sanctions</p>
<p>11</p>	<p>8. Flexibility of the process. This relates to understanding to what extent the governance model of water reuse can adopt new water loops and adapt to changes and uncertainties.</p>	<p>8. Flexibility of the process</p>
<p>12</p>	<p>While policy, regulatory and planning conditions influence the challenges of water reuse, successful implementation of these recommendations can facilitate the transition to a circular water economy.</p>	

The production included pre-production (script-writing), production (translating the script to Spanish and Italian and recording voice-overs), and post-production (compiling, video and audio editing, subtitling and rendering). A Spanish version of the video was produced under the name “Propuestas para desarrollar y fortalecer una gobernanza de la economía circular del agua”.

Figure 30. “Key propositions to develop and strengthen the governance of a circular water economy” video script translation screenshot

ENGLISH VERSION	SPANISH TRANSLATION	ITALIAN TRANSLATION
A successful transition towards a circular water economy requires an integrated approach to water resource management. It is necessary to consider new water uses and users, and the water-land use nexus.	Una transición eficaz hacia una economía circular del agua requiere un enfoque de gestión integrada de los recursos hídricos en el que sea importante considerar los nuevos usos y consumidores de agua, y el nexo entre su uso y el de la tierra.	Una transizione positiva verso un'economia circolare dell'acqua richiede un approccio integrato di gestione delle risorse idriche in cui è importante considerare i nuovi usi e consumatori dell'acqua oltre al nesso di uso dell'acqua e del suolo.
Dedicated policy instruments, adequate legal and regulatory frameworks, favorable water resources and spatial plans are key factors to consider for a successful transition.	Los instrumentos de política específicos, los marcos jurídicos y reglamentarios adecuados, los recursos hídricos favorables, así como los planes de ordenación territorial son factores clave que hay que considerar para obtener una transición eficaz.	Strumenti politici dedicati, quadri giuridici e normativi adeguati, risorse idriche e piani territoriali favorevoli sono fattori chiave da considerare per una transizione di successo.
The University of Aveiro presents eight key institutional design propositions to develop and strengthen the governance of a circular water economy.	En este sentido, la Universidad de Aveiro (UAVR) nos presenta ocho propuestas clave de diseño institucional para desarrollar y fortalecer la gobernanza de una economía circular del agua.	In questo senso, l'Università di Aveiro (UAVR) presenta otto proposte chiave di progettazione istituzionale per sviluppare e rafforzare l'amministrazione di un'economia circolare dell'acqua.
1. Clearly defined boundaries and responsibilities. This relates to the existing borders between allowed users and free riders, and ensures a clear perception of the responsibilities of agencies and stakeholders regarding new types of water.	1. Límites y responsabilidades bien definidos. Esto está relacionado con los límites existentes entre los consumidores permitidos y aquellos independientes. Esto garantiza una clara percepción de las responsabilidades de los organismos y las partes interesadas, con lo que se refiere a los nuevos tipos de agua.	1. Limiti e responsabilità ben definiti. È correlato al confine esistente tra consumatori autorizzati e free riders e garantisce una chiara percezione delle responsabilità delle agenzie e delle parti interessate per quanto riguarda i nuovi tipi di acqua.

By November 2022, these were the statuses, total views and watch time for each video:

Table 37. *Water governance videos views and watch time*

Video title	Status	Views	Duration	Total watch time
Key propositions to develop and strengthen the governance of a circular water economy ³⁶	Public	11	3:30 minutes	12 minutes
Propuestas para desarrollar y fortalecer una gobernanza de la economía circular del agua ³⁷	Public	2	4:03 minutes	6 minutes

Internal event videos

As part of Project Ô's communication efforts, two international events were organised aimed at extended networks with a focus on political communication and science advocacy relevant to water reuse (see Event Management section for details). These online public events were recorded and edited for publication on the YouTube channel.

Table 38. *International event videos views and watch time*

Video title	Views	Duration	Total watch time
Impact planning using logic models and theory of change with Mark Reed, Eric Jensen and Sarah Bowman ³⁸	524	52:02 minutes	2,508 minutes
How to make a difference in science policy with your research with Eric Jensen and Andrew George ³⁹	N/A ⁴⁰	1:22:10 minutes	N/A

Other videos

A set of other videos were produced during RP3 to support co-creation workshops and public engagement events. Content was generally provided by partners, in the form of a recorded PowerPoint presentation, and edited by IMI. Given that some of these videos were suitable for use on other platforms, such

³⁶ <https://youtu.be/71trKISjnEs>

³⁷ <https://youtu.be/P8DAz8jjKwc>

³⁸ https://youtu.be/m_jsRdQ1_xs

³⁹ <https://youtu.be/iuX68afwtmc>

⁴⁰ By the time this deliverable was written, the recording of the second international event was just published (25 November 2022).

as social media channels, they were published on the YouTube channels. Videos that were not suitable for publication were uploaded to the YouTube channel and set as private.

By November 2022, these were the statuses, total views and watch time for each video:

Table 39. Other videos status, views and watch time

Video title	Status	Views	Duration	Total watch time
Puglia Region Aquifer Background ⁴¹	Private	33	1:31 minutes	24 minutes
1 April 2022 Co-creation Workshop SOCAMEX Presentation ⁴²	Private	8	7:27 minutes	18 minutes
AQP Well walkthrough ⁴³	Private	1	6:13 minutes	6 minutes
De un modelo lineal del agua a uno circular ⁴⁴	Public	12	1:31 minutes	12 minutes
Problemas y oportunidades en la EDAR de Almendralejo ⁴⁵	Public	14	1:41 minutes	12 minutes
Planta de tratamiento en Almendralejo y nuevos circuitos del agua ⁴⁶	Public	5	1:46 minutes	6 minutes
Usos del agua regenerada en Almendralejo ⁴⁷	Public	11	2:12 minutes	6 minutes
Objetivos del demosite de Almendralejo ⁴⁸	Public	7	1:32 minutes	6 minutes
Galeb Presentation WP3 Co-Creation Workshop ⁴⁹	Private	5	5:51 minutes	12 minutes

⁴¹ <https://youtu.be/oNz9EIDeDNO>

⁴² <https://youtu.be/wFBttawx8UE>

⁴³ <https://youtu.be/zVJdWTP2vYg>

⁴⁴ https://youtu.be/ynqWHufPN_I

⁴⁵ <https://youtu.be/iOkIxeQfQ9M>

⁴⁶ https://youtu.be/E153a54Um_A

⁴⁷ https://youtu.be/_jYd5k86aQ

⁴⁸ <https://youtu.be/lmk4sQNPmGY>

⁴⁹ <https://youtu.be/HJN7OxFxcrE>

Social media report

Social media was used to coordinate communication about the different aspects of the project. In the internal stakeholder analysis report (see D8.1), most stakeholders agreed (56%) that social media was preferable as a channel for communicating project information. This aligned with more general preferences that social media be used in EU-funded projects (EC, 2018, p. 7) to convey a broader range of Project Ô-related subject matter to its audiences. The social media communications output from the project was greatly extended when IMI joined the project as a partner, taking full responsibility for the social media channels, including content production, preparing supporting visuals, outreach to potential followers, responding to users' comments, etc.

The revised social media strategy and planned media releases have been followed during RP3, with a major increase in communications and audience engagement visible since IMI took up this work. These releases are being distributed throughout the remaining time in the project and coordinated with objectives for key stakeholder audiences. For this, project partners are liaised with to source visual materials. A database was created for documenting past posts and forecasting future posts.

Moreover, the social media visual identity was updated, including new headers, profile pictures and descriptions. For the reactivated Twitter, Facebook and Instagram feeds, as well as the newly set up LinkedIn and YouTube accounts, messaging guidelines and templates were developed for partners to share Project Ô updates on their social media channels. On an ongoing basis, IMI has been managing social media engagement with followers.

Table 40. *Social media overview*

Social media platform	End-of-project follower counts (November 2022)
YouTube	1.8k views
Twitter ⁵⁰	514
Facebook	46
LinkedIn	71
Internal newsletter	51
External newsletter	28

⁵⁰ The Twitter account, established June 2018, had 303 followers until October 2019 and 513 followers as of November 2022. The Twitter account has been the primary channel used to release information about the project.

Twitter platform report

Project Ô's Twitter account⁵¹ shared similar information to that posted on the Facebook page, but with a stronger emphasis on participation in ongoing conversations through Retweets or Direct Mentions. By November 2022, the page had 514 followers. While the strategy required a minimum of five tweets per week, the final daily number depended entirely on the dynamics of the Twitter Timeline.

Figure 31. Twitter profile

Twitter Key Performance Indicators

Follower Growth

By November 2022, Project Ô's Twitter account had 514 followers, showing an **increase of 40%** in comparison to the previous period (July 2017-July 2018). In the reporting period the account has gained 149 followers, an average of 14 new followers per month. The most used hashtags were #EUProjectO (130 tweets), #WaterTreatment (55 tweets), and #WaterManagement (18 tweets).

⁵¹ <https://twitter.com/EUProjectO>

Figure 32. Twitter followers (Jan - Nov 2022)

Audience Engagement and Reach

The 200 tweets published during RP3 had a total of **295 retweets**, **19,071 impressions**, **1,182 engagements**, **67 clicks** and **642 likes**. From January 2022 to November 2022, Project Ô’s Twitter profile had an average of **95 impressions** and **6 engagements per tweet**.

Figure 33. Tweets average performance (Jan - Nov 2022)

The definition of a “good” engagement rate⁵² depends on the social channel, and it heavily depends on the way the algorithm of the channel works. In general terms, an engagement rate of 0.5% is considered good for Twitter, with anything above 1% great. According to Twitter analytics, several Project Ô tweets had a more than **14% engagement rate** from January 2022 to November 2022.

⁵² (Comments + Clicks + Shares + Reactions) divided by Impressions.

The following are examples of posts with corresponding impressions and engagement rates:

Table 41. Tweets with impressions and engagement rates (Jan - Nov 2022)

Twitter Posts	Engagement Data
<p>7:02 AM · Jun 15, 2022 · Buffer</p>	<p>Impressions: 72 Engagement rate: 17% Clicks: 4 Retweets: 2 Likes: 4</p>
<p>5:17 AM · Nov 14, 2022 · Buffer</p>	<p>Impressions: 59 Engagement rate: 15% Clicks: 1 Retweets: 1 Likes: 4</p>

Project O
@EUProjectO

#EUProjectO demosites have planning and water utility companies who are facing a range of water management challenges. They support the new water treatment technologies being installed. Learn more at eu-project-o.eu

The diagram illustrates the 'Circular Water Economy' as a continuous cycle. At the center is 'Circular Water Economy'. Surrounding it are four main stages: 'Water Treatment & Transport' at the bottom, 'Water Abstraction' on the right, 'Replenish Water Store' at the top, and 'Wastewater Treatment' on the left. A 'Reuse' loop is shown on the left side. Arrows indicate the flow of water between these stages. National flags are placed around the cycle: Israel (top left), Croatia (left), Spain (top), and Italy (right). A callout box for Israel states 'Becomes by-products & energy for reuse'.

5:28 AM · Oct 12, 2022 · Buffer

Impressions: 46
Engagement rate: 15%
Clicks: 0
Retweets: 1
Likes: 5

Project O
@EUProjectO

#EUProjectO Circular Economy Platform is designed to allow the local trade of water and by-products between different water users involved in water treatment activities. Learn more at eu-project-o.eu

The GIF shows a hand holding a tablet. The tablet screen displays a trading interface with a bar chart showing green and red bars, a play button in the center, and two buttons labeled 'BUY' (green) and 'SELL' (red) at the bottom.

GIF

3:21 AM · Jul 8, 2022 · Buffer

Impressions: 27
Engagement rate: 15%
Clicks: 0
Retweets: 1
Likes: 2

Hashtag Performance

Although the most used hashtags were #EUProjectO (with 92 impressions and 7% engagement rate), #WaterTreatment (with 102 impressions and 7% engagement rate), and #WaterManagement (with 108 impressions and 5% engagement rate), the ones with the highest engagement rate were the following:

Table 42. Hashtags with highest engagement rate (Jan - Nov 2022)

Hashtag	Posts	Average impressions	Average engagement rate
#PublicEngagement	3	68	9%
#WaterFiltration	2	135	9%
#CircularEconomyApproach	1	83	8%
#WaterSustainability	1	76	8%
#WaterReuse	2	56	8%

Facebook platform report

The Project Ô Facebook page⁵³ shared project updates, interesting news related to water sustainability, information about upcoming events, and information about partners' activities. The frequency of posts was an average of three per week, resulting in approximately **132 posts during RP3**.

Figure 34. Facebook page

Facebook Key Performance Indicators

Followers Growth

By November 2022 the Facebook page had 46 followers. The number of page followers were maintained during RP3, increasing by 5 by the end of November 2022. Although the number of followers was steady from January 2022 to November 2022, the **number of engaged users increased to 211**, a considerable growth compared to the 5 engaged users in RP2. It is also important to note that the majority of the water sustainability community is more likely to use Twitter as their primary social media channel.

Page Visits

Unlike the page Likes and Followers, the page Visits section allows us to see data about the individuals who choose to browse a Facebook page (whether they are followers or not). This data can indicate whether people are using the Project Ô page to look for information about water sustainability or to find out about upcoming events. An actual visit to the Project Ô profile page marks a higher level of engagement than simply liking a post in the News Feed.

⁵³ <http://www.facebook.com/euprojectoeu>

This suggests a more active interest in Project Ô than a convenience-based Like and/or Follow.

In a year span, there was a 200% increase in page visits with three spikes: the first one in July 2022 (related to the co-creation events held in Spain), the second one in October 2022 (related to the International School on Water Reuse held at the Chemistry Department of the Torino University in Italy in late September), and the third one in November 2022 (related to partners' outreach activities).

Figure 35. Facebook page visits (Jan - Nov 2022)

Page Reach

While page Followers show the opted-in audience and page Visits show how many people browse a profile, the page Reach goes beyond to show how many people, followers or not, actually see posts and publications. This includes eyes on the content as an organic post in a News Feed, a promoted post, or a post a friend commented on.

Similar to the page Visits, in a full year there was a 418% increase in page reach with one major spike in May 2022 (related to a post about the four demosites).

Audience Engagement and Reach

The 161 posts on Facebook during RP3 had a total of 336 engagements, 1,771 impressions, 252 reactions and 839 total reach⁵⁴. From January 2022 to November 2022, Project Ô's Facebook page had an average of 1 daily engagement and 5 daily impressions.

⁵⁴ Number of unique people who saw the posts.

Figure 36. Facebook posts average performance (Jan - Nov 2022)

According to Facebook Insights, the following posts reached more people than 98-100% of Project Ô most recent Facebook posts and stories.

Table 43. Facebook posts with highest engagement rate (Jan - Nov 2022)

Facebook Posts	Engagement Notes
<p>EU Project Ô Published by Buffer · May 6 ·</p> <p>Four sites across Europe and Israel are home to the first installations of #EUProjectO #WaterTreatment modules using a #CircularWaterEconomy. Learn more at https://www.eu-project-o.eu</p>	<p>Reach: 132 Date: 6 May 2022 Type: Text + image</p>

<p>EU Project Ó Published by Buffer · July 29 ·</p> <p>En este video, nuestros colegas de SOCAMEX (@urbaser_) explican los objetivos de la planta piloto del demosite en Almendralejo en cuanto a la reutilización del agua.</p> <p>Demosite Almendralejo Project Ó</p> <p>IMI Institute for Methods Innovation socamex</p> <p>YOUTUBE.COM Objetivos del demosite de Almendralejo Nuestros colegas de SOCAMEX explican los objetivos del demosite en Almendralejo en cuanto...</p>	<p>Reach: 16 Date: 29 July 2022 Type: Text + video</p>
<p>EU Project Ó Published by Danny Martin · November 10 at 10:39 AM ·</p> <p>Today, Giulia Molinari from Iris srl - playground for new ideas talked about how #EUProjectO is developing practical tools for a #CircularWaterEconomy at Ecomondo. We will share the interview soon!</p>	<p>Reach: 14 Date: 10 November 2022 Type: Text + image</p>

<p> <p>ELPAIS.COM Espronceda, su turbulento romance con Teresa y tecnologías para aprovechar hasta la última gota</p>	<p>Reach: 12 Date: 14 October 2022 Type: Text + link</p>
<p> <p>YOUTUBE.COM Project Ô PHOTO.CAT Unit Project Ô has developed the PHOTO.CAT unit to treat water used in textile production. It will re...</p>	<p>Reach: 12 Date: 24 August 2022 Type: Text + video</p>

LinkedIn Platform Report

The Project Ô LinkedIn page⁵⁵ was focused on the technical community. It shared project updates, articles and news related to water sustainability, information about upcoming events, and information about partners' activities. The frequency of posts was an average of two per week, resulting in approximately **100 posts during RP3**.

Figure 37. LinkedIn page

LinkedIn Key Performance Indicators

Follower Growth

The LinkedIn profile was reactivated at the beginning of RP3 and by November 2022 it had **71 followers**, gaining an average of 6 new followers per month.

Figure 38. LinkedIn page followers (Jan - Nov 2022)

The followers were mainly located in Italy (23%), Denmark (6%), Portugal (3%) and Croatia (3%), coinciding with Project Ô demosites and

⁵⁵ <https://www.linkedin.com/company/eu-project-ô/>

partners' locations. The main job functions of the followers were education (11%), research (11%), media and communication (10%), program and project management (10%) and business development (7%). Finally, the majority of followers worked in research services (19%), higher education (11%), business consulting and services (9%), and non-profit organisations (7%).

Page Visits

Page Visits are the total number of page views and unique visitors over time (whether they are followers or not). In a year span, there were **381 page views and 122 unique visitors**. During this period there were two spikes: the first one in July 2022 (related to the co-creation events held in Spain) and the second one in November 2022 (related to the International School on Water Reuse held at the Chemistry Department of the Torino University in Italy).

Figure 39. LinkedIn page visits (Jan - Nov 2022)

Audience Engagement and Reach

The 132 posts on LinkedIn during RP3 had a total of **5,822 impressions**⁵⁶, **156 likes**, **294 clicks** and an **8% engagement rate**. From January 2022 to November 2022, Project Ô's LinkedIn page had an average of **44 impressions and 3 clicks per post**.

Figure 40. LinkedIn posts average performance (Jan - Nov 2022)

As previously mentioned, the definition of a “good” engagement rate depends on the social channel, and it heavily depends on the way the algorithm of the channel works. In general terms, an engagement rate of 2% is considered good for LinkedIn, with anything above 5-6% great. According to LinkedIn analytics, several Project Ô posts had **more than 28% of engagement rate** from January 2022 to November 2022.

The following are examples of posts with corresponding impressions and engagement rates. In the particular case of LinkedIn, some of the posts with the highest engagement rates were originally written by other project partners (mainly Particular Group in Croatia), which demonstrates that the community was active and engaged with Project Ô activities.

⁵⁶ Number of times people saw the posts.

Table 44. LinkedIn posts with impressions and engagement rates (Jan - Nov 2022)

LinkedIn Posts	Engagement Data
<p>	<p>Impressions: 80</p> <p>Engagement: 31</p> <p>Likes: 4</p> <p>Clicks: 26</p> <p>Engagement rate: 39%</p>
<p> <p>De un modelo lineal del agua a uno circular youtube.com</p>	<p>Impressions: 10</p> <p>Engagement: 3</p> <p>Likes: 2</p> <p>Clicks: 0</p> <p>Engagement rate: 30%</p>

<p>EU Project Ö reposted this</p> <p>Particula Group 107 followers 1w • 🌐</p> <p>[SUTRA] • otvoreni pristup webinaru na temu: EU Project Ö "Gospodarenje otpadnim vodama u tekstilnoj industriji u Hrvatskoj " 15.11.2022. u 13:00 h</p> <p>Microsoft Teams Platforma: https://bit.ly/3tfUGMY</p> <p>Demo site / Hrvatska, Omiš - Galeb d.d.</p> <p>Program i viš informacija na sljedećoj poveznici: https://lnkd.in/drBnHRBK</p> <p>#euprojecto #watermanagement #CircularEconomy</p> <p>See translation</p>	<p>Impressions: 34</p> <p>Engagement: 10</p> <p>Likes: 0</p> <p>Clicks: 10</p> <p>Engagement rate: 29%</p>
<p>EU Project Ö reposted this</p> <p>Particula Group 107 followers 2w • Edited • 🌐</p> <p>WEBINAR HR EU Project Ö "Gospodarenje otpadnim vodama u tekstilnoj industriji" 15.11.2022. u 13:00 h</p> <p>Na sljedećoj poveznici pozvani ste priključiti se putem Microsoft Teams Platforme: https://bit.ly/3tfUGMY</p> <p>Ovaj je projekt financiran iz programa Europske unije za istraživanje i inovacije Obzor 2020. u okviru ugovora o dodjeli bespovratnih sredstava br. 776816. Poziv za podnošenje prijedloga: H2020-CIRC-2017TwoStage.</p> <p>#euprojecto #watermanagement #circulareconomy #innovation #technology #sustainabledevelopment #webinar</p> <p>See translation</p>	<p>Impressions: 41</p> <p>Engagement: 12</p> <p>Likes: 0</p> <p>Clicks: 12</p> <p>Engagement rate: 29%</p>

EU Project O
71 followers
6mo •

...

Particula Group + Follow
7mo • Edited •

EU Project O develops #water management and treatment technologies to improve #watermanagement for communities in Europe and beyond. Croatian textile company #Galeb from #Omis is building a new water treatment plant as part of their factory development.

<https://lnkd.in/dvNcM8kq>

#development #project #management #textile #croatia #sustainability #sustainabledevelopment #technologyinnovation

HORIZON 2020 PROJECT O – Press Release, CROATIA
particula-group.com • 5 min read

Impressions: 7

Engagement: 2

Likes: 2

Clicks: 0

Engagement rate: 29%

Hashtag Performance

Although the most used hashtags were #EUProjectO (with 68 impressions and 5.15% engagement rate), #WaterTreatment (with 36 impressions and 5% engagement rate), and #WaterManagement (with 6 impressions and 2% engagement rate), the ones with the highest engagement rate were the following:

Table 45. Hashtags with highest engagement rate (Jan - Nov 2022)

Hashtag	Posts	Average impressions	Average engagement rate
#PublicEngagement	2	76	14%
#Water	1	8	13%
#WaterTreatments	1	39	8%
#IFAT2022	1	167	7%
#WaterReuse	2	89	6%

YouTube platform report

The Project Ô YouTube channel⁵⁷ was created to host a suite of videos created to enhance engagement with the website and social media channels. By November 2022, the YouTube channel had 13 subscribers.

Figure 41. YouTube channel

A total of 34 videos were published (23 public and 11 private):

#	Video title	Status
1	Project Ô Overview (Original version)	Private
2	Project Ô Overview (Updated version)	Public
3	Puglia Region Aquifer Background	Private
4	1 April Co-creation Workshop SOCAMEX Presentation	Private
5	AQP Well walkthrough	Private
6	Key propositions to develop and strengthen the governance of a circular water economy	Public
7	Propuestas para desarrollar y fortalecer una gobernanza de la economía circular del agua	Public
8	De un modelo lineal del agua a uno circular	Public
9	Problemas y oportunidades en la EDAR de Almendralejo	Public
10	Planta de tratamiento en Almendralejo y nuevos circuitos del agua	Public
11	Usos del agua regenerada en Almendralejo	Public
12	Objetivos del demosite de Almendralejo	Public
13	Galeb Presentation WP3 Co-Creation Workshop	Private
14	Project Ô Environmental Life Cycle Assessment	Public
15	Project Ô Life Cycle Costing	Public
16	Project Ô Social Life Cycle Assessment	Public
17	Project Ô ADV.ERT Module - Social Acceptance Survey	Private
18	Project Ô ADV.ERT Module - Social Acceptance Survey (Italian version)	Private

⁵⁷ <https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCi7PkIOSqQ9PMO7ay88Wifw/>

19	Project Ô ADV.ERT Module	Public
20	Project Ô ADV.ERT Module (Italian version)	Public
21	Project Ô ADV.ERT Module (Detailed version)	Public
22	Project Ô MOBILE3TECH Module - Social Acceptance Survey	Private
23	Project Ô MOBILE3TECH Module - Social Acceptance Survey (Spanish version)	Private
24	Project Ô MOBILE3TECH Module	Public
25	Project Ô Módulo MOBILE3TECH (Spanish version)	Public
26	Project Ô MOBILE3TECH Module (Detailed version)	Public
27	Project Ô PHOTO.CAT Unit - Social Acceptance Survey	Private
28	Project Ô PHOTO.CAT Unit	Public
29	Project Ô PHOTO.CAT Unit (Detailed version)	Public
30	Project Ô SALTECH Module - Social Acceptance Survey	Private
31	Project Ô SALTECH Module	Public
32	Project Ô SALTECH Module (Detailed version)	Public
33	Impact planning using logic models and theory of change with Mark Reed, Eric Jensen and Sarah Bowman	Public
34	How to make a difference in science policy with your research with Eric Jensen and Andrew George	Public

YouTube Key Performance Indicators

Content Impressions and Views

From January to November 2022, the videos got **11.6k impressions**, **1.8k views** and **2,748 minutes of watch time**. The increase in content views and impressions began in July 2022 with the release of the first series of technology videos.

Figure 42. YouTube content views (Jul - Nov 2022)

Figure 43. YouTube content impressions (Jul - Nov 2022)

According to YouTube analytics, the following 5 public videos had the best performance overall:

Table 46. YouTube videos with views and impressions (Jan - Nov 2022)

YouTube videos	Views Data
<p>Impact planning using logic models and theory of change with Mark Reed, Eric Jensen and Sarah Bowman</p>	<p>Views: 191</p> <p>Duration: 52:02 minutes</p> <p>Watch time: 2,508 minutes</p> <p>Average view duration: 0:13</p> <p>Impressions: 4,225</p> <p>Impressions click-through rate⁵⁸: 0%</p>
<p>Project Ô Overview</p>	<p>Views: 171</p> <p>Duration: 5:11 minutes</p> <p>Watch time: 294 minutes</p> <p>Average view duration: 1:42</p> <p>Impressions: 111</p> <p>Impressions click-through rate: 12%</p>
<p>Project Ô ADV.ERT Module (Italian version)</p>	<p>Views: 97</p> <p>Duration: 3:04 minutes</p> <p>Watch time: 120 minutes</p> <p>Average view duration: 1:14</p> <p>Impressions: 922</p> <p>Impressions click-through rate: 0%</p>

⁵⁸ Views per impressions shown. This measures how often viewers watched a video after seeing an impression.

<p>Project Ô Social Life Cycle Assessment</p>	<p>Views: 59 Duration: 2:38 minutes Watch time: 72 minutes Average view duration: 1:12 Impressions: 517 Impressions click-through rate: 7%</p>
<p>Project Ô ADV.ERT Module</p>	<p>Views: 46 Duration: 2:41 minutes Watch time: 48 minutes Average view duration: 1:01 Impressions: 182 Impressions click-through rate: 6%</p>

Traffic source

The traffic source indicates where visitors to the videos and YouTube channel come from. 60.4% of the views came from the Project Ô website and social media channels that embedded the videos or linked to them on YouTube. Other important sources were direct URL entries and bookmarks (22.8%), the channel Browse features (5.9%) and suggestions appearing alongside or after other videos (3.8%).

Demosite signage report

Working towards a project legacy, signage was designed and installed at each demosite. A total of 5 signs (size A0) were designed: one for the project and one for each demosite. It was envisioned that these would promote the work at individual demosites and give an overview of Project Ô, including goals, the technology modules, and the other demosites.

A first draft of each signage was produced using the updated content of the website and brochures. These drafts were sent to each of the demosites for review and approval in February 2022. During March 2022, a series of meetings were held with colleagues from SOCAMEX and Acquedotto Pugliese to clarify and refine some of the infographics. By the end of the month, all signages were approved and the printed version of the files were sent to the partners.

Figure 44. Signage installed at the Croatian and Spanish demosites

Figure 45. Project Ô general signage

Implementing practical tools for

WATER SUSTAINABILITY

Project Ô shows how **local, targeted** water treatment technologies can help **improve global water management** allowing everyone **to benefit from this shared resource**

Project Ô enables water management and treatment technologies

The combination of innovative treatment technologies with two digital platforms will improve water management for communities in Europe and beyond.

- » Increasing the opportunity to reuse water
- » Improving the quality of water returned to the natural environment
- » Using less operating energy when treating water

THIS AREA IS PART OF A CIRCULAR WATER ECONOMY

Along with three other areas, it has been supported by Project Ô to benefit from the first installations of innovative water management technologies.

The Puglia region, Italy with Acquedotto Pugliese

Some freshwater sources can no longer be used. This can be due to contamination and the water source being too far from existing water treatment plants for processing.

Project Ô has developed ADVVERT, a technology that can treat contaminated water. It has low investment and operational costs, and a low environmental impact. It operates independently of a water treatment plant and can be used directly at the water site.

Eilat, Israel at The National Center for Mariculture

47% of global fish supplies come from fish farming. Current land-based mariculture water treatment systems cannot remove nitrates and other pollutants, which can then build up in the tanks.

Project Ô has developed SALTECH technology, a cost-effective nitrate removal process. It treats used land-based mariculture water allowing for an almost 100% closed loop of water use. It even provides commercial possibilities through water and nutrient reuse.

Almendralejo, Spain with SOCAMEX

Industrial wastewater may contain toxic pollutants with the potential to damage wastewater treatment plant systems. This means that toxic pollutants could end up untreated in the environment.

Project Ô has developed MOBILE3TECH, a technology to remove complex pollutants from wastewater. It ensures compliance with new water regulations, helps protect wastewater treatment plants and allows for a more effective reuse of water.

Omiš, Croatia with Galeb d.d.

Textile production is a water-intensive industry. Water is used to clean raw materials and as part of the dyeing process. Production also relies on many different substances, which can end up in used water streams and are difficult to treat.

Project Ô has developed PHOTO.CAT, a technology to remove dyes from used water and increase the percentage of water available for reuse. This module also partially removes dissolved salt used in the dyeing process for further reuse.

Partners

- » Aalborg University » Acquedotto Pugliese » CNRS » Eilat Municipality » EKSÖ » Ente Nazionale Italiano de Unificazione » Galeb d.d. » Heim.ART - Kulturverein » Hochschule Rhine-Waal » Institute for Methods Innovation » IRIS » Israel Oceanographic and Limnological Research » Kalundborg Symbiosis » National Center for Mariculture » Particula Group
- » Politecnico di Milano » Regione Puglia » SOCAMEX » Technion - Israel Institute of Technology » Universidade de Aveiro » Università di Torino » Universitat Politècnica de València

Find out more!

Project Ô Website
www.ou-project.eu

Figure 46. Demosite signage - Croatia

Supporting the textile industry to allow water and resources to be reused

Background

Omiš is a small Croatian town with a thriving tourist industry. Galeb d.d. are an established textile company who is building a new factory with its own water treatment plant.

One aim of the new water treatment plant is to allow Galeb d.d. to treat and reuse their own used water. This would reduce the need for fresh input water and allow recovery of dyeing salts for reuse, as well as being more cost-effective and a sustainable use of resources.

Circular Water Economy

Using Project Ô technologies, water use in textile production can apply a circular economy approach. By participating in Project Ô, the potential benefits to this region include:

- » Safeguarding the local environment through specialised water treatments and improving resource management helping to maintain the Natura 2000 designation.
- » Increasing local water reuse and creating huge savings in textile production by maximising resource use without disrupting the local water system.
- » Closing the loop, requires new infrastructure and land uses which can lead to an increase in local jobs in the environmental sector.
- » Increasing health and safety measures through strict regulations, quality standards and management plans to comply with national and EU environmental objectives.
- » Using a sustainable approach to water use and reuse increases resilience to changes in the climate and economy.

Technology

PHOTO.CAT technology is a modular unit that can treat chemicals used in textile production. The combination with nanofiltration technology allows dye baths to be supplied with reused water that still contains the salts and temperature needed for dyeing.

The benefits of PHOTO.CAT technology include:

- » A modular design allowing units to be configured to suit operating needs.
- » Separate used water streams can be treated independently and simultaneously.
- » It can operate continuously, driven by solar power with a low-power LED back-up.
- » It can be used off the grid or in remote locations.
- » The treated water is suitable for cost-effective reuse, while optimising use of resources such as salts and heat energy.

Project Ô has also developed a Circular Economy Platform (CEP) to allow key players involved in water treatment activities to interact by sharing requests, offers, treatment technologies and logistics.

- » A digital marketplace for the supply and demand of water and by-product resources
- » Water streams sorted as inputs or outputs, with specific chemical compositions.
- » A platform for users to reuse water as part of a circular water economy.
- » Space for communities to support local water management.

Find out more! [Project Ô Website www.eu-project-o.eu](http://www.eu-project-o.eu)

Figure 47. Demosite signage - Israel

Eilat, Israel at The National Center for Mariculture

Improving land-based mariculture to meet growing demand and comply with regulations

Background

The National Center for Mariculture promote the development of mariculture as a unique branch of aquaculture. Land-based mariculture relies on the recirculation of water to remove waste.

The water is filtered and treated to remove substances like ammonia which is converted to less toxic nitrates but current technology cannot remove nitrates and other pollutants, which can then build up in the tank. Environmental regulations now require nitrates to be removed.

Circular Water Economy

Using Project O technologies, water use land-based mariculture can apply a circular economy approach, allowing almost 100% closed loop of water reuse.

- By participating in Project O, the potential benefits to this region include:
- » **Improving the local environment** through a decrease in seawater extraction and decrease of used water discharged into the Red Sea.
 - » **More efficient removal** of nitrogen, phosphate and total suspended solids meeting tighter environmental regulations.
 - » **Commercial opportunities** are possible by selling algae already grown for the denitrification treatment and by selling nutrients extracted during desalination.
 - » Allowing land-based mariculture to **move away from coastal areas** relieving pressure on the land, bringing production closer to consumers and reducing the environmental footprint related to food transport.
 - » Closing the loop, requires new infrastructure and land uses which can lead to an **increase in local jobs in the environmental sector**.
 - » **Water quality ensured** through strict regulations, quality standards, management plans, permits and water policy instruments.

Technology

SALTECH technology removes nitrates and other pollutants and helps recover nutrients from land-based mariculture systems. It has been designed to meet environmental regulations for good mariculture practise.

- The benefits of SALTECH technology include:
- » Reducing costs incurred through pumping new input water as well as taxes from discharging wastewater.
 - » A more stable water temperature, which can lead to an improved fish growth rate.
 - » Efficient management of fish disease control, which can improve yield and quality.

Project O has also developed a Circular Economy Platform (CEP) to allow key players involved in water treatment activities to interact by sharing requests, offers, treatment technologies and logistics.

- » A digital marketplace for the supply and demand of water and by-product resources
- » Water streams sorted as inputs or outputs, with specific chemical compositions.
- » A platform for users to reuse water as part of a circular water economy.
- » Space for communities to support local water management.

Find out more!

Project O Website
www.aquaproject.eu

Facebook
[@aquaprojecteu](https://www.facebook.com/aquaprojecteu)

Twitter
[@EU7ProjectO](https://twitter.com/EU7ProjectO)

LinkedIn
[/in/aquaproject-o](https://www.linkedin.com/company/aquaproject-o)

Contact
info@aquaproject.eu

FUNDING
This project has received from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 776202

Figure 48. Demosite signage - Italy

Treating previously inaccessible water sources that have been contaminated by certain microorganisms and seawater

Background

The limestone landscape of the Puglia region has formed several natural aquifers. These underground water sources supply more than 200 wells across this coastal region.

These wells were a valuable source of freshwater. After use and treatment, water taken from the wells was discharged into the sea. This drained the wells faster than they could naturally refill from the aquifers.

The wells were abandoned as a cost-effective, local source of water as exploitation activities have resulted in the aquifers steadily containing more salt water.

Circular Water Economy

Using Project Ô technologies, water use in the Puglia Region can apply a circular economy approach. By participating in Project Ô, the potential benefits to this region include:

- » Maximising local water reuse to strengthen resilience in the region and decrease the need for external water imports.
- » Recharged aquifers ensure their viability for future use and protects a long-term local source of water.
- » New local water reuse will relieve pressure on the aqueduct and can lead to a reduction of reliance on water from external sources.
- » Closing the loop requires new infrastructure and use of technologies which can lead to an increase in local jobs in the environmental sector.
- » Returning treated water to its source supports the local environment and stops water being discharged into the Adriatic Sea.

Reuse and water efficiency are key priorities for the Puglia region.

Technology

ADV.ERT is an advanced, tertiary treatment, mobile plant. It has been designed to treat contaminated freshwater out of the reach of existing water treatment plants.

The features of ADV.ERT include:

- » Relatively small dimensions.
- » Mobile and operates independently of a water treatment plant, so it can be used directly at the water source.
- » Low electrical energy consumption, which reduces costs and increases sustainability.
- » Low investment and operational costs with a low environmental impact.
- » Can be used to treat any water source with a variable level of contamination.

Project Ô has also developed a Decision Analytic Platform (DAP) to aid water resource management and help decision-makers compare the effect of making particular decisions.

- » Analyses difficult-to-measure factors and objectives.
- » Includes holistic factors like technology costs and local conditions.
- » Considers real-world factors, like regulations and financial mechanisms.
- » Generates interactive visualisations to aid data comparisons.
- » Shows the impacts of decisions on current and future water supply.

Find out more! | Project Ô Website: www.eu-project.eu | QR Code | Facebook: @rupugliaeu | Twitter: @EUProject10 | LinkedIn: /ru-project-0 | Contact: info@eu-project.eu | FUNDING: This project has received from the European Union Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation programme under grant agreement No 776020

Figure 49. Demosite signage - Spain

Almendralejo, Spain with SOCAMEX

Supporting the detection and processing of complex pollutants,
the protection of water treatment plants and water reuse

Background

Almendralejo is a small Spanish city about 160 kilometres north of Seville. It has a population of around 35,000 and is home to almost thirty businesses processing olives for consumption as both fruit and oil.

The wastewater from both households and industry is sent for treatment to the nearby wastewater treatment plant in Almendralejo. If a spill occurs, toxic wastewater could damage the biological treatment system of the treatment plant. This means that toxic pollutants could end up untreated in the environment.

Circular Water Economy

Using Project Ô technologies, water use can apply a circular economy approach. By participating in Project Ô, the potential benefits to this region include:

- » Maximising local water reuse to strengthen resilience against changes in the climate and economy and increase the efficiency of water management.
- » Closing the loop requires new infrastructure and use of technologies which can lead to an increase in local jobs in the environmental sector.
- » Water management is supported by an increase in health and safety measures through strict regulations, quality standards, management plans, policies and permits for water reuse, storage and transportation.
- » Improving the local environment through decreases in water taken from and discharged into the local river basin.
- » Protecting the local area and wastewater treatment plant by treating toxic water and accidental spills.

Technology

MOBILE3TECH technology treats complex pollutants that may damage water treatment plants.

MOBILE3TECH technology design includes:

- » An advanced control unit to test wastewater quality and determine if pre-treatment is required according to the toxicity.
- » A cost-effective pre-treatment unit that increases the biodegradability and decreases the toxicity of wastewater before conventional treatment at a water treatment plant.
- » The regeneration of saturated activated carbon for reuse reducing the consumption of new activated carbon.
- » Low investment and operational costs.
- » Compatibility with existing facilities, minimising works to incorporate the new system.
- » The retention of emerging pollutants for safe water reuse.

Project Ô has also developed a Decision Analytic Platform (DAP) to aid water resource management and help decision-makers compare the effect of making particular decisions.

Find out more! [Project Ô Website](http://www.eu-project-0.eu) www.eu-project-0.eu

 Contact info@eu-project-0.eu

 FUNDING This project has received from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 776020

Newsletters report

As part of the internal and external project communication strategies, the IMI team compiled 8 newsletters during RP3 (4 internal newsletters for project partners and 4 external newsletters for a more general audience with little to no knowledge of the project). The newsletters were used to share project information and updates with the aim to cultivate continuous, bi-directional knowledge-transfer between the project and its different stakeholders.

A content plan for newsletters was developed by IMI and drafts were written for release to external stakeholder audiences in coordination with the calendar of planned media releases during RP3. These newsletters focused on project information, achievements, updates and shared the progress made at each demosite, and were disseminated regularly to all stakeholders who signed up for project updates.

Each issue contained information about an overarching aspect of the project (such as the need for a circular water economy and how Project Ô contributes to the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals), a focus on a demosite (Italy, Israel, Spain and Croatia) and the technologies implemented (ADV.ERT, SALTECH, MOBILE3TECH and PHOTO.CAT), latest news (including tours of demosites, project partners at conferences), upcoming events (such as the International School on Water Reuse, public engagement events, and stakeholder engagement events) useful visual content and other communication materials (access to project brochures, videos etc). Project partners were regularly invited to share their latest updates with the team for inclusion in the newsletters.

Furthermore, as part of ICT4Water, a hub for EU-funded research and innovation projects on ICT applied to water management, IMI drafted a general overview of the project which was featured in ICT4Water Quarterly Newsletter (June 2022)⁵⁹.

⁵⁹ ICT4Water newsletter (June 2022 issue) can be read here: <https://preview.mailerlite.com/e6l8i5t2p4/1988455181120967975/l4k9/>

Figure 50. External newsletter - Spring 2022 issue⁶⁰

Spring 2022 Issue

Welcome to the Project Ô newsletter!

Project Ô shows how local, targeted water treatment technologies can help improve global water management.

Did you know that many modern water systems are based on an unsustainable linear economy model?

This approach incorrectly assumes we have access to endless freshwater supplies and natural resources. Linear economies are damaging our planet, wasting limited resources and causing pollution. We must shift to a circular economy approach to build a more sustainable present and future.

DEVELOPING PRACTICAL TOOLS FOR A CIRCULAR WATER ECONOMY

Project Ô has developed water treatment technologies to support the transition to a circular water economy. These technologies work in harmony with current systems and improve technical and economic success. Adopting a circular economy helps make our systems more resilient to environmental and economic change, ultimately working to provide a reliable water supply for current and future generations.

PROTECTING THE WASTEWATER TREATMENT PLANT IN ALMENDRALEJO, SPAIN

Project Ô has developed circular water technologies at four installation sites in Croatia, Israel, Italy, and Spain. In this issue, we focus on the installation site in Almendralejo in Spain.

Almendralejo, near Seville in Spain, is home to businesses processing olives for use as both fruit and oil. Wastewater from these businesses and local homes is treated at a nearby wastewater treatment plant.

During the olive production season, the toxicity levels of the wastewater rise and can damage the biological treatment system, which removes pollutants in wastewater. This means that wastewater could go into local rivers untreated.

Project Ô has developed a [water treatment module](#) to detect and remove pollutants from businesses and households' wastewater that could damage the water treatment plant in Almendralejo. This treatment module assesses the toxicity levels of incoming wastewater samples to determine if it is safe to treat or if extra treatment is needed first. If needed, the module will ensure wastewater toxicity is reduced before it enters the normal process at the treatment plant.

While treated water is usually discharged into the local river at the end of the process, this module allows to reuse it by treating it further and removing other pollutants like pharmaceuticals, herbicides and disinfectants, making it clean and safe to sustain crops and clean municipal areas, like streets.

To further support their transition to a circular water economy, they are utilising Project Ô's web-

LATEST UPDATES FROM PROJECT Ô

Co-creation workshop in Spain

The first live online co-creation workshop was held in April 2022 with relevant stakeholders and agencies in [Almendralejo, Spain](#), one of the Project Ô demosites. Read more about the workshop [here](#).

Co-creation workshop in Italy

The second live online co-creation workshop was held in May 2022 with relevant stakeholders and agencies in the [Puglia region in Italy](#), one of the Project Ô demosites. Read more about the workshop [here](#).

Dissemination activities underway

On Friday 13 May 2022, Project Ô partner, [Università degli Studi di Torino](#) showed students a prototype of the Project Ô technology used at the [demosite in Croatia](#). Read more about it [here](#).

Demosite posters installed

As part of the communication efforts, several posters were produced and installed at the demosites. You can read and download the materials, reports and publications developed throughout the project [here](#).

You can read more about Project Ô on our website and social media channels

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 The project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 776816

⁶⁰ <https://mailer.methods4change.org/w/7iLuNya7630bcjixbCaeDV5A>

Figure 51. External newsletter - Summer 2022 issue⁶¹

Summer 2022 Issue

RESTORING SOURCES OF FRESHWATER IN THE PUGLIA REGION

Welcome to the Project O newsletter!

Project O shows how local, targeted water treatment technologies can help improve global water management, allowing current and future generations to benefit from this shared resource.

Project O is working to promote the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals

In 2015, seventeen **Sustainable Development Goals** (SDGs) were announced by the United Nations (UN), and 193 countries across the world pledged to act. The SDGs provide a shared blueprint for peace and prosperity for people and the planet, now and into the future. Eliminating poverty and inequality, preventing biodiversity loss and providing all with clean water are some of the issues being tackled. These goals are designed to align global actions to benefit us all.

Project O is contributing to three Sustainable Development Goals:

6 CLEAN WATER AND SANITATION

12 RESPONSIBLE CONSUMPTION AND PRODUCTION

13 CLIMATE ACTION

UN SDGs Project O supports

The UN forecast that by 2030, the world could face a deficit in water supply. Improving water management is a vital step towards creating a more reliable water supply. Project O develops water management and treatment technologies. They work in harmony with current systems and improve technical and economic success. The combination of innovative treatment technologies with two digital platforms will improve water management for communities in Europe and beyond.

Project O has developed circular water technologies at four installation sites in Croatia, Israel, Italy, and Spain. In this issue, we focus on the installation site in the Puglia region in southern Italy.

Some freshwater sources can no longer be used. This can be due to contamination and the water source being too great a distance from existing water treatment plants for processing.

Overexploited and now abandoned wells in the Puglia region of Italy present this challenge. They have been contaminated with seawater and certain microorganisms, but are too remote to be treated by existing water treatment plants.

Project O has developed a **water filtration technology module** to treat contaminated water. It operates independently of a water treatment plant and can be used directly at the water source, aiding the sustainable recovery of an untapped water resource.

Project O technologies installed at the demosite in Italy

Watch this video about the water treatment module installed at the demosite in Italy

ADV.ERT Module

Read more about Project O's activities in Italy [here](#).

LATEST UPDATES FROM PROJECT O

From waste to resources in farming

On June 15 and 16 2022, the event entitled "From waste to resources in the primary sector" was held in collaboration with **CIRCULAR BIOCARBON**. Read more about the two-day workshop [here](#).

International School on Water Reuse 2022

We are thrilled to share our learnings and resources in this upcoming **International School on Water Reuse**. See further details and register your place [here](#).

International School on Water Reuse (in person: Turin, Italy)

September 2022

⁶¹ <https://mailer.methods4change.org/w/RRS66wh81VfBGJkqf0jXg>

Figure 52. External newsletter - Autumn 2022 issue⁶²

Autumn 2022 Issue

Welcome to the Project Ô newsletter!

Project Ô shows how local, targeted water treatment technologies can help improve global water management, allowing current and future generations to benefit from this shared resource.

Project Ô addresses the crucial challenge of water sustainability

Water sustainability is increasingly important with parts of Europe facing record heat waves and droughts this year. Water shortages disrupt the ability of many local regions to manage water use and sustain water supplies.

Project Ô is funded by the European Commission in 2018 to demonstrate how different water treatment technologies can improve regional capacity for sustaining crucial water supplies.

In this article, we share how research within Project Ô has supported the installation of innovative water treatment technologies that lower costs, reduce energy and give local regions access to alternative water sources.

As an EU-funded project, research is often needed to **show whether new technologies are beneficial for stakeholders within a local community**. This research involves numerous assessments of the technologies, such as being environmentally friendly, socially just and financially affordable. Each water treatment technology within Project Ô received these assessments.

The **environmental assessment** includes an impact evaluation based on a set of indicators of environmental outcomes such as global warming. Learn more about this analysis in [this video](#).

Environmental Life Cycle Assessment

The **social assessment** of water treatment technologies focused on relevant social factors, such as feedback from community stakeholders about their concerns. Take a look at [the video](#) explaining how the social assessment is being conducted in the project.

DEMONSTRATING THE VALUE OF WATER TREATMENT TECHNOLOGY

Project Ô demonstrates how water treatment technologies can improve regional capacity for sustaining crucial water supplies, while lowering costs, reducing energy demands and giving local regions access to alternative water sources.

IMPROVING LAND-BASED FISH FARMING IN ISRAEL

Project Ô has developed circular water technologies at four installation sites in Croatia, Israel, Italy, and Spain.

As the Earth's population expands, access to fresh, healthy, sustainable food is an ever greater challenge. Fish farming systems are the fastest growing food production sector in the world, providing 47% of global fish supplies.

However, fish farms produce 250 cubic meters of wastewater per hour (the equivalent of 2.5 olympic swimming pools of wastewater per day), causing significant negative environmental impacts. The project is demonstrating the potential for more advanced circular water management to reuse water from these farms.

Project Ô has developed **water treatment technology** called SALTECH as a cost-effective water treatment for land-based fish farming. Find out more about how this technology works in [this video](#) available on YouTube.

UPCOMING EVENTS

 International School on Water Reuse 2022
 International School on Water Reuse (in person: Turin, Italy)
 September 2022

Lessons learned from the project will feature in the upcoming International School on Water Reuse. See further details and register [here](#).

Upcoming public engagement events

Live online co-creation workshops will be held with communities in Puglia (Italy), Omis (Croatia) and Eilat (Israel) in September and October. The agenda will include an overview of both the project and group discussions to unearth perspectives on water sustainability concerns and hopes.

Public Engagement Events
September-October

You can read more about Project Ô on our website and social media channels

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 This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 776816

⁶² <https://mailer.methods4change.org/w/de0HRvs9IEakjqMMbQC0EQ>

Figure 53. External newsletter - Winter 2022 issue

Winter 2022 Issue

Welcome to the Project Ô newsletter!

Project Ô shows how local, targeted water treatment technologies can help improve global water management, allowing current and future generations to benefit from this shared resource.

Outcomes and outlook | A final message from Project Ô

After four years of planning, developing and implementing practical tools for a circular water economy, Project Ô is nearing completion.

This final newsletter provides a glimpse of what Project Ô has done to improve water management for communities in Europe and beyond. The water treatment technologies have been tested in a diverse range of settings to make sure that they work in harmony with current systems and improve technical and economic success.

While the project formally closes on 30 November 2022, the Project Ô website will be maintained as a source of information, and as a place for those interested in water sustainability to learn about significant collaborative efforts to bring about water sustainability innovations.

The whole team thanks you sincerely for being part of the Project Ô journey.

DEMONSTRATING THE VALUE OF WATER TREATMENT TECHNOLOGY

Project Ô demonstrates how water treatment technologies can improve regional capacity for sustaining crucial water supplies, while lowering costs, reducing energy demands and giving local regions access to alternative water sources.

SUPPORTING THE TEXTILE INDUSTRY TO ALLOW WATER AND RESOURCES TO BE REUSE

ADV.ERT Module

The ADV.ERT module treats contaminated freshwater, including that from groundwater sources in Italy's Puglia region.

MOBILE3TECH Module

The MOBILE3TECH module was developed to treat the toxic used water produced by industry in Almdralejo in Spain.

SALTECH Module

The SALTECH module removes nitrates from land-based mariculture systems in Eilat, Israel.

PHOTO.CAT Unit

The PHOTO.CAT unit was developed to treat water used in textile production in Omiš, Croatia.

LATEST UPDATES FROM PROJECT Ô

Co-creation events about water sustainability concerns and hopes

ITALY

CROATIA

ISRAEL

Project Ô has developed circular water technologies at four installation sites in Croatia, Israel, Italy, and Spain.

We need water to survive. But every day, finite freshwater resources are used and discarded through unsustainable industrial production. It is especially important to reduce the impact of water-intensive industries, such as clothing.

For example, on average, it takes 2,700 liters of water to make a simple cotton t-shirt. That's enough water for one person to drink for 900 days. Also, the water used for clothing production is contaminated with chemicals that harm the natural environment, if left untreated.

A clothing factory in [Croatia](#) is working to increase the reuse of finite water resources. This factory is building its own water treatment plant using Project Ô technologies to clean water after it's been used to make material for clothing, enabling its sustainable reuse.

[PHOTO.CAT](#) is a modular unit that removes harmful chemicals and organic pollutants and recovers salts from the water. The treatment process is designed to automatically mix different streams of treated water to ensure the right salt levels and temperatures for making clothing materials. These targeted treatments enable the factory's immediate reuse of the water, and also boost energy efficiency because the treated water is already optimised for clothing production.

To further support their transition to a circular water economy, they are utilising Project Ô's [web-based platform](#) designed to enable local trade of water and by-products between different water users involved in water treatment activities.

By using Project Ô water treatment technologies like PHOTO.CAT, the factory can increase its sustainability and efficiency because more water can be reused while requiring less energy. This reduces demands on finite freshwater resources and power supplies.

Project Ô site visits conducted in Eilat, Israel

[Eilat Municipality](#) and [Technion - Israel Institute of Technology](#) - have been conducting tours of the Project Ô demo site to present the project and the technology solutions implemented at the site to stakeholders in the community. The visits were focused on students from around the city of Eilat working on solving water problems in the Red Sea.

International School on Water Reuse 2022 hosted in Italy

The first International School on Water Reuse took place from 19 to 21 September 2022 at the Chemistry Department of the [Torino University](#) in Italy in collaboration with the [Butterfly Area](#). The School was organised as part of Project Ô, and was hosted for those interested in water sustainability. Read more about this event on [Project Ô's website latest section](#).

Project Ô technologies lead to spin-out for Aalborg University

Xianzhong Ma, a postdoctoral student at [Aalborg University](#), received a grant to mature "Fibrane", a membrane distillation technology based on that developed by Professor Vittorio Boffa and used in some of Project Ô's water treatment modules. Read more about this project on [Project Ô's website latest section](#).

You can read more about Project Ô on our website and social media channels

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This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 776816

Newsletter content was written in plain and accessible language to benefit non-expert communities and stakeholder groups, with an extensive internal review process for quality assurance. Partners were consulted to request inputs. Where possible, additional video and visual content was shared to supplement written materials. The newsletter, as shown in the visual examples above, was professionally designed by the IMI team and disseminated using Sendy, an email newsletter application.

As of November 2022, 28 readers subscribed to the newsletter, and online versions were archived on the Library section of the website. During the reporting period, there were four campaigns (May 2022, July 2022, September 2022 and November 2022).

Table 47. Project Ô external newsletters performance (Jan - Nov 2022)

Issue	Unique opens	Unique clicks
Project Ô Newsletter Spring 2022	43.48%	8.7%
Project Ô Newsletter Summer 2022	40.74%	7.41%
Project Ô Newsletter Autumn 2022	37.04%	3.7%
Project Ô Newsletter Winter 2022	Not yet available	Not yet available

By the time this deliverable was written, the final Project Ô newsletter was being finalised and scheduled to be sent on 30 November 2022. The final issue provided updates on a range of final activities and explained how the website will be maintained as a resource for those interested in learning more about water sustainability.

Other partners' contributions

As part of WP8 communications efforts, partners from Heim.Art planned to facilitate artistic communal activities as site-specific outreach actions in Project Ô. Due to unforeseen circumstances, these activities did not take place. Instead, the Heim.Art team traveled to each demosite to take professional photographs and interview key stakeholders to produce a series of videos. Lisa Sayles, from the IMI team, traveled to Almendralejo, Spain and Omiš, Croatia to facilitate Heim.Art's contributions.

By November 2022, there were the outputs that were received by the IMI team.

Table 48. Heim.Art's media contributions (T8.5 - Media list)

Media asset	Description	Status
Photo + Video	Photos and videos of water treatment modules in action at the demosite	Delivered
Photo	Photo of ADV.ERT installed at the demo site as a close crop	Delivered
Photo	Photo of ADV.ERT installed at the demo site as a wide shot	Delivered
Photo	Photo of land-based mariculture tanks, wider shots showing all tanks in general	Delivered
Photo	Photo of SALTECH installed at the demo site as a close crop	Delivered
Photo	Photo of SALTECH installed at the demo site as a wide shot	Delivered
Photo	Photo of MOBILE3TECH installed at the demo site as a close crop	Delivered
Photo	Photo of MOBILE3TECH installed at the demo site as a wide shot	Delivered
Photo	Photo of PHOTO.CAT installed at the demo site as a close crop	Delivered
Photo	Photo of PHOTO.CAT installed at the demo site as a wide shot	Delivered
Photo	Photos of people in the consortium actively working on Project Ô, at the	Delivered

	demo sites, in office spaces and workshops.	
Photo	Photos and videos of someone using DAP at the demosites (or other local partner location, e.g. regional government)	Not delivered
Photo	Photos and videos of someone using CEP at the demosites (or other local partner location, e.g. regional government)	Not delivered
Photo	High-quality photographs (headshots) of every interviewee representing each demo site (one each as a minimum) and providing testimonial videos to be used as part of the testimonials packages to promote the project.	Croatia: Not delivered Israel: Not delivered Italy: Not delivered Spain: Not delivered
Video	Video testimonials (with transcript) from key representatives for each demosite (one each as a minimum) discussing the benefits of engaging in Project Ô <u>for the local area</u> (of that demo site).	Croatia: Delivered without transcripts Israel: Delivered without transcript/translation (video in Hebrew) Italy: Not delivered Spain: Not delivered
Video	Video testimonials (with transcript) from key representatives for each demosite discussing the benefits of using Project Ô technologies <u>in general</u> .	Croatia: Delivered without transcripts Israel: Delivered without transcript/translation (video in Hebrew) Italy: Not delivered Spain: Not delivered
Video	Videos of positive quotes from stakeholder/s about use of ADV.ERT <u>in general</u> . Minimum of 3 quotes per stakeholder; minimum of 3 different stakeholders.	Croatia: Not delivered Israel: Not delivered Italy: Not delivered Spain: Not delivered
Video	Videos of positive quote/s from stakeholder/s about use of SALTECH <u>in general</u> . Minimum of 3 quotes per stakeholder; minimum of 3 different stakeholders.	Croatia: Not delivered Israel: Not delivered Italy: Not delivered Spain: Not delivered
Video	Videos of positive quote/s from	Croatia: Not delivered

	stakeholder/s about use of MOBILE3TECH <u>in general</u> . Minimum of 3 quotes per stakeholder; minimum of 3 different stakeholders.	Israel: Not delivered Italy: Not delivered Spain: Not delivered
Video	Videos of positive quotes from stakeholder/s about use of PHOTO.CAT <u>in general</u> . Minimum of 3 quotes per stakeholder; minimum of 3 different stakeholders.	Croatia: Not delivered Israel: Not delivered Italy: Not delivered Spain: Not delivered
Video	Videos of positive quotes from stakeholder/s about use of DAP <u>in general</u> . Minimum of 3 quotes per stakeholder; minimum of 3 different stakeholders.	Croatia: Not delivered Israel: Not delivered Italy: Not delivered Spain: Not delivered
Video	Videos of positive quote/s from stakeholder/s about use of CEP <u>in general</u> . Minimum of 3 quotes per stakeholder; minimum of 3 different stakeholders.	Croatia: Not delivered Israel: Not delivered Italy: Not delivered Spain: Not delivered

Table 49. Heim.Art's media contributions (T8.7 - Event contribution)

Media asset	Description	Status
Video	Assist demo sites to produce pre-recorded virtual walk-through tours of the technologies at their demosite for use in the co-creation events.	Not delivered
Video	Produce high-quality documentary style videos for each event (approx. 5 minutes of well-edited film each).	Not delivered

Other stakeholder engagement activities

Knowledge transfer

As part of a continuous bi-directional knowledge-transfer between the project and its stakeholders, including other relevant EU-funded projects and activities, IMI Director of Research Dr Eric A. Jensen represented Project Ô at EU sister project NextGen's final event in Athens, Greece, in October 2022.

He attended along with representatives from sister project HYDROUSA and NextGen partners in ULTIMATE, B-WaterSmart, and WaterMining. As part of the agenda, Work Package leaders from NextGen provided lessons learnt during the project, potential synergies regarding circular water technologies and future opportunities. Dr Jensen's presence at the event cemented collaboration between the different projects and will allow for future relationships between researchers and institutions working on European Commission funded projects.

Figure 54. NextGen's final event

Image credit: Dr Eric Jensen | Institute for Methods Innovation

Figure 55. NextGen's final event

Image credit: Dr Eric Jensen | Institute for Methods Innovation

Project news articles

As part of the external project communication strategies, the IMI team wrote and published 13 news articles on the website.

Table 50. News articles published on the website

Title	Description	Screenshot
Co-creation workshop in Almendralejo, Spain ⁶³	Overview of the WP3 co-creation workshop in Spain	
Co-creation workshop in the Puglia region, Italy ⁶⁴	Overview of the WP3 co-creation workshop in Italy	

⁶³ <https://www.eu-project-o.eu/spain-workshop/>

⁶⁴ <https://www.eu-project-o.eu/co-creation-workshop-in-the-puglia-region-italy/>

<p>Project Ô dissemination activities underway⁶⁵</p>	<p>Description of Torino University's dissemination efforts</p>	<p>The screenshot shows a website with a header image of people in white lab coats. Below the header, there are two smaller images: one showing a group of people in a lab setting, and another showing a digital display with the Project Ô logo. The text on the page is partially legible, mentioning 'Project Ô dissemination activities underway' and '17 May 2022'.</p>
<p>Co-creation workshop in Omiš, Croatia⁶⁶</p>	<p>Overview of the WP3 co-creation workshop in Croatia</p>	<p>The screenshot shows a website with a header image of a presentation slide titled 'Co-creation workshop in Omiš, Croatia'. Below the header, there is a video player showing a presentation slide with text and a logo. The text on the page is partially legible, mentioning 'Co-creation workshop in Omiš, Croatia' and '17 May 2022'.</p>

⁶⁵ <https://www.eu-project-o.eu/project-o-dissemination-activities-underway/>

⁶⁶ <https://www.eu-project-o.eu/co-creation-workshop-in-croatia/>

<p>Co-creation workshop in Eilat, Israel⁶⁷</p>	<p>Overview of the WP3 co-creation workshop in Israel</p>	
<p>Project Ô technologies installed at the demosite in Italy⁶⁸</p>	<p>Details about Project Ô's water filtration technologies installation at the Cozza Guardati well in Italy</p>	

⁶⁷ <https://www.eu-project-o.eu/co-creation-workshop-in-israel/>

⁶⁸ <https://www.eu-project-o.eu/project-o-technologies-installed-at-the-demosite-in-italy/>

<p>From waste to resources in the primary sector⁶⁹</p>	<p>Overview of the WP8 public engagement workshop in Spain</p>	<p>From waste to resources in the primary sector</p> <p>Contexto y objetivos</p>
<p>Co-creation event about water sustainability concerns and hopes in Italy⁷⁰</p>	<p>Overview of the WP8 public engagement workshop in Italy</p>	<p>Co-creation event about water sustainability concerns and hopes in Italy</p> <p>Introduzione del Project O Workshop pubblico di co-creazione</p>

⁶⁹ <https://www.eu-project-o.eu/from-waste-to-resources-in-the-primary-sector/>

⁷⁰ <https://www.eu-project-o.eu/water-sustainability-italy/>

<p>Proyecto Ô: Tecnologías para aprovechar hasta la última gota⁷¹</p>
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<p>International School on Water Reuse 2022 hosted in Italy⁷²</p>	<p>Overview of the first International School on Water Reuse that took place from 19 to 21 September 2022 at the Chemistry Department of the Torino University in Italy</p>	
<p>Co-creation workshop about water sustainability concerns and hopes in Croatia⁷³</p>	<p>Overview of the WP8 public engagement workshop in Croatia</p>	

⁷² <https://www.eu-project-o.eu/international-school-on-water-reuse-2022-hosted-in-italy/>

⁷³ <https://www.eu-project-o.eu/workshop-croatia/>

<p>Local community involvement in Israel⁷⁴</p>	<p>Overview of the demosite tours in Israel to present the project and SALTECH</p>	
<p>Co-creation workshop about water sustainability concerns and hopes in Israel⁷⁵</p>	<p>Overview of the WP8 public engagement workshop in Israel</p>	

⁷⁴ <https://www.eu-project-o.eu/local-community-involvement-in-israel/>

⁷⁵ <https://www.eu-project-o.eu/cocreation-israel/>

<p>Project Ô technologies lead to spin-out for Aalborg University⁷⁶</p>	<p>Interview with Xianzheng Ma, a postdoctoral student at Aalborg University, who received a grant to mature a membrane distillation technology based on the work of Professor Vittorio Boffa and used in some of Project Ô's water treatment modules</p>	<p>The screenshot shows a news article with a large header image of a laboratory setting. The title is 'Project Ô technologies lead to spin-out for Aalborg University'. Below the title is a sub-header with the date '20 October 2017' and the author 'By [unreadable]'. The main text of the article is visible but mostly illegible due to the low resolution. There are several small inset images of people, likely related to the project or the spin-out.</p>
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⁷⁶ <https://www.eu-project-o.eu/spin-out-aalborg-university/>

(T8.7) Event Management

The Project Ô Description of Action states that there should be ‘1 Event for each demo site’ aimed at engaging the local community stakeholders and other events aimed at ‘close’ and ‘extended’ networks. The full Project Ô programme of events organised by the Institute for Methods Innovation (IMI) engaged a total of 577 participants (about double the official target in the project DoA of 290 event participants).

Table 51. *Project Ô full event programme*

Event	Date
<i>Public engagement: Spain</i>	15-16 June 2022
<i>International professional event: Impact planning using logic models and theory of change</i>	31 August 2022
<i>Public engagement: Italy</i>	22 September 2022
<i>Public engagement: Croatia</i>	19 October 2022
<i>International professional event: How to make a difference in science policy with your research</i>	21 November 2022
<i>Public engagement: Israel</i>	22 November 2022

This report documents a series of public engagement events that were planned and delivered with a focus on engaging with local publics and non-expert communities. These events informed the direction and implementation of Project Ô innovations, enabling the project to listen to concerns and hopes about the future of circular water economy solutions. This report discusses co-creation events that took place between June and November 2022 in Spain, Italy, Croatia, and Israel as part of Project Ô's communication efforts (four local co-creation events)⁷⁷. Finally, the report presents details of the international events organised by the project, which were aimed at a broad international professional audience. This report also documents each public engagement event, including the delivery of information, the co-creation activity, context, information gathering, and results. A description of each event is provided as an independent case study. The concluding section discusses the implications of the key findings.

⁷⁷ The coordinator determined that four co-creation events would take place for the project.

Local Co-creation Public Engagement Events: Event Case Studies and Key Findings

In this section, each public engagement event is documented, including content delivery, co-creation activity, context, information gathering, and results. Public participation in these events highlighted pre-knowledge, attitudes, expectations, and concerns relevant to the project. Diverse groups of stakeholders provided insights on public views of water management, sustainability, and innovation, generally, and Project Ô technologies and approaches to promoting a circular water economy, specifically. The public engagement activities were designed to inform the work during the project, as well as foreground issues relevant to other water reuse initiatives within and outside the European Union.

The Institute for Methods Innovation (IMI) team engaged extensively with demosite partners and the project coordinator to try to involve other partners in the public engagement co-creation event organisation process. Ultimately, IMI took primary responsibility for the design, delivery, data collection, management and analysis of these co-creation events. In Spain, collaboration with a sister water sustainability project called CIRCULAR BIOCARBON was successfully implemented with a face-to-face 2-day public engagement event in Almendralejo.

For this event, practical adjustments were made to ensure that both projects gained what was needed. For the other three demosite locations, the public engagement events were fully organised by IMI, with demosite partners attending and encouraged to invite known contacts to attend with them. IMI took responsibility for all aspects of event organisation, administration and follow-up. Practical tasks involved in the event management process implemented by IMI included:

- Liaising with demosite partners and other stakeholders
- Preparing targeted outreach messaging for local members of the public to gain their participation
- Recruiting and liaising with workshop participants

- Determination of workshop approach and outline of the agenda Workshop scheduling and practical organisation
- Registration for workshops
- Ensuring GDPR and informed consent is obtained prior to any workshop data collection commencing
- Preparation of workshop materials (including invitations, worksheets, slide decks)
- Subtitling relevant project videos for workshop purposes
- Development, translation and adaptation of templates for local language and context
- Updating participants, answering queries and ongoing participant communications
- Managing the practicalities of the meeting, ensuring high-quality data collection and participant experience through skilled workshop facilitation
- Recording the session to allow for data collection, and quality assurance
- Transcription, translation and management of recorded data
- Documentation of participants' perspectives through note-taking and data analysis
- Ensure that participant preferences for anonymisation/confidentiality are fully implemented and all ethical guidelines are followed
- GDPR-compliant data management, storage, analysis and reporting
- Participant feedback survey preparation, delivery and analysis

The co-creation events have been structured to deliver the project's objectives relating to public involvement and stakeholder engagement. Engaging the local community close to each demosite was a key requirement in the project to improve social acceptance and enhance the project's impact. IMI spent a great deal of time working to engage other project partners (particularly demosites), with the aim of including them in this process. However, the skills to deliver this kind of work were not widely available, meaning that IMI had to take on considerably more responsibilities than was originally foreseen. The process began with development of an event management strategy and then a detailed plan. A series of templates and

guidelines were prepared to address all aspects of the co-creation events from first contacting potential participants until post-event follow-up communications.

The events were structured in a way that would ensure community participants with no previous information about the project or related topics could fully engage. This required an initial introduction to orient participants, including a tour of the demosite and its planned technology implementation, and establish a shared basis for subsequent discussions. This was followed by data collection exploring community members' views about the demosite implementation in their area and general themes relevant to the project. The final part of the co-creation event was aimed at drawing out creative contributions from community members to express their understanding of circular water economy innovations in their own words. Expert event facilitators from IMI were critical to the process, because we needed to balance the need to inform participants about relevant developments in their community on the one hand, with the need to gather data about their own perspectives on the other hand. Results from the co-creation events are presented in this report and have been communicated to project partners.

Co-creation public engagement event report: Spain

Synergies were identified between Project Ô and CIRCULAR BIOCARBON78, another EU-funded project (GA No. 101023280). On this basis, a series of collaborative meetings and documentation were organised by IMI with the CIRCULAR BIOCARBON coordination team and Project Ô demosite partner SOCAMEX. The public engagement co-creation event was collaboratively organised in the planning phase as a joint communication effort between the two projects.

The combined public engagement co-creation event, titled “From waste to resources in the primary sector,” was held over two days on the 15th and 16th of June 2022. The workshop involved stakeholders in activities and discussions about water sustainability and solid waste reuse specific to the primary sector, including project key concepts and innovations. To increase inclusiveness, the event was delivered in a hybrid modality, allowing for both online and in-person participation.

Figure 56. Invitation for the co-creation workshop in Almendralejo, Spain

Image credit: Daniela Martin | Institute for Methods Innovation

Local Water Sustainability Context

Almendralejo, a city in the province of Badajoz, Extremadura, Spain, is home to numerous primary sector industries, especially agriculture. Several factors indicate the merits of adopting circular water economy solutions in this region, such as large quantities of heavy waste, toxic substances that impede the breakdown of organic matter, and increasingly severe drought conditions in

⁷⁸ <https://circularbiocarbon.eu/>

the region. The two EU projects involved in the public engagement activity are focused on challenges associated with wastewater material reuse. Project Ô's MOBILE3TECH technology increases the sustainable reuse of wastewater by integrating an adaptive, customised system comprised of three technologies that assess toxicity, pre-treat as needed, and apply a final treatment to ensure that water is thoroughly and efficiently cleaned in order to once again help meet human needs. This technology reduces the demands on finite water.

Technologies from the CIRCULAR BIOCARBON project will support the improvement of agricultural yields in Almendralejo by turning organic solid waste into added-value products, such as fertilisers. These products will be tailored to the specific needs of the beneficiaries with the aim to outperform the products currently used. The workshop collaboration between Project Ô and CIRCULAR BIOCARBON highlighted innovations of relevance and potential benefit to the primary sector in Almendralejo.

Water Sustainability Public Engagement Event

The first day of the co-creation event was 15 June 2022. Policymakers and representatives from the primary sector were gathered to visit the Almendralejo Wastewater Treatment Plant (WWTP) where Project Ô's MOBILE3TECH treatment module is installed. Fourteen stakeholders participated in the event. Local partners included SOCAMEX and Urbaser.

Figure 57. Co-creation workshop in Almendralejo, Spain

Image credit: Urbaser S.A.

Figure 58. Co-creation workshop in Almendralejo, Spain

Image credit: Urbaser S.A.

Figure 59. Co-creation workshop in Almendralejo, Spain

Image credit: Urbaser S.A.

On the second day of the event, 16 June 2022, a live online workshop was held with the local Almendralejo community. This session was facilitated by the Institute for Methods Innovation team and was delivered in Spanish to maximise inclusivity, including translations for all presentation materials, such as slide decks and handouts, and the subsequent transcription of the session. The workshop provided an overview of both projects and key concepts, followed by a recorded group discussion intended to unearth attitudes and perspectives on water sustainability and solid waste reuse concerns and hopes.

Figure 60. Screenshots from the co-creation workshop in Almendralejo, Spain

Co-Creation Group Discussion Findings

The co-creation group discussion portion of the workshop asked stakeholders to consider topics in-depth, for example water availability in different areas, the economic impacts of water scarcity and decreased water quality, regulations on crops grown in different geographical areas of Almendralejo, communication strategies to engage with the public and raise awareness, and benefits of engaging with Project Ô and CIRCULAR BIOCARBON technologies. Participants were asked about their concern, hopes and expectations relating to water sustainability in their area. The key concerns are outlined below.

Water Sustainability Concerns

Participants were most concerned about **water availability** in their local area. Water availability is area-specific and does not necessarily threaten every citizen equally:

“Citizens may see their quality of life endangered. Unfortunately, this concern does not apply to everyone, as the availability of water depends on the area in which they live.” (Consumer stakeholder, Female)

Concerns about water availability exist and are a daily reality.

Participant,
Spain co-creation
workshop

The shortage of water resources were identified as more urgent in particular regions, such as Alange, Spain, where the reservoir capacity has reduced substantially:

“In Mérida, the Alange reservoir has less than 20% of its water capacity remaining. The local population is living in a critical situation.” (Industry stakeholder, Male)

Participants clarified that the level of concern about **water scarcity** depends on the geographic, social, and environmental conditions:

“The level of concern about water availability depends on geographical location and socio-environmental conditions.” (Consumer stakeholder, Female)

Participants noted concerns about the broader economic implications of water scarcity and micro-level impact on how businesses operate:

“If there is not enough water, companies could not continue their productive process and this could have broader economic impacts.” (Consumer stakeholder, Female)

In addition, participants mentioned the economic impacts of water scarcity on leisure activities:

“Leisure activities may also be affected (e.g. water parks, public swimming pools, public fountains), generating an economic impact.” (Consumer stakeholder, Female)

Furthermore, there are concerns over **water quality** as a direct consequence of water scarcity. If there is water scarcity, this would impact water quality, according to this participant:

“The lower the quantity of water, the lower the water quality because there is less volume in which pollutants can be diluted.” (Consumer stakeholder, Male)

Because of an increase in pollutants, this would mean the price of treating water will be higher:

“Higher concentrations of pollutants in water are leading to an increase in the use of chemical treatment agents, which makes water more expensive and has economic implications for both consumers and businesses.” (Industry stakeholder, Male)

As with concerns about water availability, water quality concerns are also area specific:

“There are several municipalities in which tap water cannot be consumed.” (Consumer stakeholder, Male)

Participant,
Spain co-creation workshop

In addition to concerns over water quality, participants in Spain shared concerns about the controls necessary to safeguard water quality and health:

“Poor water management/treatment can have a significant impact on public health.” (Industry stakeholder, Female)

Participants also discussed the importance of an appropriate strategy to **effectively communicate the problem of water scarcity** to shore up public confidence.

“If communication is poorly managed, it can lead to general panic.”
(Consumer stakeholder, Female)

This concern about water management in Spain being distorted for political reasons was noted repeatedly during the workshop.

“What is being communicated about the state of water is politicised and has many nuances. For example, the information given about the Guadiana river on the EU website is incorrect.”
(Industry stakeholder, Male)

One of the main concerns in this area is to have **adequate regulations of water overuse**, both for citizens and for the primary sector. There is a need to regulate wells that are built and used by citizens:

“Groundwater is being drained by wells built by citizens. Many of them are illegal or unregulated.” (Industry stakeholder, Male)

There is also a general need for consideration and solidarity between those who use water:

“People take water only for themselves and do not consider the needs of others.” (Consumer stakeholder, Male)

Different types of crops require different amounts of water, which could increase water scarcity:

“We need to start regulating the type of crops grown in the area. For example, the irrigation of avocados requires more water, which has an impact on the environment and makes production more expensive.” (Industry stakeholder, Male)

The problem lies in the choice of crops. There are crops that end up being more of a luxury than a necessity because they require a lot of water.

Participant,
Spain co-creation workshop

There are also concerns over political influences in water management:

“Water managers face political pressures that affect their final decisions.” (Industry stakeholder, Male)

Water Sustainability Hopes and Expectations

One of the main expectations mentioned was to raise **public awareness** of the problem. Storytelling is one way to raise awareness about water scarcity issues:

“It is necessary to use storytelling techniques to provoke an emotional resonance and generate collective awareness.”
(Consumer stakeholder, Female)

Another way to increase public awareness by educating people about water reuse:

“There is a need for education on responsible water use. Currently there is more indiscriminate consumption, which shows a reversal in water use behaviour.” (Industry stakeholder, Female)

Another expectation was that there would be greater awareness of **water use in irrigation** in relation to the hydrological characteristics of different geographical areas. According to this participant, indigenous crops should be prioritised over other species:

“We need to establish regulations on the type of crops grown in different geographical areas. We need to favour endemic species in order to avoid invasive species.” (Policy stakeholder, Male)

This participant agrees that crops with lower water requirements should be favoured:

“We need to find the best value for water. For example, irrigation of avocado trees in unsuitable areas can consume large volumes of water with low-volume production. On the other hand, there are crops that consume a lot of water but

We need to find the **best value for water**, where there is the right balance between cost, quality and sustainability to meet human needs.

Participant,
Spain co-creation workshop

generate a large volume of product, such as rice.” (Industry stakeholder, Female)

Participants also expressed the hope that in the near future they will be able to **avoid water loss** altogether:

“We need to prevent water loss at the domestic level and also at the industrial level.” (Industry stakeholder, Male)

Maintenance of water treatment plants should be undertaken regularly to avoid unnecessary losses:

“Water infrastructures, such as WWTPs, must be constantly maintained to ensure that not a drop of water is lost.” (Industry stakeholder, Male)

Circular economy solutions can help increase water reuse opportunities, according to this participant.

“We hope that this type of technology (referring to Project Ô water treatment module) will allow us to reuse 100% of the water.” (Industry stakeholder, Female)

Co-creation Activity Result

The final stage of the event was a co-creation activity in which participants were asked to create and share news stories about either the future of water sustainability in their local areas or innovations at the demonstration sites. The participants opted to write a news article about their hopes for a mobile tanker truck, containing the MOBILE3TECH water treatment module, that could collect wastewater from domestic septic tanks and transform it into water suitable for human needs. This particular story sheds light on their hopes to make these water treatment technologies accessible to communities.

Figure 61. News article created by participants during the co-creation workshop in Spain

THE TRUCK THAT TRANSFORMS WATER

SOCAMEX, in collaboration with the CNRS, the Polytechnic University of Valencia and the Technion in Israel, has developed a prototype tanker truck incorporating a pioneering water regeneration system called MOBILE3TECH.

This truck can collect wastewater from domestic septic tanks and transform it into water suitable for human consumption, as well as for irrigation of avocado and grapefruit fields.

The tanker can also travel to remote areas and small villages to treat water directly on site to meet the specific needs of each location.

The director of the Almendralejo WWTP, Pedro Sánchez, expects this modular solution to be replicated in 15 other municipalities in the coming year.

Citizens will be able to identify the tanker truck by means of a melody transmitted by a megaphone so that they can prepare their wastewater in advance.

Co-creation public engagement event report: Italy

A live, online co-creation event was held on 22 September 2022 with people from the Puglia region who were interested in the topic of circular water management. As in other locations, the event programme included an overview of Project Ô, a facilitated group discussion, and a co-creation activity. The first part of the programme was informational while the second part was oriented towards data collection and co-creation. All participant communications for the event, and the event itself, used the Italian language to ensure wide participation from the local community.

Figure 62. Invitation and agenda screenshots for the co-creation workshop in Puglia, Italy

Project Ô
Innovative circular water systems

Sei invitato/a a partecipare al workshop online

Introduzione al Project Ô:

Sviluppare strumenti pratici per la sostenibilità dell'acqua

PARTECIPATE TRAMITE ZOOM

DATA
22 Settembre 2022

ORA
9:00 - 12:00 (CET)

ID Riunione: 881 2272 9356
Password: 340491
Link: <https://us02web.zoom.us/j/88122729356?pwd=U3hHd25UMTEyRmE1REFxZmR6dWVvZz09>

Per qualsiasi informazione aggiuntiva, non esitate a contattarci per mail a questo indirizzo daniela@methodsinnovation.org

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Commissione europea
Programma di lavoro di ricerca e innovazione
Horizon Europe - Investimenti europei in futuro
101016923 | 2021-2025

Workshop online
Introduzione al Project Ô: Sviluppare strumenti pratici per la sostenibilità dell'acqua

PROGRAMMA:

- 09:00** Apertura e introduzioni
- 09:15** Presentazione del Project Ô
- 09:25** Discussione sulla sostenibilità dell'acqua
- 10:00** Pausa
- 10:15** Attività di co-creazione: Creazione di una notizia
- 11:00** Pausa
- 11:15** Presentazione delle notizie
- 11:30** Feedback e dibattito finale
- 11:45** Chiusura

Image credit: Daniela Martin | Institute for Methods Innovation

Local Water Sustainability Context

Groundwater resources supply over 200 wells in southern Italy and have helped to sustain the Puglia region for years. Over time, though, these wells have become contaminated with seawater and harmful bacteria. In addition, the wells are located too far away to rely on existing water treatment plants.

Project Ô's ADV.ERT filtration technology module is installed at the Cozza Guardati well in Lecce, in southern Italy's Puglia Region. This technology removes harmful bacteria and excess salt from the water. It also reduces potential harmful levels of pesticides and pharmaceuticals that could be present in the water, making it clean and safe for essential human needs such as drinking and farming. Project Ô's ADV.ERT technology can be operated as a remote unit directly at the water source, making it especially beneficial in remote locations like the wells in the Puglia region.

Water Sustainability Public Engagement Event

The live online co-creation workshop was facilitated by the Institute for Methods Innovation team and was delivered in Italian to maximise inclusivity, including local adaptations and translations for all presentation materials, such as slide decks and handouts, and the subsequent transcription of the session.

Figure 63. Screenshot from the co-creation workshop in Puglia, Italy

Co-Creation Group Discussion Findings

The group discussion portion of the workshop asked stakeholders to consider topics in-depth, including impacts of climate change on local water availability, lack of legislation on water reuse in Italy, and the need for water reuse. When asked about their perspectives on water sustainability concerns and future expectations, participants expressed the following:

Climate change is making the management, and the treatment of this resource [water] even more complex.

Participant,
Italy co-creation workshop

Water Sustainability Concerns

Climate change and its impact on water availability was one of the major concerns raised by participants during the workshop. This has an impact on water availability in the region:

“Climate change has aggravated the water scarcity situation in the Puglia region.”
(Policy stakeholder, Female)

We are a region with very little water, so I think the biggest concerns are due to this [factor].

Participant,
Italy co-creation workshop

In addition, this has affected weather patterns in the area:

“Rainfall is no longer as predictable as it used to be due to climate change. This has made water harvesting and accumulation almost impossible.” (Policy stakeholder, Male)

Another concern was the **lack of legislation on water reuse** in Italy. This participant expressed a need for increased monitoring:

“We need to monitor water bodies and water resources.” (Policy stakeholder, Male)

The more [water] we have now, the more we will have in the future.

Participant,
Italy co-creation workshop

In addition, water reuse opportunities should also be regulated:

“There is no legislation from the perspective of water reuse opportunities. For example, the issue of water conservation has not been considered in new legislatures to promote energy conservation.” (Policy stakeholder, Female)

Water Sustainability Hopes and Expectations

One of the main hopes was that there would be a growing change in attitudes and behaviour towards **water reuse**. Conserving water is everyone’s responsibility, according to this participant:

“We need everyone to start saving and reusing water as much as possible.” (Policy stakeholder, Male)

By reusing water, costs can be saved, according to this participant:

“There is a need to increase the volume of water reused in agriculture to save money.” (Policy stakeholder, Male)

In the future it would be appropriate to create a resilience plan on the only common good that truly unites all of us. It seems like we have forgotten about it: **the water.**

Participant,
Italy co-creation workshop

More water should be treated to the extent that it can be reused as drinking water:

“We could be closer to adopting a circular system if we manage to increase the volume of treated water used as drinking water.” (Policy stakeholder, Female)

Education about water reuse is also critical:

“We hope to bring about a change in the mindset of citizens. We have to make them aware that (i) reused water is of the same (if not higher) quality than what people are used to, and that (ii) the circular economy benefits the community.” (Policy stakeholder, Male)

By changing people’s mindsets, water can be increasingly reused:

“This change in citizens’ mindset can be crucial. And it can start with basic actions such as reusing water from the sink, storing rainwater for watering the garden, etc.”
(Policy stakeholder, Male)

Another hope was that water bodies would be **protected through legislation**:

“We need to pay more attention to the legislative and political side if we really want to protect water bodies.” (Policy stakeholder, Female)

Plan a project with funding in the field of water management which can be handed down over time to future generations, because they will have to deal with this criticality.

Participant,
Italy co-creation workshop

This participant suggested that water reuse be made mandatory:

“One option is to make water reuse mandatory.” (Policy stakeholder, Female)

Co-creation Activity Result

The final stage of the event was a co-creation activity in which participants were asked to create and share news stories about either the future of water sustainability in their local areas or Project Ô innovations at the demonstration site. Participants wrote a fictional story about the need for more water treatment plants in the region to meet the demand of citizens and farmers. Participants opted to write about a Utopian scenario, reflecting their hopes for water sustainability in the Puglia region, as part of the co-creation workshop in Italy. This particular story sheds light on their hopes to adopt a circular system by increasing the volume of water treated to meet human needs.

Figure 64. News article created by participants during the co-creation workshop in Italy

BY POPULAR DEMAND FROM FARMERS, A PNRR OF WATER IS BEING ENCOURAGED

The plan of investments and incentives for water reuse is adopted by more than 90 percent of Puglian farmers. There was a change of hearts, and farmers are now looking forward to using water from water treatment plants in the Puglia region. More plants are already under construction to meet this huge demand. In 2021, only 5 plants were active in giving water for reuse. To date, in addition to the 18 projects already underway, all water treatment plants have been retrofitted. The impact is huge: from 2020 to now, water reuse has increased from 5% to 80%.

How was this possible?

Citizens first began to retrofit their homes for water reuse. Farmers, inspired by this exemplary behaviour, have aligned themselves in reusing water in their working environments as well.

Co-creation public engagement event report: Croatia

A live, online co-creation workshop was held on 19 October 2022 linked to the Galeb d.d. project demosite in Croatia. The same agenda structure was used: Starting with an overview of Project Ô, then a facilitated group discussion, a co-creation activity, and a concluding discussion about water sustainability in the local area.

Figure 65. Invitation and agenda screenshots for the co-creation workshop in Omiš, Croatia

Image credit: Daniela Martin | Institute for Methods Innovation

Water Sustainability Context

In Croatia, the demosite focused on textile production. Every day, finite freshwater resources are used and discarded through unsustainable industrial production. It is especially important to reduce the impact of water-intensive industries, such as clothing. Galeb d.d., a clothing factory in Croatia, is working to increase the reuse of finite water resources by building its own water treatment plant. The technology module being deployed by Project Ô in this location is called PHOTO.CAT: This has been integrated into Galeb d.d.'s new water

The whole project is emphasising something that should be a focus for the textile industry in the upcoming years and decades.

Participant,
Croatia co-creation workshop

treatment plant. This photocatalytic unit is designed to remove harmful chemicals and organic pollutants and recover salts from the water.

The treatment process is designed to automatically mix different streams of treated water to ensure the right salt levels and temperatures for making clothing materials. These targeted treatments enable the factory's immediate reuse of the water, and also boost energy efficiency because the treated water is already optimised for clothing production.

Water Sustainability Public Engagement Event

The live online co-creation workshop was designed, organised and conducted by the Institute for Methods Innovation. The workshop allowed Project Ô to identify attitudes and expectations, anxieties and pre-knowledge about sustainability aspects of water management among stakeholders from *Galeb d.d.* Twelve stakeholders participated in this event.

None of us is looking 50 or 100 years ahead [...] this is definitely something that needs to be talked about in the public [space] and people need to be aware that what they are doing today will impact future generations.

Participant,
Croatia co-creation workshop

Figure 66. Screenshot from the co-creation workshop in Omiš, Croatia

The screenshot shows a Zoom meeting interface. On the left, a slide titled 'Welcome' displays an agenda for the workshop. On the right, a vertical list of participants is visible, including JELENAKOG, Ivana Podrug, Josip Aračić, ANTEMU, and Jelena Kristić. The bottom of the slide features logos for IMI (Institute for Methods Innovation), the website www.eu-project-o-eu, and Galeb d.d.

Welcome

Agenda:

- 09:00 Opening and introduction
- 09:15 Presentation of Project Ô and the need for water reuse
- 09:25 Discussion on water sustainability
- 10:00 Break
- 10:15 Co-creation activity: Create a news story
- 11:00 Presentation of news stories
- 11:30 Final discussion and feedback
- 11:45 Closing

IMI Institute for Methods Innovation
www.eu-project-o-eu
Galeb d.d.

Participants: JELENAKOG, Ivana Podrug, Josip Aračić, ANTEMU, Jelena Kristić

Co-Creation Group Discussion Findings

The group discussion portion of the workshop asked stakeholders to consider topics in-depth, including concerns over water scarcity and water quality, environmental concerns, and the need for public engagement.

Water Sustainability Concerns

Water scarcity and public awareness were the main concerns expressed by participants, as well as the **quality of the available water**. According to this participant, local citizens are not taking water scarcity seriously enough:

“There is not enough concern about water scarcity. This is because there are rivers and plenty of water sources in the area and people don’t realise how serious the situation really is.”

(Industry, Female)

At this point, more of a concern is the quality of the water that we are drinking [...] at this time, that is the main concern.

Participant,
Croatia co-creation workshop

“People do not have the mentality that water scarcity is possible because they have not experienced it.” (Industry, Female)

Furthermore, water quality and the protection of the environment is concerning, according to this participant:

“The quality of drinking water is the main concern. We must prioritise the protection of the environment around these water sources.” (Industry, Female)

In addition, the water reuse and circular water economy solutions should be promoted in Croatia, and the rest of the world:

“We need to promote a circular water economy and water reuse.”
(Industry, Female)

Water Sustainability Hopes and Expectations

One of the main hopes mentioned was to raise **public awareness** of the problem.

“Around the world, water scarcity should be talked about more so people know the potential threats.”
(Industry, Female)

I think the hope for everybody, not just in Croatia, but all around the world should be that we have to talk more about the potential problem of water scarcity.

Participant,
Croatia co-creation workshop

By working together and considering the needs of others, water conservation will be more achievable, according to this participant:

“People need to show more solidarity and think of others.”
(Industry, Female)

Furthermore, the textile industry in Croatia should invest in circular water economy solutions:

“More people should be aware of the importance of a circular water economy. This should also be the focus for the entire textile industry.” (Industry, Female)

Co-creation Activity Result

The final stage of the event was a co-creation activity in which participants were asked to create and share news stories about either the future of water sustainability in their local areas or Project Ô innovations at the demonstration site. The participants decided to write a press article on water treatment technologies used at *Galeb d.d.*. This particular story sheds light on their hopes to make a real impact on water sustainability and benefit their local communities by using, and possibly scaling up, water treatment technologies.

Figure 67. Fictional news created by participants in the co-creation workshop in Croatia

PROJECT Ô TECHNOLOGY IS GREAT FOR WATER PRESERVATION

Most production companies should be encouraged to implement technologies to ensure water sustainability and the protection of the environment. Technology is an effective way to preserve water. By implementing a circular water economy at Galeb, new input water isn't needed. Because production requires high volumes of water, this is a great start to saving water for the future. Furthermore, technology ensures that used water at Galeb is of better quality. There are also energy consumption savings and cost savings.

Co-creation public engagement event report: Israel

In Israel, the co-creation workshop was held on the 22 November 2022 with participants interested in the water sector in Israel (including Ardag Eilat, the Agriculture Ministry, the National Center for Mariculture, and NPO AquaculTech). The same structure was used for this event, including an informational overview of Project Ô, a facilitated group discussion, a co-creation activity, and a concluding discussion.

Figure 68. Invitation and agenda screenshots for the co-creation workshop in Eilat, Israel

Project Ô
Innovative circular water systems

You're invited to
the online workshop

Introducing Project Ô

Developing practical tools
for water sustainability

JOIN VIA ZOOM

DAY
22 November 2022

TIME
10:00 - 12:00 (Israel time)

ID Meeting: 864 6243 9565
Passcode: 248363
Link: <https://us02web.zoom.us/j/86462439565?pwd=TKwzak1seWJzeFhTR3dWL2tia2hZQT09>

If you need more information, please send organiser Lali van Zuydam (Institute for Methods Innovation) an email at lali@methodsinnovation.org

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Twitter @EUProjectO
LinkedIn /eu-project-o

www.eu-project-o.eu

The project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No. 77626

Workshop online
Introducing Project Ô: Developing practical tools for water sustainability

AGENDA:

- 10:00** Opening and introductions
- 10:15** Presentation of Project Ô
- 10:25** Discussion on water sustainability
- 11:00** Break
- 11:15** Co-creation activity: Create a news story
- 11:00** Break
- 11:15** Presentation of news stories
- 11:30** Final discussion and feedback
- 11:45** Closing

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www.eu-project-o.eu

 This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No. 770818.

Image credit: Daniela Martin | Institute for Methods Innovation

Local Water Sustainability Context

Fish farming systems are the fastest-growing food production sector in the world, providing 47% of global fish supplies. However, fish farms can produce the equivalent of 2.5 olympic swimming pools of wastewater daily, creating the conditions for significant negative environmental impacts. Traditionally, the water used in fish farming tanks is treated to convert harmful waste from fish into less toxic elements, called nitrates. Yet, these nitrates and other pollutants that remain in the water are typically released into lakes and oceans, where they can cause excessive algae and plant growth, overwhelming water-based ecosystems and harming wildlife. This is why new global environmental regulations require these nitrates to be removed from fish farming systems.

Project Ô's SALTECH technology module treats wastewater from land-based fish farms by removing nitrates, other pollutants, and excess salts from used water, which enables the water to be sustainably reused in fish tanks or to water plants. The technology also allows for valuable nutrients to be recovered from the wastewater, which can then be used as fish food or processed further to be used as biofuel or green fertilisers. Finally, the treatment process maintains a stable water temperature, which improves disease control management, resulting in bigger and healthier fish.

Participant,
Israel co-creation
workshop

Participant,
Israel co-creation workshop

The SALTECH module is installed at the National Center for Mariculture in Israel. The technology can be used in any land-based mariculture location, even systems located away from coastal land. By using Project Ô water treatment technologies, water can be reused sustainably in fish farming systems, while using less water, making full use of available nutrients, and protecting the environment from the negative impacts of harmful wastewater, thereby reducing the demands on finite resources.

Water Sustainability Public Engagement Event

The group discussion portion of the workshop asked stakeholders to consider topics in-depth, including local water availability in the desert environment, reuse of water and other mariculture byproducts/nutrients, communication strategies to engage with the public and raise awareness, and benefits of engaging with circular water economy technologies, such as those used in Project Ô.

Figure 69. Screenshot from the co-creation workshop in Eilat, Israel

Co-Creation Group Discussion Findings

Water Sustainability Concerns

According to participants, there are concerns over the **high cost of water resources**, water needed for **agricultural activities**, as well as the **deterioration of water quality** in the southern region of the country, where the city of Eilat is situated. This area is arid and freshwater sources are rare. Desalination and wastewater treatment in this area go back decades.

Freshwater is really rare [in the region], and over the past few decades, we desalinate water in order to make a living. And so from the very early stages, we had to put much emphasis on recirculating water.

Participant,
Israel co-creation workshop

We have a lack of enough water for the crops that we are growing.

Participant,
Israel co-creation workshop

This participant mentioned that water sustainability has been a concern for decades, because it is an arid area.

"It's a way of living in the Southern [region], it's a desert, freshwater is really rare, and over the past few decades, we desalinate water in order to make a living here in terms of human consumption and also for agriculture. And so from the very early stages, we had to

put much emphasis on recirculating water." (Industry stakeholder, Israel)

Another industry stakeholder reinforced this notion, suggesting that there is a strong base of support for water reuse in southern Israel:

"Water is something that has high value and we do appreciate each reuse for livelihood as well as various agricultural pathways."
(Industry stakeholder, Israel)

A policy/government participant said that the longstanding agricultural use of water had caused concerns about the quality local water supplies:

"Another issue is the use of water here in the region, for agriculture, is causing slow but evident deterioration in the quality of the water because the water comes from local wells, local sources. Continuous use of this water is gradually increasing the salinity of the soil and the water and sustainability can only be achieved by using water treatment and other sources of water, national sources of water, which is already being done." (Policy/government stakeholder, Israel)

The use of water [in the region] for agriculture is causing slow but evident deterioration in the quality of the water because the water comes from local wells. Continuous use of this water is gradually increasing the salinity of the soil and the water, and sustainability can only be achieved by using water treatment and other sources of water.

Participant,
Israel co-creation workshop

Furthermore, this participant noted a need for water resources for agriculture in the Eilat region:

"We have a lack of enough water for the crops that we are growing." (Industry stakeholder, Israel)

Another concern, mentioned by this participant is the high cost of adopting circular water solutions:

"[...] technology must be cost-effective. Otherwise, it won't enable the users to carry on their activities. They need to be profitable [...] So if costs [are] too high, it won't allow the implementation."
(Industry stakeholder, Israel)

This industry stakeholder said that the deployment of water management solutions that works for industry must account for issues of cost and logistics:

"[...] you might have your fish tanks in one place, but the water removal to another place, the freshwater needed in another area. And this adds to the complexity and to the cost because the water flows are not always synchronised [...]." (Industry stakeholder, Israel)

Water Sustainability Hopes and Expectations

Some of the hopes participants expressed include the possibility of **reusing water multiple times** and **creating alternative water loops**, such as those implemented as part of Project Ô.

This participant highlighted the value of engaging the local community about circular water economy solutions, as an important end-user:

In the hopes section, maybe a little bit of outreach and some educational programmes about water recycling projects and technologies to local schools and of course academia.

Participant,
Israel co-creation workshop

"[Hope that] outreach and some educational programmes about water recycling projects and technologies to local schools and, of course, academia [will increase awareness about water-related issues]." (Industry stakeholder, Israel)

Industry stakeholders consider water reuse technologies as crucial for water sustainability in mariculture:

"I would like to see recycling RAS [Recirculating Aquaculture System] happening in the area. The most sustainable systems are the ones that reuse [nearly] 100% of the water." (Industry stakeholder, Israel)

I would like to see recycling RAS [Recirculating Aquaculture System] happening in the area. The most sustainable systems are the ones that reuse [nearly] 100% of the water.

Participant,
Israel co-creation workshop

The project's circular water economy solution is designed to capitalise on the value of both recovering nutrients and water to maximise the benefits for industry users. Focus group

participants highlighted the potential for multiple benefits to such water reuse solutions:

"It is about recycling water and nutrients as well." (Industry stakeholder, Israel)

Co-creation Activity Result

The final stage of the event was a co-creation activity in which participants were asked to create and share a news story about either the future of water sustainability in their local areas or Project Ô innovations at the demonstration site. The participants decided to write a press article about how Project Ô innovations create opportunities for improving sustainability and the environmental footprint at the demosite in Eilat. They also included ideas for potential future projects for the reuse of resources, such as sludge and seaweed. This particular story sheds light on their hopes to have a real impact on water sustainability in their region, benefiting all local communities.

Figure 70. News article created by participants in the co-creation workshop in Israel

PROJECT Ô TECHNOLOGIES TO REDUCE ENVIRONMENTAL FOOTPRINT

Project Ô technologies have created new opportunities at the National Center for Mariculture in Eilat, Israel.

By using Project Ô technologies, a variety of fish species can be cultivated. Currently carnivorous fish, such as seabream, are cultivated, but these have a higher environmental impact than herbivorous or omnivorous fish species. Because of the variety of technologies, new ways of treating water are possible, which can allow for the cultivation of multiple fish species, with different water salinity requirements.

Furthermore, because fish farming takes place on land, away from the ocean, there is a lower environmental impact because transport and shipping distances are reduced.

The National Center for Mariculture is satisfied with what has been achieved in terms of circular water economy solutions. According to site representatives, there is a 80% recovery rate of water and Project Ô technologies are ready to be implemented in a scaled pilot system. The systems are also considered energy efficient because solar energy is being used.

Future opportunities for reuse include recovering materials from sludge, and using seaweed more widely, such as in the textile, cosmetics and bioplastics sectors.

Participant feedback survey

A feedback survey was designed and sent to all the public engagement event participants. The aim of this survey was to determine the effectiveness of the process and to improve the subsequent workshops. The most relevant results are summarised below.

Overall, most participants agreed that the events were important (90%), valuable (100%), useful (92%), relevant (100%) and fascinating (80%).

Figure 71. Participants' general feedback on the workshop (Likert scale)

In general, participants felt that they were able to actively participate (Figure 72) and that their contribution to the process was valued (Figure 73), which confirms that the expert event facilitators from IMI were critical to the success of the process.

Figure 72. 'I was able to actively participate' statement

Figure 73. 'My contribution to the process was valued' statement

When asked about factors that made it difficult for them to participate in the workshop, some participants mentioned lack of prior information as a major obstacle (Figure 74). These responses enabled the IMI team to provide more contextual information at the beginning of the events. This balanced the need to inform participants about relevant events in their community on the one hand, and the need to collect data on their own perspectives on the other.

Figure 74. 'I needed more information to fully participate' statement

International engagement events aimed at extended professional networks

As part of Project Ô's engagement and communication efforts in WP8, IMI organised two international events for extended professional networks with a focus on political communication and science advocacy relevant to water reuse. These events were foreseen in the project's Description of Action (DoA). They were public events focused on water sustainability-relevant themes such as public engagement and impact evaluation, and were enriched by the participation of internationally renowned academics and practitioners as speakers/facilitators.

Table 52. *International events overview*

International event theme	Date
Impact planning using logic models and theory of change	31 August 2022
How to make a difference in science policy with your research	21 November 2022

Participation

There was overwhelming demand to attend these international Project Ô events, greatly exceeding the attendance targets in the DoA. IMI invested considerable efforts in widely promoting the events, and had to add more spaces due to the resulting in very high demand.

Total attendance across the two international events was 536 participants, representing a wide range of professional backgrounds and organisations. Participants joined from all over the world, including the Americas (Canada, United States, Mexico, Venezuela, Brazil, Argentina, Chile, Colombia, Ecuador and Peru), Europe (Sweden, Finland, Poland, Germany, Belgium, France, Spain, Portugal, Switzerland, Italy, Ireland, Austria, Slovenia, Greece, Malta, Romania, Bulgaria and the UK), Africa (Nigeria, Zambia, Zimbabwe, South Africa, Ghana, Uganda and Kenya), Asia (Turkey, Israel, Saudi Arabia, India, Nepal, Indonesia, Philippines, South Korea and Japan) and Oceania (Australia and New Zealand).

Figure 75. Overview of countries of residence of webinar participants**Table 53.** Governmental institutions that participated in the webinar

Government	Country
European Food Safety Authority	Belgium
European Space Agency	Netherlands
District Institute of Science, Biotechnology and Health Innovation	Colombia
Department of Further and Higher Education, Research, Innovation and Science	Ireland
Science Foundation Ireland	Ireland
Gencat - Information, procedures and services of the Government of Catalonia	Spain
Oceanic Platform of the Canary Islands	Spain
California Council on Science and Technology	United States
Health Security Agency	United Kingdom
Natural England	United Kingdom
Animal & Plant Health Agency	United Kingdom
Justice Department	United Kingdom
National Health Service	United Kingdom
Innovate UK	United Kingdom
UK Research and Innovation	United Kingdom
Environment Agency	United Kingdom
Department for International Trade	United Kingdom
Hackney Council	United Kingdom

Table 54. Universities that participated in the webinar

Universities	Country
Australian National University	Australia
Swinburne University of Technology	Australia
Monash University	Australia
Melbourne University	Australia
Griffith University	Australia
Ghent University	Belgium
EAFIT University	Colombia
Savonia University of Applied Sciences	Finland
Aalto University	Finland
Munster Technological University	Germany
Weihenstephan Triesdorf University of Applied Sciences	Germany
University College Dublin	Ireland
Trinity College Dublin	Ireland
Queen's University Belfast	Ireland
Maynooth University	Ireland
University College Cork	Ireland
Royal College of Surgeons in Ireland	Ireland
University of Galway	Ireland
University of Malta	Malta
National Autonomous University of Mexico (UNAM)	Mexico
Maastricht University	Netherlands
Vrije Universiteit Amsterdam	Netherlands
Technische Universiteit Delft	Netherlands
University of Otago	New Zealand
Otago Polytechnic	New Zealand
Wrocław University of Science and Technology	Poland
University of Aveiro	Portugal
University Institute of Lisbon	Portugal
University of Coimbra	Portugal
University of Bucharest	Romania
Nanyang Academy of Fine Arts	Singapore
National Institute of Education	Singapore
Stellenbosch University	South Africa
Lund University Centre for Sustainability Studies	Sweden

Bournemouth University	United Kingdom
University of Edinburgh	United Kingdom
The Open University	United Kingdom
Durham University	United Kingdom
University of Plymouth	United Kingdom
University of Derby	United Kingdom
University of Sussex	United Kingdom
Lancaster University	United Kingdom
University of Central Lancashire	United Kingdom
King's College London	United Kingdom
University College London	United Kingdom
University of Exeter	United Kingdom
University of Portsmouth	United Kingdom
University of Oxford	United Kingdom
Liverpool John Moores University	United Kingdom
University of Leeds	United Kingdom
Coventry University	United Kingdom
University of Bristol	United Kingdom
De Montfort University	United Kingdom
Swansea University	United Kingdom
University of the West of England	United Kingdom
University of Stirling	United Kingdom
Oxford Brookes University	United Kingdom
University of Liverpool	United Kingdom
London Metropolitan University	United Kingdom
University of South Wales	United Kingdom
Manchester Metropolitan University	United Kingdom
University of Bath	United Kingdom
University of Glasgow	United Kingdom
University of Cumbria	United Kingdom
University of Bradford	United Kingdom
University of Wolverhampton	United Kingdom
University of Suffolk	United Kingdom
University of Lincoln	United Kingdom
University of Warwick	United Kingdom
University of Sheffield	United Kingdom
University of St Andrews	United Kingdom
Heriot-Watt University	United Kingdom

British Columbia Institute of Technology	United Kingdom
University of Birmingham	United Kingdom
University of Hull	United Kingdom
Keele University	United Kingdom
Scotland's Rural College	United Kingdom
University of Gloucestershire	United Kingdom
St George's, University of London	United Kingdom
University of Nottingham	United Kingdom
Nottingham Trent University	United Kingdom
University of the West of Scotland	United Kingdom
Ulster University	United Kingdom
University of Kent	United Kingdom
University of Cambridge	United Kingdom
University of East Anglia	United Kingdom
University of York	United Kingdom
Cornell University	United States
Worcester Polytechnic Institute	United States
University of California, Berkeley	United States
West Virginia University	United States

Table 55. Research organisations that participated in the webinar

Research organisations	Country
Ludwig Boltzmann Gesellschaft (LBG)	Austria
European Lung Foundation	Belgium
European Southern Observatory	Germany
DBT/Wellcome Trust India Alliance	India
SFI Research Centre in Applied Geosciences	Ireland
ADAPT Research Centre	Ireland
National Children's Research Centre	Ireland
Engineers Ireland	Ireland
Early Childhood Ireland	Ireland
European Place Observing System	Italy
Mathematics Research Centre	Mexico
Wavec Offshore Renewables	Portugal
Calouste Gulbenkian Foundation	Portugal
Africa Health Research Institute	South Africa
Barcelona Supercomputing Centre	Spain
Schweizerische Akademie der Geistes- und Sozialwissenschaften	Sweden
Health Data Research UK	United Kingdom
Great Ormond Street Hospital Children's Charity	United Kingdom
The Francis Crick Institute	United Kingdom
The Alan Turing Institute	United Kingdom
National Institute for Health and Care Research	United Kingdom
The Bat Conservation Trust	United Kingdom
Royal Botanic Gardens, Kew	United Kingdom
South Downs National Park	United Kingdom
The Pirbright Institute	United Kingdom
The Zoological Society of London	United Kingdom
UK Energy Research Centre	United Kingdom
NFU Scotland	United Kingdom
The James Hutton Institute	United Kingdom
Wellcome Sanger Institute	United Kingdom
Sage Bionetworks	United States
Aspen Institute	United States

Table 56. Industry and services organisations that participated in the webinar

Industry and services	Country
Temaiken Bioparque	Argentina
Melbourne Water	Australia
Springer Nature	United Kingdom
Inscico	Germany
Analytic Translations	Germany
Zoho Corporation Pvt	India
Sector 3 Solutions Ltd	Ireland
Kinia Learning is Life	Ireland
Saint John of God Hospitaller Services Group	Ireland
Climate and Cities	United Kingdom
Marwell Wildlife	United Kingdom
Vertigo Ventures	United Kingdom
Mindfully Wired Communications	United Kingdom
Oxentia Limited	United Kingdom
Research Your Way	United Kingdom
Covalent Creative Partnerships Ltd	United Kingdom
Brooke Hospital for Animals	United Kingdom
Gweld Communications Ltd	United Kingdom
Just Economics LLC	United States
Virgin Media	United States
STEAM Workgroup	United States
Connecticut Academy of Science and Engineering	United States

International event details: Impact planning using logic models and theory of change

On Wednesday 31 August 2022, a Project Ô-organised webinar was offered on the topic of impact planning using logic models and theory of change. It was organised primarily by the Institute for Methods Innovation on behalf of the project, working in collaboration with a company focused on research impact (Fast Track Impact) and its highly-cited CEO Professor Mark Reed.

Using water sustainability examples from Project Ô and other projects, the workshop introduced participants to powerful tools that will enable them to think systematically about their pathway to impact, including risks and assumptions they might need to take into account and indicators to help them track their progress.

Figure 76. “Impact planning using logic models and theory of change” webinar header

Image credit: Daniela Martin | Institute for Methods Innovation

Professor Mark Reed (Scotland's Rural College and Fast Track Impact) introduced participants to logic models based on his widely used impact planning template and his approach to stakeholder analysis. Dr Eric Jensen (Institute for Methods Innovation and Project Ô) introduced the theory of change approach that IMI uses to deliver evidence-based research impact activities. Prof. Reed explained how participants could co-produce a more detailed theory of change with stakeholders, and Dr. Jensen showed how theory of change can be used to evaluate impact, using a water research case study. Participants

had the opportunity to see examples of logic models and theory of change developed with researchers by Sarah Bowman (Trinity College Dublin)⁷⁹.

Figure 77. “Impact planning using logic models and theory of change” webinar screenshots

⁷⁹ Recording of the workshop is available on YouTube: https://youtu.be/m_jsRdQ1_xs

International event details: How to make a difference in science policy with your research

A second Project Ô-organised international event was organised for 21 November 2022 on the topic, How to make a difference in science policy with research⁸⁰. It was organised by the Institute for Methods Innovation on behalf of the project, with the invited speaker, renowned science policy strategist and organiser of the Science Policy Bootcamp in the United States, Dr Andrew George (Sigma Xi scientific honours society). This live event was aimed at water sustainability researchers, professionals and others interested in the links between research, innovation and public policy.

Figure 78. “How to make a difference in science policy with your research” event header

Image credit: Daniela Martin | Institute for Methods Innovation

The event addressed how researchers can make an effective plan for creating policy impact. It introduced the differences in culture between research and policy and provided tools to chart pathways to public policy impact. Dr Andrew George (Sigma Xi, a scientific society in the United States) introduced the cultural differences between research and innovation, and policy, based on his time establishing the North Carolina STEM Policy Fellowship and as a strategy consultant for the U.S. government’s National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration. Dr Eric A. Jensen (IMI/Project Ô) introduced concepts such as policy impact objectives, impact logic models and theories of

⁸⁰ Recording of the workshop is available on YouTube: <https://youtu.be/iuX68afwtmc>

change, showing how to use these concepts to develop policy impacts from research and innovation actions. Dr Jensen and Dr George provided concrete examples, drawing on their research and policy work, with Dr Jensen highlighting examples from Project Ô.

Figure 79. Screenshots from the “How to make a difference in science policy with your research” webinar

This live online workshop had the number of ‘seats’ restricted to ensure Dr Jensen and Dr George could offer sufficient support to participants to start developing their policy impact theory of change.

(T8.6) Internal Communications Report

The internal communication activities are key for working effectively at all levels in the project. Given that consortium partners were diverse both professionally and geographically, facilitating communication and a common understanding of project progress and reflections was necessary. The internal communication task requirements were established and facilitated by IMI and maintained through several channels, in addition to IRIS's project coordination internal communications.

Background

A project internal online survey was conducted in June 2019 to determine the communication expectations and capacities within the consortium. The survey was distributed twice electronically on June the 13th 2019, and on August the 7th 2019. In total, this survey was answered by 29 representatives of 21 project beneficiaries.

Based on this survey, several internal lists and resources were established including:

- Names and contacts of the public relations officers of 15 project beneficiaries.
- 16 Twitter accounts associated with Project Ô's beneficiaries (including both personal and company/department accounts), which, in total, have 96,332 followers (in October 2019).⁸¹
- 11 LinkedIn accounts associated with Project Ô's beneficiaries.
- Facebook accounts of 10 beneficiaries.
- 42 communication channels⁸² to communicate about Project Ô provided by 18 of the beneficiaries.

⁸¹ This includes a variety of institutional Twitter accounts with very different numbers of followers. The expectation is that the project will make use of this resource at certain times to announce important achievements.

⁸² This involves sustainability magazines, environmental and university events, among other potential communication channels/activities, which could be used for any communicative purpose.

- 21 related projects (about water management, circular economy, etc.) with contact details of their representatives, who are likely to create synergies with Project Ô.

With the addition of IMI to the consortium, internal project communication was dramatically increased in the form of regular email updates and newsletter dissemination to all partners and web-meetings between partners, where appropriate, to facilitate project progression. More specifically, work was done to engage project partners with WP8 contributions via supportive sub-tasks:

- **Sub-task 1:** Providing technical input for events and when communicating externally via blog posts about technical aspects, such as publications, developments and project results.
- **Sub-task 2:** Gathering media, such as providing photographs and videos, collecting testimonials and creating documentary films for each event.
- **Sub-task 3:** Supporting engagement with technical stakeholders, such as via the Project Ô LinkedIn channel and through promotion of Project Ô via engagement with ICT4Water, such as providing articles for their newsletter and boosting the Project Ô profile on the ICT4Water website.
- **Sub-task 4:** Providing translations of survey instruments, for specific communications and for event information at each demonstration site.
- **Sub-task 5:** Qualitative analysis and supporting survey data collection at each demonstration site.

Project partners were invited to support in line with their roles and capabilities, such as development and collection of new media for external project communications. For example, this support included utilising technical partners to ensure accuracy of written content that has been adapted into plain language and with gathering and generating media, such as photographs of the installations at each demonstration site. These developments connect with T8.5 and T8.6.

Newsletters

Most of the surveyed beneficiaries in 2019 agreed (45%) or strongly agreed (40%) that internal newsletters should be a source of information about Project Ô. During this last reporting period, an internal newsletter kept the consortium updated about deliverables, management decisions, upcoming events, and related news from the project community.

Four internal newsletters were sent out in 2022 (Spring, Summer, Autumn and Winter editions). Useful resources, such as project videos and images, communication materials (such as bi-fold and tri-fold brochures, and slide deck templates), links to social media content, and other consortium news (such as installation updates and event invitations) were shared with all project partners. IMI regularly invited consortium partners to share their news content, images, and project activities for use in the newsletter.

Figure 80. Internal newsletter - Spring 2022 issue

Welcome to the Project Ô consortium newsletter

Project Ô website and social media relaunched

With WP8 in full swing, we invite you to check out the new website and follow Project Ô on social media

Dear consortium colleagues,

We invite you to have a look at the [new project website](#). Website content has been updated to reach target audiences more effectively and includes a suite of graphics to use across social media channels, as well as for project events. It also includes information about all active Project Ô partners. Click on the image below visit the website.

We also invite you to **follow Project Ô on social media**, where we share informative and accessible project content. Please like and share!

We also invite you to **follow Project Ô on social media**, where we share informative and accessible project content. Please like and share!

Facebook

Twitter

LinkedIn

In addition, **we have created a media library**, where you can access high-resolution, illustrative media, videos and other useful communication materials, as bi-fold and tri-fold brochures about the project as well as useful PowerPoint templates. Feel free to use any of these resources for project events.

The infographic titled 'Water scarcity is a human-made problem' outlines solutions such as the ADVISORY MODULE, MOBILITECH MODULE, REGIONAL ANALYTIC PLATFORM, PHOTOCAT MODULE, and SALTOCH MODULE. It also lists Project Ô solutions: Customisable, Scalable, Cost-effective, and Sustainable.

We also invite you to **follow Project Ô on social media**, where we share informative and accessible project content. Please like and share!

UPCOMING EVENTS

Virtual co-creation workshop (part of WP3) *Innovative planning and governance for water reuse: Fostering the transition to the circular water economy.*

ITALY DEMOSITE

Wednesday 4 May
(9am to 1pm CET)

We also have events coming up as part of WP8 and will share more information closer to the time. For more information about the upcoming events, please contact us directly.

We are looking forward to sharing regular project updates with you.

Best wishes,
Lali van Zuydam
Communications Officer

Copyright © 2022 Project Ô. All rights reserved.
This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 776816.

Figure 81. Internal newsletter - Summer 2022 issue

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Welcome to the Project Ô consortium newsletter

Project Ô General Assembly

Dear Project Ô partner,

The Project Ô General Assembly took place remotely at the end of May 2022. Project partners and work package leaders presented updates about each aspect of the project.

Some key project updates include:

- Message from project coordinator IRIS: An in-person closing event for the project is planned in Spain (date to be confirmed).
- Installations of technologies are underway at the demosite in Italy.
- Installations at the other demosites: pilot plant installation ongoing in Israel and Spain, pilot plant installation expected in Croatia in August.
- Co-creation workshops for better planning and to facilitate the transition to a circular water economy have been completed.

DEMOSITE INSTALLATION UPDATES

Project Ô technologies installed at the demosite in Italy

Image credit: Giulia Molinari, IRIS

Caption (left to right): Nanofiltration unit, HiNaPEF unit, ADV.ERT integration, installation site
Credit: WPS lead General Assembly presentation

Project Ô's water filtration technologies have been installed at the Cozza Guardati well in Lecce, in southern Italy's Puglia Region.

Groundwater resources, like aquifers, are an important source of freshwater. Such groundwater supplies over 200 wells in southern Italy and have helped to sustain the Puglia region for years. Over time, though, these wells have become contaminated with seawater and harmful bacteria. In addition, these wells are located too far away to rely on existing water treatment plants.

Project Ô technologies remove harmful bacteria and excess salt from the water. It also reduces potential harmful levels of pesticides and pharmaceuticals that could be present in the water, making it clean and safe for essential human needs such as drinking and farming.

An added benefit of this module is that it can be moved around and installed easily in remote areas that are far from existing water treatment plants.

LATEST PROJECT Ô UPDATES

Project Ô represented at IFAT 2022
Project Ô coordinator, IRIS s.r.l. represented the project at IFAT 2022 - a trade fair for water, sewage, waste and raw materials management - in Munich, Germany.

Co-creation workshop in Croatia
A live online co-creation workshop was held with relevant stakeholders and agencies in Omiš, Croatia, one of the Project Ô demosites. During this workshop, participants discussed and identified potential solutions to problems related to the implementation of the new water loop at textile factory Galeb d.d. in Omiš. Read more [here](#).

Co-creation workshop in Israel
A live online co-creation workshop was held with relevant stakeholders and agencies in Eilat, Israel, one of the Project Ô demosites. During this workshop, participants discussed and identified potential solutions to problems related to the implementation of the new water loop at the National Center for Mariculture. Read more [here](#).

UPCOMING PROJECT Ô EVENTS

Project Ô and CIRCULAR BIOCARBON joint event (hybrid)

Wednesday 15 and Thursday 16 June

International School on Water Reuse (in person: Torino, Italy)

September 2022

Figure 82. Internal newsletter - Autumn 2022 issue

www.eu-project-o.eu

Welcome to the Project Ô consortium newsletter

Project Ô now on YouTube!

Dear Project Ô partner,

As part of the project's external communications plan, a series of video resources have been developed explaining the technologies developed as part of Project Ô as well as the sustainability assessments conducted during the project. Project partners are invited to share this content on their social media platforms.

ADV.ERT Module

The ADV.ERT module treats contaminated freshwater, including that from groundwater sources in Italy's Puglia region.

MOBILE3TECH Module

The MOBILE3TECH module was developed to treat the toxic used water produced by industry in Almedralejo in Spain.

SALTECH Module

PHOTO.CAT Unit

Other useful video resources

To ensure that Project Ô's solutions are truly sustainable, a series of sustainability evaluations, including Environmental Life Cycle, Social Life Cycle, and Life Cycle Costing assessments, were conducted to show whether the water treatment system are environmentally friendly, socially just, and economically viable. These videos explain these assessments:

Environmental Life Cycle Assessment

Life Cycle Costing Assessment

Social Life Cycle Assessment

Reminders for project partners

- Engage with Project Ô on social media: [Twitter](#), [Facebook](#) and [LinkedIn](#).
- Online [resource library](#) can be accessed on project website.
- Please send us news for the [Latest section](#) on the website.

Latest Project Ô updates

Water treatment technology installed in Lecce, Italy

RHS photo (left to right): Manuel Lai, Valter Maurino, Simone Barletta and Giulia Molinari. Image credit: IRIS s.r.l.

Project coordinator IRIS installed its water treatment technology in Lecce in Italy. This technology is cleaning contaminated groundwater at the source, restoring this valuable water resource.

From waste to resources in farming

Image credit: Yolanda Ballesteros, SOCAMEX

The event entitled "From waste to resources in the primary sector" was held in collaboration with [CIRCULAR BIOCARBON](#). The **two-day workshop** was developed to inform participants about the projects' innovations and key concepts (water sustainability and solid waste reuse), improving their awareness and clarifying their local public perspectives on these kinds of innovations.

Upcoming Project Ô events

International School on Water Reuse
(in person: Torino, Italy)

September 2022

See further details of this event [here](#)

Public Engagement Event: Italy

22 September
(9am to 12pm CET)

See further details of this event [here](#)

Public Engagement Event: Croatia

19 October
(9am to 12pm CET)

See further details of this event [here](#)

Public Engagement Event: Israel

26 October
(9am to 12pm CET)

See further details of this event [here](#)

Figure 83. Internal newsletter - Winter 2022 issue

www.eu-project-o.eu

Welcome to the Project Ô consortium newsletter

Dear Project Ô partner,

After four years of planning, developing and implementing practical tools for a circular water economy, Project Ô is nearing completion. While the project formally closes on 30 November 2022, the Project Ô website will be maintained as a source of information, the water treatment technologies will continue to have an impact on local communities at the demosites, and the networks developed throughout the project will enable water sustainability stakeholders to stay connected.

The whole WP8 team thanks you sincerely for being part of Project Ô!

New Project Ô video resources

The [Institute for Methods Innovation](#) team have created detailed versions of the videos about the Project Ô technologies and demosites. **You are invited to share this content on your social media platforms.**

ADV.ERT Module

The ADV.ERT module treats contaminated freshwater, including that from groundwater

MOBILE3TECH Module

The MOBILE3TECH module was developed to treat the toxic used water produced by

[Project Ô's website Latest section.](#)

Project Ô outputs on Zenodo

Project partners can access project outputs on open repository Zenodo. If you have any outputs to add, please send us an email at info@eu-project-o.eu. Take a look at [the Zenodo community for Project Ô](#).

[Project Ô's website Latest section.](#)

International School on Water Reuse 2022 hosted in Italy

The first International School on Water Reuse took place from 19 to 21 September 2022 at the Chemistry Department of the [Torino University](#) in Italy in collaboration with the Butterfly Area. The School was organised as part of Project Ô, and was hosted for those interested in water sustainability. Read more about this event on [Project Ô's website Latest section](#).

[Project Ô's website Latest section.](#)

Project Ô technologies lead to spin-out for Aalborg University

Xianzheng Ma, a PhD student at [Aalborg University](#), received a grant to mature "FiBrane", a membrane distillation technology based on that developed by Professor Vittorio Boffa and used in some of Project Ô's water treatment modules. Read more about it on [Project Ô's website Latest section](#).

SALTECH Module

The SALTECH module removes nitrates from land-based mariculture systems in Eilat, Israel.

PHOTO.CAT Unit

The PHOTO.CAT unit was developed to treat water used in textile production in Omis, Croatia.

You can see all project videos on the [Project Ô YouTube channel](#).

Reminders for project partners

- Engage with Project Ô on social media: [Twitter](#), [Facebook](#) and [LinkedIn](#).
- Online [resource library](#) can be accessed on project website.

Latest Project Ô updates

Co-creation events about water sustainability concerns and hopes

ITALY

On 22 September 2022, a live online co-creation workshop was held with members of [Acquedotto Galileo](#) in [Capri](#).

CROATIA

On 19 October 2022, a live online co-creation workshop was held with stakeholders from [Galeb](#) in [Dubrovnik](#).

ISRAEL

On 22 November 2022, a live online co-creation workshop was held with stakeholders interested in the technologies installed at [Eilat](#).

Upcoming Project Ô events

Project Ô site visits conducted in Eilat, Israel

[Eilat Municipality](#) and [Technion](#) – Israel Institute of Technology – have been conducting tours of the Project Ô demosite to present the project and the technology solutions implemented at the site to stakeholders in the community. The visits were focused on students from around the city of Eilat working on solving water problems in the Red Sea.

Project Ô final meeting

The final Project Ô meeting will take place on 24 and 25 January 2023 in Almdralejo, Spain. For more information, please contact project coordinator, Giulia Molinari at giulia.molinari@trisrl.eu.

Final meeting

24-25 January 2023
Almdralejo, Spain

You can read more about Project Ô on our website and social media channels

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Conclusion

In this document, we have presented the Project Ô Public Engagement and Communication Activities Report. The document began with an account of the process of communication strategy development undertaken by IMI when it joined the project as a partner during Reporting Period 2. In this first section of the report, we detailed IMI's strategies for the website and social media. In subsequent sections of the deliverable, we have shown the steps that we have taken in the project to ensure that both technical and non-technical audiences are made aware of this EU-funded investment in water sustainability and its implications. Our approach has focused on the economic, environmental, and societal impacts of the Project Ô innovations.

Beyond communication with both internal and external audiences for the project, we have also engaged directly with the public in each of the demosite locations via co-creation events. These events were used to systematically collect data on public views relevant to the project's demosite implementations and the broader concept of circular water management. Crucially, these recorded co-creation discussions enabled in-depth understanding of community views. These public engagement co-creation events highlighted key learning points, including:

Spain

- Effective public awareness and communication activities about water availability and sustainability should be increased
- Water availability affects different regions and levels of society differently
- Lack of water resources could lead to negative economic impacts
- Water regulations should be increased to curb overuse of water resources
- Circular water economy solutions can increase water reuse opportunities

Israel

- Because the Eilat region is arid, water sustainability has been a concern for decades
- There is a strong base of support for water reuse in southern Israel

- Public awareness and outreach activities should be increased
- Opportunities for reusing water multiple times should be embraced

Croatia

- Citizens are not concerned enough about water scarcity, which means there is a need for increased public awareness
- Water quality and the protection of the environment is concerning
- Circular water economy solutions should be promoted in Croatia
- By working together and considering the needs of others, water conservation will be more achievable

Italy

- Climate change impacts water availability in Italy's Puglia region
- Lack of legislation on water reuse impacts the situation in the region negatively
- There is a need for attitudinal and behavioural changes towards water reuse
- Education and increased public awareness about water reuse is crucial
- There are hopes to implement legislation to protect water bodies

We have leveraged these empirical insights in the design of project engagement and communication activities as part of our evidence-based approach. We have also shared such insights with the wider professional community involved in water sustainability efforts through international events, presentations and publications.

Acknowledgements

The Institute for Methods Innovation team would like to thank the following project partners for their contributions:

- **External communications tasks:**
 - Project coordinator IRIS s.r.l. for their review of communication assets and informing IM about project information and updates.
 - WP8 leader Professor Alexander Gerber (Rhine-Waal University of Applied Sciences) for their contributions to communication strategies and decision-making.
 - Heim.Art for participating in visual communication efforts at the demosites.

- **Event management assistance:**
 - Project Ô demosite partners for their organisational, administrative and participant recruitment support: Acquedotto Pugliese and Regione Puglia in Italy, SOCAMEX (a division of Urbaser S.A) in Spain, National Center for Mariculture in Eilat, Israel, and *Galeb d.d.* in Croatia.
 - Project coordinator IRIS s.r.l.

- **Internal project communications:**
 - Project coordinator IRIS s.r.l. for their revision of internal communication content
 - WP8 leader Professor Alexander Gerber (Rhine-Waal University of Applied Sciences) for contributions to communication strategies and decision-making.

Data Access

Results are presented in this report, and relevant anonymised datasets from the project's research can be found in the [Project Ô community](#) on the free open access repository, Zenodo.

Annexes

ADV.ERT module

Short version - Video script

Primary audience: General, non-technical public, most of who are living in EU countries.

Key aims:

- Increase general awareness of water sustainability innovation solutions that are being deployed in the EU.
- Improve attitudes about EU research and innovation investment by EU taxpayers by demonstrating how funds are being invested to solve real-world problems.

Key messages:

- There is an opportunity for reviving contaminated water sources (for drinking) using Project Ô technologies.
- This increased water reuse is beneficial for local communities.

All Project Ô videos will start with the same intro as the overview video - the water with the logo.

Voice-over	Proposed visuals
<p>[Introduction and contextualising the general problem that the Project Ô demosite situation instantiates]</p> <p>Narrator: We need <u>water</u> to <u>survive</u>. Groundwater resources, like aquifers, are an important source of freshwater. Such groundwater supplies wells all around the world.</p> <p>In southern Italy, over 200 wells dotted across the countryside have helped to <u>sustain</u> the Puglia region for years.</p> <p>Over time, though, these wells have become contaminated with seawater and harmful bacteria, and they are located too far away to rely on existing water treatment plants.</p> <p>As a result, the Puglia region has been forced to import freshwater from other locations to meet local needs. This is an unsustainable and costly short-term solution to a long-term challenge.</p>	<p>NOTE: All the visuals for this scene can be generic - don't need to be specific to Lecce</p> <p>Groundwater image</p> <p>Might include an image that shows the path from groundwater to well/human consumption. For example, the following images (1 and 2) only made specific to the region, home styles and types of wells (aquifer to well with close proximity to home/human consumption).</p> <p>Pictures/video footage from demosite</p>
<p>[What is being done about the problem?]</p> <p>Narrator: The EU-funded Project Ô focuses on customised, technology-based solutions for <u>sustainable</u> water systems.</p> <p>In Puglia, a <u>mobile</u> treatment module, combining two advanced technologies, is cleaning contaminated groundwater in a historic well, restoring this valuable resource.</p>	<p>The module diagram appears (<i>this is only a draft and will be finalised once the voice-over is approved</i>)</p>

<p>[Details of the Project Ô solution]</p> <p>Narrator: This module is designed to be moved around and can be installed easily in remote areas that are far from existing water treatment plants.</p> <p>The module's two technologies remove harmful bacteria and excess salt from the water. They also reduce potentially harmful levels of pesticides and pharmaceuticals that could be present in the water, making it clean and safe for <u>essential</u> human needs such as drinking and farming.</p>	<p>People drinking or using water</p>
<p>[Benefits of the solution - locally]</p> <p>Narrator: With Project Ô's water treatment technologies, wells across the Puglia region can again be used as a <u>sustainable</u> source of freshwater, requiring less dependence on water from sources outside the region.</p> <p>[½ second pause] By using these technologies, contaminated water is no longer discharged into the sea.</p>	<p>Landscape / Aquifers / Aqueduct / Water</p>

<p>[Project Ô technologies help close the loop on water use - global perspective]</p> <p>Narrator: Project Ô is showing how locally targeted water treatment solutions can improve <u>sustainability</u>.</p> <p>For more information about Project Ô's tailored water sustainability solutions in Croatia, Israel, Italy and Spain, sign up for updates on our website.</p>	<p>Same visuals as the <u>overview video</u> (00:32-01:10)</p>

Short version - Video script (Italian translation)

ENGLISH	ITALIAN
<p>We need <u>water</u> to <u>survive</u>. Groundwater resources, like aquifers, are an important source of freshwater. Such groundwater supplies wells all over the world.</p> <p>In southern Italy, over 200 wells dotted across the countryside have helped to <u>sustain</u> the Puglia region for years.</p> <p>Over time, though, these wells have become contaminated with seawater and harmful bacteria, and they are located too far away to rely on existing water treatment plants.</p> <p>As a result, the Puglia region has been forced to import freshwater from other locations to meet local needs. This is an unsustainable and</p>	<p>Abbiamo bisogno di <u>acqua</u> per <u>sopravvivere</u>. Le risorse idriche sotterranee, come le falde acquifere, sono un'importante fonte di acqua dolce. Queste acque sotterranee alimentano i pozzi di tutto il mondo.</p> <p>Nell'Italia meridionale, oltre 200 pozzi distribuiti in tutta la campagna hanno contribuito a <u>sostenere</u> la regione Puglia per anni.</p> <p>Con il passare del tempo, tuttavia, questi pozzi sono stati contaminati dall'acqua marina e da batteri nocivi, inoltre si trovano troppo lontani per poter dipendere dagli impianti di trattamento delle acque esistenti.</p>

<p>costly short-term solution to a long-term challenge.</p>	<p>Di conseguenza, la regione Puglia è stata costretta a importare acqua dolce da altre zone per soddisfare il fabbisogno locale. Si tratta di una soluzione a breve termine insostenibile e costosa per una sfida a lungo termine.</p>
<p>The EU-funded Project Ô focuses on customised, technology-based solutions for <u>sustainable</u> water systems.</p> <p>In Puglia, a <u>mobile</u> treatment module, combining two advanced technologies, is cleaning contaminated groundwater at the source, restoring this valuable resource.</p>	<p>Il Project Ô, finanziato dall'UE, si concentra su soluzioni personalizzate e tecnologicamente avanzate per realizzare sistemi idrici <u>sostenibili</u>.</p> <p>In Puglia, un modulo di trattamento <u>mobile</u>, in cui sono state combinate due tecnologie avanzate, sta depurando le acque sotterranee contaminate alla fonte, ripristinando questa preziosa risorsa.</p>
<p>This module is designed to be moved around and can be installed easily in remote areas that are far from existing water treatment plants.</p> <p>The module's two technologies remove harmful bacteria and excess salt from the water. They also reduce potentially harmful levels of pesticides and pharmaceuticals that could be present in the water, making it clean and safe for <u>essential</u> human needs such as drinking and farming.</p>	<p>Questo modulo è progettato per essere trasportato e può essere installato facilmente in aree remote, distanti dagli impianti di trattamento dell'acqua esistenti.</p> <p>Le due tecnologie del modulo rimuovono i batteri nocivi e il sale in eccesso dall'acqua. Inoltre, riducono i livelli potenzialmente dannosi di pesticidi e farmaci che possono essere presenti nell'acqua, rendendola pulita e sicura per i bisogni umani <u>essenziali</u>, come bere e coltivare.</p>

<p>With Project Ô's water treatment technologies, wells across the Puglia region can again be used as a <u>sustainable</u> source of freshwater, requiring less dependence on water from sources outside the region.</p> <p>[½ second pause] By using these technologies, contaminated water is no longer discharged into the sea.</p>	<p>Grazie alle tecnologie di trattamento delle acque del Progetto Ô, i pozzi della Regione Puglia possono essere nuovamente utilizzati come fonte <u>sostenibile</u> di acqua dolce, riducendo la dipendenza da fonti esterne alla regione.</p> <p>[½ second pause] Utilizzando queste tecnologie, l'acqua contaminata non viene più scaricata in mare.</p>
<p>Project Ô is showing how locally targeted water treatment solutions can improve <u>sustainability</u>.</p> <p>For more information about Project Ô's tailored water sustainability solutions in Croatia, Israel, Italy and Spain, sign up for updates on our website.</p>	<p>Il Progetto Ô sta dimostrando come soluzioni di trattamento delle acque localmente orientate possano migliorare la <u>sostenibilità</u>.</p> <p>Per maggiori informazioni sulle soluzioni personalizzate del Progetto Ô per la sostenibilità dell'acqua in Croazia, Israele, Italia e Spagna, iscrivetevi alla newsletter nel nostro sito web.</p>

Detailed version - Video script

Voice-over	Proposed visuals
<p>[Introduction and contextualising the general problem that the Project Ô demosite situation instantiates]</p> <p>Narrator: We need <u>water</u> to <u>survive</u>. Groundwater resources, like aquifers, are an important source of freshwater. Such groundwater supplies wells all around the world.</p> <p>In southern Italy, over 200 wells dotted across the countryside have helped to <u>sustain</u> the Puglia region for years.</p> <p>Over time, though, these wells have become contaminated with seawater and harmful bacteria, and they are located too far away to rely on existing water treatment plants.</p> <p>As a result, the Puglia region has been forced to import freshwater from other locations to meet local needs. This is an unsustainable and costly short-term solution to a long-term challenge.</p>	<p>Same as short version.</p>
<p>[What is being done about the problem?]</p> <p>Narrator: The EU-funded Project Ô focuses on customised, technology-based solutions for <u>sustainable</u> water systems.</p> <p>In Puglia, a mobile Advanced Tertiary Treatment module called “ADV.ERT” has been developed by technology company, IRIS, and Aalborg University. This module cleans contaminated groundwater in a range of water areas, such as historic wells.</p>	<p>Same as short version, adjusting the timing of the animation and adding partners’ logo.</p>
<p>[Details of the Project Ô solution]</p> <p>Narrator: ADV.ERT is designed to be moved around and can be installed easily in remote areas or isolated communities that are far from existing water treatment plants.</p> <p>The ADV.ERT technology uses two water treatment processes:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Nanofiltration where membranes with nanometer-sized pores remove excess salt from the water, and 	<p>Same as short version, adding module’s infographic and technology names and adjusting timing.</p> <p>Include animation about energy consumption (NEW).</p>

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● an Advanced Oxidation Process called “High-voltage Nanosecond Pulsed Electric Field”. This process uses low frequency and high voltage nano-pulses to generate a wide spectrum of very active oxidative species. These species reduce potentially harmful microorganisms, such as bacteria, and non-biodegradable pollutants, such as pesticides or pharmaceuticals. <p>These treatment processes have low electric energy consumption, making them cost effective for water reuse. The treated water is clean and safe for <u>essential</u> human needs, such as drinking and farming.</p>	
<p>[Benefits of the solution - locally]</p> <p>Narrator:</p> <p>With Project Ô’s water treatment technologies, wells across the Puglia region can again be used as a <u>sustainable</u> source of freshwater, requiring less dependence on water from sources outside the region.</p> <p>[½ second pause] By using these technologies, contaminated water is no longer discharged into the sea.</p>	Same as short version.
<p>[Project Ô technologies help close the loop on water use - global perspective]</p> <p>Narrator:</p> <p>Project Ô is showing how locally targeted water treatment solutions can improve <u>sustainability</u>.</p> <p>For more information about Project Ô’s tailored water sustainability solutions in Croatia, Israel, Italy and Spain, visit our website and sign up for updates.</p>	Same as short version.

MOBILE3TECH Module

Short version - Video script

Primary audience: General, non-technical public, most of who are living in EU countries.

Key aims:

- Increase general awareness of water sustainability innovation solutions that are being deployed in the EU.
- Improve attitudes about EU research and innovation investment by EU taxpayers by demonstrating how funds are being invested to solve real-world problems.

Key messages:

- There is an opportunity to increase water reuse and protect wastewater treatment plants using Project Ô technologies.
- This increased water reuse is beneficial for society, businesses as well as the environment.

Key Terms:

- Safe vs Unsafe (Toxic vs Non-toxic)

All Project Ô videos will start with the same intro as the overview video - the water with the logo

Voice-over	Visuals
<p>[Introduction and contextualising the general problem that the Project Ô demosite situation instantiates]</p> <p>Narrator: What happens to the water we use in our homes or businesses? To keep everyone safe, this wastewater must be treated <u>before</u> it is returned to the natural environment or sustainably <u>reused</u>.</p> <p>Water goes to nearby treatment plants after it's used, where harmful <u>organic</u> pollutants are removed.</p> <p>Normally, water treatment systems stop working properly when pollutants become too <u>concentrated</u>, as can happen with wastewater from <u>agriculture</u>. This means that the water could still be unsafe when it goes back to local rivers after it's already been treated.</p>	<p>NOTE: All the visuals for this scene can be generic - don't need to be specific to Almendralejo</p> <p>Water runoff general footage Natural environment footage - e.g. rivers/lakes looking pristine WWTP Food industry/agriculture footage, wastewater treatment plant, water discharged to river</p>

<p>[What is being done about the problem?]</p> <p>Narrator:</p> <p>The EU-funded Project Ô focuses on customised, technology-based solutions for <u>sustainable</u> water systems.</p> <p>The set of Project Ô technologies installed in Almendralejo, <u>Spain</u>, addresses many of the challenges associated with organic pollutants, and improves the cleaning and reuse of wastewater.</p>	<p>Project Ô logo</p>
<p>[Details of the Project Ô solution]</p> <p>Narrator: Project Ô technology allows early detection of excessive water pollution from local food-based industries.</p>	<p>A water safety meter appears and the needle moves from one side to the other as if it is determining how safe or unsafe the water is.</p>

Once detected, this wastewater is diverted for extra treatment before reaching the plant's main system. This new treatment step is critical to protect the plant.

A contaminated drop appears with a magnifying glass on top of it. Then, the water goes through treatment (icon TBD) until it is clean and safe. A shield appears when the voiceover mentions the word 'protect'.

This combination of early detection and as-needed extra treatment also saves energy and money by applying water cleaning technology in a targeted way.

The contaminated drop and the treatment icon appear again, side by side. A plus sign appears between them. The energy and money saving icons appear as they are mentioned.

The Project Ô solution also includes technology that adds an additional layer of treatment after the water leaves the plant's main system.

Project Ô module icon appears. A clean drop of water and a human appears.

This additional treatment enables the water to be immediately reused for vital human needs such as farming.

<p>[Benefits of the solution]</p> <p>Narrator:</p> <p>Project Ô’s technologies increase the <u>sustainable reuse</u> of wastewater by helping to ensure it is <u>thoroughly</u> and <u>efficiently cleaned</u>, so it can once again help to meet human needs. This reduces the demands on <u>finite water resources</u>.</p>	<p>thenWater being used / Water being discharged into river / Regulations</p>
<p>[Project Ô technologies help close the loop on water use - global perspective]</p> <p>Narrator:</p> <p>Project Ô is showing how locally targeted water treatment solutions can improve <u>sustainability</u>.</p> <p>For more information about Project Ô’s tailored water sustainability solutions in Croatia, Israel, Italy and Spain, sign up for updates on our website.</p>	<p>Same visuals as the <u>overview video</u> (00:32-01:10)</p>

All Project Ô videos will end with the same outro as the overview video - social media, website and funding text.

Short version - Video script (Spanish translation)

ENGLISH	SPANISH
<p>What happens to the water we use in our homes or businesses? To keep everyone safe, this wastewater must be treated <u>before</u> it is returned to the natural environment or sustainably <u>reused</u>.</p> <p>Water goes to nearby treatment plants after it's used, where harmful <u>organic</u> pollutants are removed.</p> <p>Normally, water treatment systems stop working properly when pollutants become too <u>concentrated</u>, as can happen with wastewater from <u>agriculture</u>. This means that the water could still be unsafe when it goes back to local rivers after it's already been treated.</p>	<p>¿Qué ocurre con el agua que utilizamos en nuestros hogares o empresas? Para proteger a todos, estas aguas residuales deben ser tratadas antes de ser devueltas al ambiente natural o reutilizadas de forma sostenible.</p> <p>El agua va a las plantas de tratamiento cercanas después de ser utilizada, donde se eliminan los contaminantes orgánicos nocivos.</p> <p>Normalmente, los sistemas de tratamiento de agua dejan de funcionar correctamente cuando los contaminantes se concentran demasiado, como puede ocurrir con las aguas residuales procedentes de la agricultura. Esto significa que el agua podría seguir siendo insegura cuando vuelve a los ríos locales, aún después de haber sido tratada.</p>
<p>The EU-funded Project Ô focuses on customised, technology-based solutions for <u>sustainable</u> water systems.</p> <p>The set of Project Ô technologies installed in Almendralejo, <u>Spain</u>, addresses many of the challenges associated with organic pollutants, and improves the cleaning and reuse of wastewater.</p>	<p>Project Ô, financiado por la Unión Europea, se enfoca en soluciones tecnológicas y personalizadas para sistemas de agua sostenibles.</p> <p>El conjunto de tecnologías de Project Ô, instalado en la Estación Depuradora de Aguas Residuales de Almendralejo, España, resuelve muchos de los problemas relacionados con los contaminantes orgánicos, y mejora la limpieza y reutilización de las aguas residuales.</p>
<p>Project Ô technology allows early detection of excessive water pollution from local food-based industries.</p> <p>Once detected, this wastewater is diverted for extra treatment <u>before</u> reaching the</p>	<p>La tecnología de Project Ô permite la detección temprana de contaminación excesiva del agua procedente de las industrias alimentarias locales.</p> <p>Una vez detectada, esta agua residual se desvía para recibir un tratamiento adicional</p>

<p>plant's main system. This new treatment step is critical to <u>protect</u> the plant.</p> <p>This combination of early detection and as-needed extra treatment also saves energy and money by applying water cleaning technology in a <u>targeted</u> way.</p> <p>The Project Ô solution also includes technology that adds an <u>additional</u> layer of treatment <u>after</u> the water leaves the plant's main system.</p> <p>This <u>additional</u> treatment enables the water to be <u>immediately reused</u> for <u>vital</u> human needs such as farming.</p>	<p>antes de ingresar al sistema principal de la planta. Este tratamiento es fundamental para proteger la estación depuradora.</p> <p>La combinación de detección temprana y tratamiento adicional también ahorra energía y dinero pues el agua es tratada sólo cuando es necesario.</p> <p>La solución de Project Ô también incluye una tecnología que añade una capa adicional de tratamiento después de que el agua sale del sistema de la estación principal.</p> <p>Este tratamiento permite reutilizar inmediatamente el agua para necesidades humanas primarias, como la agricultura.</p>
<p>Project Ô's technologies increase the <u>sustainable reuse</u> of wastewater by helping to ensure it is <u>thoroughly</u> and efficiently cleaned, so it can once again help to meet human needs. This reduces the demands on <u>finite water resources</u>.</p>	<p>Las tecnologías de Project Ô aumentan la reutilización sostenible de las aguas residuales, ya que contribuyen a garantizar que se limpien de forma exhaustiva y eficaz para que puedan volver a cubrir necesidades humanas. Esto reduce la demanda de recursos de agua limitados.</p>
<p>Project Ô is showing how locally targeted water treatment solutions can improve <u>sustainability</u>.</p> <p>For more information about Project Ô's tailored water sustainability solutions in Croatia, Israel, Italy and Spain, sign up for updates on our website.</p>	<p>Project Ô está demostrando cómo las soluciones locales de tratamiento del agua pueden mejorar la sostenibilidad.</p> <p>Para saber más sobre las soluciones de sostenibilidad del agua de Project Ô en Croacia, Israel, Italia y España, suscríbete a nuestro boletín en nuestro sitio web.</p>

Detailed version - Video script

Voice-over	Visuals
<p>[Introduction and contextualising the general problem that the Project Ô demosite situation instantiates]</p> <p>Narrator: What happens to the water we use in our homes or businesses? To keep everyone safe, this wastewater must be treated <u>before</u> it is returned to the natural environment or sustainably <u>reused</u>.</p> <p>Water goes to nearby treatment plants after it's used, where harmful <u>organic</u> pollutants are removed.</p> <p>Normally, water treatment systems stop working properly when pollutants become too <u>concentrated</u>, as can happen with wastewater from <u>agriculture</u>. This means that the water could still be unsafe when it goes back to local rivers after it's already been treated.</p>	<p>Same as short version.</p>
<p>[What is being done about the problem?]</p> <p>Narrator:</p> <p>The EU-funded Project Ô focuses on customised, technology-based solutions for <u>sustainable</u> water systems.</p> <p>A water treatment module called "MOBILE3TECH" was developed in a collaboration between three research institutes: the Polytechnic University of Valencia, France's National Scientific Research Centre and the Israel Institute of Technology.</p> <p>This module is installed by SOCAMEX, a service provider for water treatment located in Almendralejo, Spain, to improve the process of cleaning and reusing water.</p>	<p>Same as short version. Include a middle scene with the module name + partners' logos.</p>

<p>[Details of the Project Ô solution]</p> <p>Narrator: The water treatment plant in Almendralejo redirects samples of used water to MOBILE3TECH, which has an advanced control unit that assesses the toxicity levels as an early detection step. The control unit determines if the used water is within acceptable thresholds to go directly to the treatment plant or if pre-treatment is required.</p> <p>If used water requires pre-treatment, it will go through additional steps that reduce water toxicity levels. The first step is advanced adsorption which uses activated carbon, a low cost material, to filter contaminants from the water. The second step is an Advanced Oxidation Process called “solar photo-Fenton” which targets any remaining contaminants in the used water.</p> <p>These extra pre-treatment steps are effectively targeted to conserve energy and lower water toxicity level to thresholds that protect the treatment plant’s main system.</p> <p>Finally, MOBILE3TECH uses a tertiary treatment for advanced absorption that can remove emerging pollutants <u>after</u> the water leaves the plant’s main system.</p>	<p>Same as short version.</p> <p>Scene order:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Control unit Pre-treatment icon Technology names + icons (NEW) Energy saving Protective shield Additional filter sequence <p><u>OR could use animated infographic</u></p>
<p>[Benefits of the solution]</p> <p>Narrator:</p> <p>Project Ô’s technologies improve the <u>sustainable water reuse</u> by effectively targeting and removing contaminants in wastewater before and after treatment at plants, so used water can once again help to meet human needs. These treatment steps reduce the demands on <u>finite water resources</u> and protect the environment and human health.</p>	<p>Same as short version.</p>
<p>[Project Ô technologies help close the loop on water use - global perspective]</p> <p>Narrator:</p> <p>Project Ô is showing how locally targeted water treatment solutions can improve <u>sustainability</u>.</p> <p>For more information about Project Ô’s tailored water sustainability solutions in Croatia, Israel, Italy and Spain, visit our website and sign up for updates.</p>	<p>Same as short version.</p>

PHOTO.CAT Unit

Short version - Video script

Primary audience: General, non-technical public, most of who are living in EU countries.

Key aims:

- Increase general awareness of water sustainability innovation solutions that are being deployed in the EU.
- Improve attitudes about EU research and innovation investment by EU taxpayers by demonstrating how funds are being invested to solve real-world problems.

Key messages:

- There is an opportunity for increased water reuse (turning wastewater into a resource) using EU-funded Project Ô technologies.
- This increased water reuse is beneficial for society, businesses as well as the environment.

All Project Ô videos will start with the same intro as the overview video - the water with the logo

Voice-over	Visuals
<p>[Introduction and contextualising the general problem that the Project Ô demosite situation instantiates]</p> <p>Narrator: We need water to survive. But every day, finite freshwater resources are used and discarded through <u>unsustainable</u> industrial production.</p> <p>It is especially important to reduce the impact of water-intensive industries, such as clothing.</p> <p>For example, on average, it takes 2,700 liters of water to make a simple cotton t-shirt. That's enough water for one person to drink for 900 days.</p> <p>[Alt. version, please record as well since we don't which visuals we are going to use in the end] For example, on average, it takes 2,700 liters of water to make a simple cotton t-shirt. That's enough water for one person to drink for almost two and a half years.</p> <p>Also, the water used for clothing production is contaminated with chemicals that harm the natural environment, if left untreated.</p>	<p>NOTE: All the visuals for this scene can be generic - don't need to be specific to Omiš</p> <p>Water runoff general footage</p> <p>General footage of clothing production</p> <p>The following diagram will appear. The 900 days (represented as day calendars) will appear one by one.</p> <div data-bbox="699 958 1321 1272" data-label="Diagram"> </div> <p><i>This diagram is just a first raw sketch</i></p> <p>Textile factory footage / Wastewater discharge</p> <div data-bbox="625 1456 1013 1975" data-label="Image"> </div>

[What is being done about the problem?]

Narrator: The EU-funded Project Ô focuses on customised, technology-based solutions for sustainable water systems.

A clothing factory in **Croatia** is working to increase the reuse of finite water resources.

This factory is building its own water treatment plant using Project Ô technologies to clean water after it's been used to make material for clothing, enabling its sustainable reuse.

Project Ô logo

Demosite pictures or textile industry stock footage

[Details of the Project Ô solution]

Narrator:

Project Ô technologies in the treatment plant remove harmful chemicals and organic pollutants and recover salts from the water.

Each of the elements of the next diagram appear as they are mentioned. The salts will be animated in a way that they look as if they were extracted from the drop of water.

The treatment process is designed to automatically mix different

Two streams (or more) of water flow to a container. Two level indicators appear: one for salt, one for temperature.

streams of treated water to ensure the right salt levels and temperatures for making clothing materials.

These targeted treatments enable the factory's immediate reuse of the water, and also boost energy efficiency because the treated water is already optimised for clothing production.

Footage of factory using water

[Benefits of the solution]

Narrator: Project Ô technologies increase the factory's sustainability and efficiency because more water can be reused while requiring less energy. This reduces demands on finite freshwater resources and power supplies.

Footage of water being used

<p>[Project Ô technologies help close the loop on water use - global perspective]</p> <p>Narrator:</p> <p>Project Ô is showing how locally targeted water treatment solutions can improve <u>sustainability</u>.</p> <p>For more information about Project Ô's tailored water sustainability solutions in Croatia, Israel, Italy and Spain, sign up for updates on our website.</p>	<p>Same visuals as the <u>overview video</u> (00:32-01:10)</p>
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All Project Ô videos will end with the same outro as the overview video - social media, website and funding text.

Short version - Video script (Croatian translation)

ENGLISH	CROATIAN
<p>We need water to survive. But every day, finite freshwater resources are used and discarded through <u>unsustainable</u> industrial production.</p>	<p>Trebamo vodu da preživimo. Ali svaki dan se ograničeni resursi slatke vode koriste i rasipaju kroz neodrživu industrijsku proizvodnju.</p>
<p>It is especially important to reduce the impact of water-intensive industries, such as clothing.</p>	<p>Osobito je važno smanjiti utjecaj industrije koja intenzivno troši vodu, kao što je odjevna.</p>
<p>For example, on average, it takes 2,700 liters of water to make a simple cotton t-shirt. That's enough water for one person to drink for 900 days.</p>	<p>Na primjer, u prosjeku je potrebno 2700 litara vode za izradu jednostavne pamučne majice. To je dovoljno vode da jedna osoba pije 900 dana.</p>
<p>Also, the water used for clothing production is contaminated with chemicals that harm the natural environment, if left untreated.</p>	<p>Također, voda koja se koristi za proizvodnju odjeće je zagađena kemikalijama koje štete prirodnom okolišu, ako se ne tretira.</p>

<p>The EU-funded Project Ô focuses on customised, technology-based solutions for <u>sustainable</u> water systems.</p> <p>A clothing factory in Croatia is working to increase the <u>reuse</u> of finite water resources.</p> <p>This factory is building its own water treatment plant using Project Ô technologies to clean water after it's been used to make material for clothing, enabling its <u>sustainable</u> reuse.</p>	<p>Projekt koji financira EU Ô usmjeren je na prilagođena tehnološka rješenja za održive vodne sustave.</p> <p>Tvornica odjeće u Hrvatskoj radi na povećanju ponovnog korištenja ograničenih vodnih resursa.</p> <p>Ova tvornica gradi vlastito postrojenje za pročišćavanje vode koristeći Project Ô tehnologije za čišćenje vode nakon što je korištena za izradu materijala za odjeću, omogućujući njezinu ponovnu upotrebu na održiv način.</p>
<p>Project Ô technologies in the treatment plant remove harmful chemicals and organic pollutants and recover salts from the water.</p> <p>The treatment process is designed to automatically mix different streams of treated water to ensure the right salt levels and temperatures for making clothing materials.</p> <p>These targeted treatments enable the factory's immediate reuse of the water, and also boost <u>energy</u> efficiency because the treated water is already optimised for clothing production.</p>	<p>Projekt Ô tehnologije u postrojenju za pročišćavanje uklanjaju štetne kemikalije i organske zagađivače te obnavljaju soli iz vode.</p> <p>Proces obrade osmišljen je za automatsko miješanje različitih tokova pročišćene vode kako bi se osigurale odgovarajuće razine soli i temperature za izradu materijala za odjeću.</p> <p>Ovi ciljani tretmani omogućuju neposrednu ponovnu upotrebu vode u tvornici i također povećavaju energetska učinkovitost jer je pročišćena voda već optimizirana za proizvodnju odjeće.</p>
<p>Project Ô technologies increase the factory's <u>sustainability and efficiency</u> because <u>more</u> water can be <u>reused</u> while requiring <u>less</u> energy. This <u>reduces</u> demands on <u>finite freshwater resources</u> and power supplies.</p>	<p>Projektne Ô tehnologije povećavaju održivost i učinkovitost tvornice jer se više vode može ponovno upotrijebiti uz manje energije. Ovo smanjuje zahtjeve za ograničenim resursima slatke vode i izvorima energije.</p>

<p>Project Ô is showing how locally targeted water treatment solutions can improve <u>sustainability</u>.</p> <p>For more information about Project Ô's tailored water sustainability solutions in Croatia, Israel, Italy and Spain, sign up for updates on our website.</p>	<p>Projekt Ô pokazuje kako lokalno ciljana rješenja za pročišćavanje vode mogu poboljšati održivost.</p> <p>Za više informacija o prilagođenim rješenjima održivosti vode Projekta Ô u Hrvatskoj, Izraelu, Italiji i Španjolskoj prijavite se za ažuriranja na našoj web stranici.</p>
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Detailed version – Video script

Voice-over	Visuals
<p>[Introduction and contextualising the general problem that the Project Ô demosite situation instantiates]</p> <p>Narrator: We need water to survive. But every day, finite freshwater resources are used and discarded through <u>unsustainable</u> industrial production.</p> <p>It is especially important to reduce the impact of water-intensive industries, such as clothing.</p> <p>For example, on average, it takes 2,700 liters of water to make a simple cotton t-shirt. That’s enough water for one person to drink for 900 days.</p> <p>Also, the water used for clothing production is contaminated with chemicals that harm the natural environment, if left untreated.</p>	<p>Same as short version.</p>
<p>[What is being done about the problem?]</p> <p>Narrator: The EU-funded Project Ô focuses on customised, technology-based solutions for <u>sustainable</u> water systems.</p> <p>A clothing factory in Croatia, called Galeb, is working to increase the <u>reuse</u> of finite water resources.</p> <p>This factory is building its own water treatment plant using Project Ô technologies to clean water after the dyeing process, enabling its <u>sustainable</u> reuse.</p>	<p>Same as short version.</p>
<p>[Details of the Project Ô solution]</p> <p>Narrator:</p> <p>PHOTO.CAT is a modular unit developed by the University of Turin and Aalborg University that removes harmful chemicals from water used in textile production.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● This water treatment module is composed of a solar photoreactor that produces superoxide and hydrogen peroxide, which are capable of removing bacteria and organic pollutants from water. ● In addition, the module is equipped with a nanofiltration unit where nanoporous membranes reduce and recover salts from the water. 	<p>Same as short version.</p> <p>Scene order:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Module’s icon + name Partners’ logo (NEW) Solar photoreactor (icon + name) (NEW) Two drops with bacteria and organic pollutants Nanofiltration

<p>The combination of these two technical components allows the treatment plant to automatically combine streams of used water and ensure the salt levels and temperatures are calibrated for coloring clothing materials.</p> <p>These targeted treatments enable water reuse and boost <u>energy</u> efficiency because the treated water is ready for clothing production.</p>	<p>(icon + name) (NEW) Drop with salt Following sequences stay the same</p> <p>OR use animated <u>infographic</u></p>
<p>[Benefits of the solution]</p> <p>Narrator: Project Ô technologies increase the factory's <u>sustainability and efficiency</u> because <u>more</u> water can be <u>reused</u> while requiring <u>less</u> energy. This <u>reduces</u> demands on <u>finite freshwater resources</u> and power supplies.</p>	<p>Same as short version.</p>
<p>[Project Ô technologies help close the loop on water use - global perspective]</p> <p>Narrator:</p> <p>Project Ô is showing how locally targeted water treatment solutions can improve <u>sustainability</u>.</p> <p>For more information about Project Ô's tailored water sustainability solutions in Croatia, Israel, Italy and Spain, visit our website and sign up for updates.</p>	<p>Same as short version.</p>

SALTECH module

Short version - Video script

Primary audience: General, non-technical public, most of who are living in EU countries.

Key aims:

- Increase general awareness of water sustainability innovation solutions that are being deployed in the EU.
- Improve attitudes about EU research and innovation investment by EU taxpayers by demonstrating how funds are being invested to solve real-world problems.

Key messages:

- There is an opportunity to increase water reuse in land-based fish farming systems using Project Ô technologies.
- This increased water reuse is beneficial for society, businesses as well as the environment.

All Project Ô videos will start with the same intro as the overview video - the water with the logo

Voice-over	Visuals
<p>[Introduction and contextualising the general problem that the Project Ô demosite situation instantiates]</p> <p>Narrator: As the Earth’s population expands, access to fresh, healthy, sustainable food is an ever greater challenge. Fish farming systems are the fastest growing food production sector in the world, providing 47% of global fish supplies.</p> <p>However, fish farms produce the equivalent of 2.5 olympic swimming pools of wastewater <u>daily</u>, causing significant negative environmental impacts.</p> <p>Traditionally, the water used in fish farming tanks is treated to convert harmful waste from fish into less toxic elements, called nitrates.</p> <p>Yet, these nitrates and other pollutants that remain in the water are typically released into lakes and oceans, where they can cause excessive algae and plant growth, overwhelming water-based ecosystems and harming wildlife.</p>	<p>NOTE: All the visuals for this scene can be generic - don’t need to be specific to Eilat</p> <p>Fish farming footage</p>

<p>This is why new global environmental regulations require these nitrates to be <u>removed</u> from fish farming systems.</p>	
<p>[What is being done about the problem?] Narrator: The EU-funded Project Ô focuses on customised, technology-based solutions for <u>sustainable</u> water systems. Project Ô’s water treatment technologies are installed at the National Center for Mariculture in Israel for wastewater from land-based fish farms.</p>	<p>NCM images</p>
<p>[Details of the Project Ô solution] Narrator: Project Ô technologies remove nitrates, other pollutants and excess salts from the water, which enables it to be sustainably reused in fish tanks or to water plants.</p> <p>These technologies also allow for valuable nutrients to be recovered from the wastewater, which can then</p>	<p>Three drops of water appear, one with nitrates, another with pollutants and the last one with salts. A red cross appears as the voiceover mentions each one of them. The three drops fall on the icons of a fish tank and a plant.</p> <p>An abstract representation of “nutrients” appears on top of a wastewater stream. The nutrients are then turned into biofuel and green fertiliser.</p>

<p>be used as fish food or processed further to be used as biofuel or green fertilisers.</p> <p>This process also maintains a stable water temperature, which is very important to improve the management of disease control. This allows the fish to grow bigger and healthier.</p> <p>An added benefit of these technologies is that they require less energy to operate than those currently in use.</p>	
<p>[Benefits of the solution]</p> <p>Narrator: By using Project Ô water treatment technologies, water can be reused <u>sustainably</u> in fish farming systems. This means meeting the growing need for healthy food while using less water, protecting the environment from the negative impacts of harmful wastewater, and making full use of available</p>	<p>Fish tanks / Water discharge / Water flow</p>

<p>nutrients, thereby reducing the demands on <u>finite resources</u>.</p>	
<p>[Project Ô technologies help close the loop on water use - global perspective]</p> <p>Narrator:</p> <p>Project Ô is showing how locally targeted water treatment solutions can improve <u>sustainability</u>.</p> <p>For more information about Project Ô's tailored water sustainability solutions in Croatia, Israel, Italy and Spain, sign up for updates on our website.</p>	<p>Same visuals as the <u>overview video</u> (00:32-01:10)</p>

All Project Ô videos will end with the same outro as the overview video - social media, website and funding text.

Short version - Video script (Hebrew translation)

ENGLISH	HEBREW
<p>As the Earth's population expands, access to fresh, healthy, sustainable food is an ever greater challenge. Fish farming systems are the fastest growing food production sector in the world, providing 47% of global fish supplies.</p> <p>However, fish farms produce the equivalent of 2.5 olympic swimming pools of wastewater <u>daily</u>, causing significant negative environmental impacts.</p> <p>Traditionally, the water used in fish farming tanks is treated to convert harmful waste from fish into less toxic elements, called nitrates.</p> <p>Yet, these nitrates and other pollutants that remain in the water are typically released into lakes and oceans, where they can cause excessive algae and plant growth, overwhelming water-based ecosystems and harming wildlife.</p> <p>This is why new global environmental regulations require these nitrates to be <u>removed</u> from fish farming systems.</p>	<p>ככל שאוכלוסיית כדור הארץ מתרחבת, הגישה למזון טרי, בריא ובר-קיימא היא אתגר גדול יותר ויותר. מערכות גידול דגים הן מגזר ייצור המזון הצומח ביותר בעולם, ומספקות 47% מאספקת הדגים העולמית.</p> <p>עם זאת, חוות דגים מייצרות כמות שווה של 2.5 בריכות שחייה אולימפיות של שפכים מדי יום, מה שגורם להשפעות סביבתיות שליליות משמעותיות.</p> <p>באופן מסורתי, המים המשמשים במכלי גידול דגים מטופלים כדי להמיר פסולת מזיקה מדגים ליסודות פחות רעילים, הנקראים חנקות.</p> <p>עם זאת, החנקות האלה ומזהמים אחרים שנותרו במים משתחררים בדרך כלל לאגמים ולאוקיינוסים, שם הם יכולים לגרום לגידול מוגזם של אצות וצמחים, להציף מערכות אקולוגיות מבוססות מים ולפגוע בחיות הבר.</p> <p>זו הסיבה שתקנות סביבתיות גלובליות חדשות מחייבות את החנקות הללו להיות מוסרות ממערכות גידול דגים.</p>
<p>The EU-funded Project Ô focuses on customised, technology-based solutions for <u>sustainable</u> water systems.</p> <p>Project Ô's water treatment technologies are installed at the National Center for Mariculture in Israel for wastewater from land-based fish farms.</p>	<p>פרויקט זה במימון האיחוד האירופי מתמקד בפתרונות מותאמים אישית ומבוססים על טכנולוגיה למערכות מים בר קיימא.</p> <p>טכנולוגיות הטיפול במים של הפרויקט מותקנות במרכז הארצי לחקלאות ימית בישראל, שם מטופלים שפכים של חוות דגים יבשתיות.</p>

<p>Project Ô technologies remove nitrates, other pollutants and excess salts from the water, which enables it to be sustainably reused in fish tanks or to water plants.</p> <p>These technologies also allow for valuable nutrients to be recovered from the wastewater, which can then be used as fish food or processed further to be used as biofuel or green fertilisers.</p> <p>This process also maintains a stable water temperature, which is very important to improve the management of disease control. This allows the fish to grow bigger and healthier.</p> <p>An added benefit of these technologies is that they require less energy to operate than those currently in use.</p>	<p>הטכנולוגיות של הפרויקט מסירות מהמים חנקות, מזהמים אחרים ועודפי מלחים, ומאפשרות שימוש חוזר לצמיתות במיכלי דגים או במפעלי מים.</p> <p>טכנולוגיות אלה גם מאפשרות לשחזר חומרי מזון יקרי ערך מהשפכים, אשר לאחר מכן יכולים לשמש כמזון דגים או לעבד אותם עוד יותר כדי שישמשו כדלק ביולוגי או דשנים ירוקים.</p> <p>תהליך זה גם שומר על טמפרטורת מים יציבה, אשר חשוב מאוד כדי לשפר את ניהול בקרת המחלה. זה מאפשר לדגים לגדול ולהיות בריאים יותר.</p> <p>יתרון נוסף של טכנולוגיות אלה הוא שהן דורשות פחות אנרגיה כדי לפעול מאשר אלה הנמצאות כיום בשימוש.</p>
<p>By using Project Ô water treatment technologies, water can be reused <u>sustainably</u> in fish farming systems. This means meeting the growing need for healthy food while using less water, protecting the environment from the negative impacts of harmful wastewater, and making full use of available nutrients, thereby reducing the demands on <u>finite resources</u>.</p>	<p>על ידי שימוש בטכנולוגיות הטיפול במים של הפרויקט, ניתן לעשות שימוש חוזר במים במערכות גידול דגים. משמעות הדבר היא לתת מענה לצורך ההולך וגובר במזון בריא תוך שימוש בפחות מים, הגנה על הסביבה מפני ההשפעות השליליות של שפכים מזיקים, וניצול מלא של חומרים מזינים זמינים, ובכך להפחית את הדרישות למשאבים מוגבלים.</p>
<p>Project Ô is showing how locally targeted water treatment solutions can improve <u>sustainability</u>.</p> <p>For more information about Project Ô's tailored water sustainability solutions in Croatia, Israel, Italy and Spain, sign up for updates on our website.</p>	<p>פרויקט Ô מראה כיצד פתרונות טיפול במים ממוקדים מקומיים יכולים לשפר את הקיימות.</p> <p>למידע נוסף על פתרונות קיימות המים המותאמים אישית של הפרויקט בקרואטיה, ישראל, איטליה וספרד, הירשמו לקבלת עדכונים באתר האינטרנט שלנו.</p>

Short version - Video script (Arabic translation)

ENGLISH	ARABIC
<p>As the Earth's population expands, access to fresh, healthy , sustainable food is an ever greater challenge. Fish farming systems are the fastest growing food production sector in the world, providing 47% of global fish supplies.</p> <p>However, fish farms produce the equivalent of 2.5 olympic swimming pools of wastewater <u>daily</u>, causing significant negative environmental impacts.</p> <p>Traditionally, the water used in fish farming tanks is treated to convert harmful waste from fish into less toxic elements, called nitrates.</p> <p>Yet, these nitrates and other pollutants that remain in the water are typically released into lakes and oceans, where they can cause excessive algae and plant growth, overwhelming water-based ecosystems and harming wildlife.</p> <p>This is why new global environmental regulations require these nitrates to be <u>removed</u> from fish farming systems.</p>	<p>مع توسع سكان الأرض ، أصبح الحصول على طعام طازج وصحي ومستدام تحديًا أكبر من أي وقت مضى. أنظمة الاستزراع السمكي هي أسرع قطاع إنتاج غذائي نموًا في العالم ، حيث توفر 47٪ من الإمدادات السمكية العالمية.</p> <p>ومع ذلك ، تنتج المزارع السمكية ما يعادل 2.5 من حمامات السباحة الأولمبية من المياه العادمة يوميًا ، مما يتسبب في آثار بيئية سلبية كبيرة.</p> <p>تقليديا ، يتم معالجة المياه المستخدمة في أحواض تربية الأسماك لتحويل النفايات الضارة من الأسماك إلى عناصر أقل سمية تسمى النترات.</p> <p>ومع ذلك ، فإن هذه النترات والملوثات الأخرى التي تبقى في الماء يتم إطلاقها عادةً في البحيرات والمحيطات ، حيث يمكن أن تسبب نموًا مفرطًا للطحالب ونمو النباتات ، مما يؤدي إلى إغراق النظم البيئية القائمة على المياه والإضرار بالحياة البرية.</p> <p>هذا هو السبب في أن اللوائح البيئية العالمية الجديدة تتطلب إزالة هذه النترات من أنظمة تربية الأسماك.</p>

<p>The EU-funded Project Ô focuses on customised, technology-based solutions for <u>sustainable</u> water systems.</p> <p>Project Ô's water treatment technologies are installed at the National Center for Mariculture in Israel for wastewater from land-based fish farms.</p>	<p>يركز المشروع الممول من الاتحاد الأوروبي على حلول مخصصة قائمة على التكنولوجيا لأنظمة المياه المستدامة.</p> <p>يتم تركيب تقنيات معالجة المياه الخاصة بالمشروع في المركز الوطني لتربية الأحياء البحرية في إسرائيل من أجل المياه العادمة من المزارع السمكية البرية.</p>
<p>Project Ô technologies remove nitrates, other pollutants and excess salts from the water, which enables it to be sustainably reused in fish tanks or to water plants.</p> <p>These technologies also allow for valuable nutrients to be recovered from the wastewater, which can then be used as fish food or processed further to be used as biofuel or green fertilisers.</p> <p>This process also maintains a stable water temperature, which is very important to improve the management of disease control. This allows the fish to grow bigger and healthier.</p> <p>An added benefit of these technologies is that they require less energy to operate than those currently in use.</p>	<p>تعمل تقنيات المشروع على إزالة النترات والملوثات الأخرى والأملاح الزائدة من المياه ، مما يتيح إعادة استخدامها بشكل مستدام في خزانات الأسماك أو في محطات المياه.</p> <p>تسمح هذه التقنيات أيضًا باستعادة العناصر الغذائية القيمة من مياه الصرف ، والتي يمكن استخدامها بعد ذلك كغذاء للأسماك أو معالجتها أيضًا لاستخدامها كوقود حيوي أو أسمدة خضراء.</p> <p>تحافظ هذه العملية أيضًا على درجة حرارة ثابتة للماء ، وهو أمر مهم جدًا لتحسين إدارة مكافحة الأمراض. هذا يسمح للأسماك أن تنمو بشكل أكبر وأكثر صحة.</p> <p>ومن المزايا الإضافية لهذه التقنيات أنها تتطلب طاقة أقل للتشغيل من تلك المستخدمة حاليًا.</p>
<p>By using Project Ô water treatment technologies, water can be reused <u>sustainably</u> in fish farming systems. This means meeting the growing need for healthy food while using less water, protecting the environment from the negative impacts of harmful wastewater, and making full use of available nutrients, thereby reducing the demands on <u>finite resources</u>.</p>	<p>باستخدام تقنيات معالجة مياه المشروع ، يمكن إعادة استخدام المياه على نحو مستدام في أنظمة تربية الأسماك. وهذا يعني تلبية الحاجة المتزايدة إلى الغذاء الصحي مع استخدام كميات أقل من المياه ، وحماية البيئة من الآثار السلبية لمياه الصرف الصحي الضارة ، والاستفادة الكاملة من العناصر الغذائية المتاحة ، وبالتالي تقليل الطلب على الموارد المحدودة.</p>

<p>Project Ô is showing how locally targeted water treatment solutions can improve <u>sustainability</u>.</p> <p>For more information about Project Ô's tailored water sustainability solutions in Croatia, Israel, Italy and Spain, sign up for updates on our website.</p>	<p>يوضح المشروع كيف يمكن لحلول معالجة المياه المستهدفة محلياً أن تحسن الاستدامة.</p> <p>لمزيد من المعلومات حول حلول استدامة المياه المصممة خصيصاً من Project في كرواتيا وإسرائيل وإيطاليا وإسبانيا ، قم بالتسجيل للحصول على التحديثات على موقعنا على الإنترنت.</p>
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Detailed version - Video script

Voice-over	Visuals
<p>[Introduction and contextualising the general problem that the Project Ô demosite situation instantiates]</p> <p>Narrator: As the Earth’s population expands, access to fresh, healthy , sustainable food is an ever greater challenge. Fish farming systems are the fastest growing food production sector in the world, providing 47% of global fish supplies.</p> <p>However, fish farms produce the equivalent of 2.5 olympic swimming pools of wastewater <u>daily</u>, causing significant negative environmental impacts.</p> <p>Traditionally, the water used in fish farming tanks is treated to convert harmful waste from fish into less toxic substances, called nitrates.</p> <p>Yet, these nitrates and other pollutants that remain in the water are typically released into lakes and oceans, where they can cause excessive algae and plant growth, overwhelming water-based ecosystems and harming wildlife.</p> <p>This is why new global environmental regulations require these nitrates to be <u>removed</u> from fish farming systems.</p>	<p>Same as short version.</p>
<p>[What is being done about the problem?]</p> <p>Narrator: The EU-funded Project Ô focuses on customised, technology-based solutions for <u>sustainable</u> water systems.</p> <p>Project Ô’s water treatment module, called SALTECH, is installed at the National Center for Mariculture in Israel to treat wastewater from land-based fish farms.</p>	<p>Same as short version.</p>

<p>[Details of the Project Ô solution]</p> <p>Narrator: SALTECH, developed by technology company IRIS, Aalborg University, France’s National Scientific Research Centre and Israel’s Oceanographic and Limnological Research implements two processes:</p> <p>First, wastewater from a fish tank passes through a filter which separates solid particles and recovers valuable nutrients which can then be used as fish food or processed further to be used as biofuel or green fertiliser.</p> <p>Next, the wastewater continues to denitrification reactors, where the nitrate level is reduced. A percentage of the treated water is then discharged into the sea.</p> <p>The rest of the water, intended for reuse in the fish tanks, moves through an algae plant to further remove nitrates and then through advanced adsorption treatment using activated carbon to further clean the water.</p> <p>If the water is intended for reuse in the fish tanks, it is channeled back to the tanks. If it is intended to water crops, the water passes through two additional stages of treatment:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● an Advanced Oxidation Process called High-voltage Nanosecond Pulsed Electric Field, which generates very active oxidative species using nanosecond-pulsed electric discharges that remove potentially harmful levels of bacteria, pesticides and pharmaceuticals that could be present in the water; and ● membrane distillation where water is filtered through nanometer sized pores to remove excess salts. <p>This process also maintains a stable water temperature, which is very important to improve the management of disease control. This allows the fish to grow bigger and healthier.</p>	<p>Scene order:</p> <p>Module (icon + name) (NEW) Partners’ logos (NEW) SALTECH infographic animation adjusting final two steps (HiNaPEF) and membrane distillation</p>
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<p>An added benefit of these technologies is that they require less energy to operate than those currently in use.</p>	
<p>[Benefits of the solution] Narrator: By using Project Ô water treatment technologies, water can be reused <u>sustainably</u> in fish farming systems. This means meeting the growing need for healthy food while using less water, protecting the environment from the negative impacts of harmful wastewater, and making full use of available nutrients, thereby reducing the demands on <u>finite resources</u>.</p>	<p>Same as short version.</p>
<p>[Project Ô technologies help close the loop on water use - global perspective] Narrator: Project Ô is showing how locally targeted water treatment solutions can improve <u>sustainability</u>. For more information about Project Ô's tailored water sustainability solutions in Croatia, Israel, Italy and Spain, visit our website and sign up for updates.</p>	<p>Same as short version.</p>